

Proceedings of 2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023)

(APRIL 07 – 09, 2023)

Jointly Organized By

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

(Estd. 25 Aug 1969 - (Affiliated To D.D.U. Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur(U.P.) | B++ with C.G.P.A. 2.84)

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Science Tech Institute, Lucknow UP

(Run by: Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society)

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860, Reg. No. LUC/03140/2019-2020, INDIA)

(Registered by : : Govt. of India , NITI Aayog, Reg. No. UP/2019/0248444)

दिविजयनाथ स्नातकोत्तर महाविद्यालय, गोरखपुर
शिक्षकगण
सत्र 2022-23

Edited by

Prof. (Dr.) Parikshit Singh
Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav

**Proceeding of 2nd International Conference on Advance
Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023)**

Editors

Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh
Professor
Dept. of Botany
,Digvijay Nath P.G College Gorakhpur, UP, India

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary
MKSES Educational Society,
Lucknow, UP, India

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav
Assistant Professor
Department of Statistics & Demography
NIHFW, New Delhi

2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023))

(April 07-09, 2023)

Jointly organized by

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

(Estd.25 Aug 1969 - (Affiliated To D.D.U. Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur (U.P.) | B++ with C.G.P.A. 2.84)

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Science Tech Institute

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(Registered by: Govt. of India, NITI Aayog, Reg. No. UP/2019/0248444)

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur was established on 25th August, 1969 by the managing committee constituted under Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur. It is situated in civil lines, the heart of Gorakhpur city in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Days are not far when the college shall be able to realize the vision and the grand mission of the great soul 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj', whose name decorates the identity of the College. His Holiness 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj, former Head Priest of world fame Shree Guru Goraksh Nath Temple, Gorakhpur was the founder of the college. He was a pioneer of educational renaissance in Eastern U.P. It was none other than himself who established Maha Rana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur in 1932 to spread the light of knowledge and awareness among the people of Eastern U.P. whom he found to be living in utter poverty, ignorance and backwardness of all kinds. He came to Gorakhnath temple, Gorakhpur at the age of five from the Royal Rana Family of Mewar, Rajasthan in 1900 and grew and learnt the lesson of selfless sacrifice and dedication to the service of humanity under the spiritual care of his accomplished great Guru Yogiraj Gambhir Nathji Maharaj. In 1949-50 Maharana Pratap Degree College was established by "Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad Gorakhpur", which was later sacrificed to contribute to the establishment of Gorakhpur University. Maharana Pratap Degree College along with its entire infrastructure including teaching and non-teaching staff was dedicated to count for the resources to meet up the requirements for establishment of the University of Gorakhpur, in 1958. Post-merger of the Maharana Pratap Degree College into Gorakhpur University, there was a vacuum in the educational facilities of the area. To fill in this vacuum, Digvijai Nath College was established on 25th August 1969. Now the administration of this college is run by the managing committee appointed by Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, under inspiring guidance and patronage of His Holiness Mahant Aditya Nath ji Maharaj. His holiness Gorakshpeethadheeshwar 'Brahmleen Mahant Avedya Nathji Maharaj (the Ex-Head priest of Gorakhnath Temple) and his worthy successor who is the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh His Holiness reverent Yogi Aditya Nath ji Maharaj, is the guiding light behind more than four dozen institutions, including D.N.P.G. College Gorakhpur, successfully run by the Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad. The College holds the glory of functioning with four faculty disciplines covering various departments at undergraduate and post graduate levels. College provides education at graduate level in eleven subjects covering Arts, six in Science and Commerce. Post Graduate teaching is offered in Ancient History Archeology & Culture, Geography and Hindi & Modern Indian Language; apart from its renowned Bachelors in Education. In addition to these, part time classes in eight non-practical subjects are also offered and the Institution also serves as an education center of Uttar Pradesh Rajarshi Tandon Open University; and hosts their 26 courses at U.G and P.G. level. In light of letter dated 15 June 2006 from U.P. State Council for Higher Education we revised 'The Self Study Report' on modified format on the basis of guidelines of

NAAC-Bangalore. Digvijai Nath P.G. college, Civil lines, Gorakhpur has been placed on the UGC-NAAC approved list in 2021 with B⁺⁺ grade with C.G.P.A 2.84. Gorakhnath sahyik kendra is established by UP Hindi Sansthan Lucknow in 2019. The institution, guided by the vision of Brahmleen Digvijay Nath Ji Maharaj, is a believer in multi-dimensional development of students. His vision of 'healthy mind residing in a healthy body' is relied and practiced by the Institution. Beyond books and classes students are groomed by extra-curricular and co-curricular activities. Students have participated in Inter-University and Inter-State games & sports as well as in the prestigious republic day parade in the National capital. Students of the college participate and compete with the students of other colleges of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, in different competitions organized during Founder's Week every year from 4th to 10th December. Institution also hosts an annual sports festival. To meet the Post-Accreditation requirements, the College also has the Internal Quality Assurance Cell. IQAC maneuvers to assure the internal quality of Academic and Administrative activities through its different committees at college.

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow UP

(Run by: Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society)

The Science-Tech is one of the premier institutes of Lucknow dedicated to organize various academic activities like conferences, seminars, workshops and training programmes in collaboration with many national & international organizations and Institute have own Publication house and Journals' to be published Edited books, Course books and research papers. The institute is run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow. The society is working for the development of deprived socio-economic students by providing them quality education.

2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023)

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP are going to organize 2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023). This Conference will provide a platform to the researchers and academicians to enrich their methodological and analytical skills. Currently, the research fraternity is missing their lively and interactive conference due to COVID-19 Pandemic. To address the present situation we are conducting this 2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023) for faculty members, research scholars and students of all the disciplines in the country and abroad from April 07- 09, 2023.

As we are aware about the fact that currently world is suffering from Covid-19 pandemic. This has brought us to a juncture where innovation and interdisciplinary research are crucial for the survival of humanity. It has become a moral imperative these days to have exchange of ideas using available advanced technologies. Hence the global scientific community must become a key player on scientific and technological innovations, not only to combat the COVID-19 emergency, but also to impart true education to the academia and industry across the globe. In the era of social distancing, **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, U.P. & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, U.P.** India has chosen an e-platform for the scientific community to share their ideas and research by organizing a three day **2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023)** Conference will include Keynote lectures, Invited lectures, Oral presentations and Poster presentations.

Chief Patron

Mahanth Yogi Aditya Nath Ji Maharaj, Manager/ Secretary, Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Patron

Prof. Udai Pratap Singh, President, Maharana Pratap Siksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, UP, Former Vice Chancler, V.B.S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur

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Prof.(Dr.).Om Prakash Singh, Principal, Digvijay Nath P.G, College Gorakhpur, UP

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Mrs. Shweta Singh, Chairman, Governing Body, MKSES Educational Society, Lucknow, UP, India

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1. Prof. D.S. Hooda, Former, (Pro-Vice Chancellor) Kurukshetra University, Haryana, India
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4. Prof. R. K. Shukla (Professor, Department of Physics, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, UP)
5. Prof. C.K. Dixit, Dean & Head, DSMR University, Lucknow, India
6. Prof. R.R. Singh, Professor & Head, D.S.M.N.R.U, Lucknow, UP, India

Convener

- ❖ **Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh**, Professor Dept. of Botany, Digvijay Nath P.G College Gorakhpur, UP, India

Organizing Secretary

- ❖ **Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh**, General Secretary, Science Tech Institute, MKSES Educational Society Lucknow, UP, India
- ❖ **Dr. Dharmendra Kr. Yadav**, Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics & Demography NIHF, New Delhi

Conference Organizer

- ❖ Dr. Shubhranshu Shekhar Assistant Professor Dept. of Defence and Strategic Studies DNPG College, Gorakhpur
- ❖ Dr. Dilshad Ahmad Associate Professor Dept. of Commerce AIDC, Lucknow, UP India
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- ❖ Dr. Abhay Kumar Malviya, Assistant Professor, Dept of Commerce, Digvijay Nath PG College Gorakhpur, UP, India
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- ❖ Mr.Jitendra Kumar Pandey, Assistant Professor. Dept. of Geography, Digvijay Nath P.G. College Gorakhpur, UP, India
- ❖ Mr.Rakesh Kumar Singh, Assistant Professor, B.ed. Department, Digvijay Nath PG College Gorakhpur, UP, India
- ❖ Mr.Himanshu Yadav, Assistant Professor, Dept .of Zoology, Digvijay Nath P.G. College Gorakhpur, UP, India
- ❖ Dr. Rashmi Singh, Associate Professor, Amity University, Noida, India
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- ❖ Dr. Alka Singh Bhatt, Assistant Professor,Amity Business School, Amity University Lucknow, UP, India
- ❖ Dr. Shiba Sethi, Assistant Professor, SK Government Medical College,Sikar, Rajasthan, India
- ❖ Dr. Uma, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Agronomy, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Agra, U.P.

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 Prof. A.P. Mishra, Sagar University, India

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Prof. D.K. Awasthi, Jai Naryan PG College, Lucknow, UP
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Dr. Kaushiki Singh Assistant Professor,Dept. of Commerce, D.SM.N.R.U, Lucknow, UP, India
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Dr. Mahendra Agnihotri, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, UP, India
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Dr. K.K Yadav, Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Institute of Medical Sciences, Lucknow
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Dr. Zeenat Kashmeeri Dada Ramchand Bakhru Sindhu Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur
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Dr. Mohd Naseem Siddiqui, Mumtaz P.G.College, Lucknow
Dr. K.C. Dubey, Shia PG College, Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. Tanveer Hasan, Shia PG College, Lucknow, UP, India

Local Advisory Committee

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Prof. Dharendra Singh ,Head of the Department History, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Prof. Geeta Singh, Head of the Department B.Ed., DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Prof. Archana Singh, Head of the Department Sociology, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Prof. Satyendra Pratap Singh, Head of the Department Hindi, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Singh , Head of the Department Commerce DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
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Dr. Anita Kumari , Head of the Department Zoology, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr. Nitesh Shukla , Head of the Department Physics, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr Suraj Kumar Shukla , Head of the Department of Mathematics, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr. Ram Prasad Yadav, Head of the Department of Defence, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Shri Indresh Kumar, Head of the Department of Political Science, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr. Anil Bhaskar, Head of the Department of Geography, DNPG College, Gorakhpur

UP, India

Dr. Nidhi Rai, Head of the Department of Education, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Dr. Piyush Kumar Singh, Head of the Department of English, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Dr. Vivek Kumar Shahi, Head of the Department of Psychology, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Dr. Pawan Kumar Pandey, Head of the Department of Computer Science, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Dr. Harishnkar Gupta, Head of the Department of BCA, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Shri Awadhesh Kumar Shukla, Head of the Department of Physical Education, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

❖ **Awards**

- 1. Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society Award for Best Research Presentation
“Theme based” (₹1500/- Cash Prize).**

DIGVIJAI NATH POST GRADUATE COLLEGE

GORAKHPUR-273001

(NAAC B++ Accredited College)

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website : www.dnpgcollege.edu.in

Affiliated to

D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Ref. No. : /2022-23

Date :22-03-2023

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023) during April 07-09, 2023**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to National and International students, Academicians, Researchers and Industrialists to interact and involve in research and innovation. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge and work experience in the field of research, analytics and innovation. I sincerely appreciate the humble efforts of the Institute in providing a platform for students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to share their ideas and research outcome through the forum of this Conference. I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Prof.(Dr.).Om Prakash Singh
Principal

DIGVIJAI NATH POST GRADUATE COLLEGE

GORAKHPUR-273001

(NAAC B⁺⁺ Accredited College)

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Affiliated to

D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Ref. No. : /2022-23

Date : 22-03-2023

Message

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Prof. Udai Pratap Singh
President

Maharana Pratap Siksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, UP
Former Vice Chancler
V.B.S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur

DIGVIJAI NATH POST GRADUATE COLLEGE

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Affiliated to

D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Ref. No. : /2022-23

Date :22-03-2023

Message

I'm incredibly happy to send my greetings on this historic occasion to the core committee of the share that Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP are going to organize 2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023) during April 07-09, 2023. In current scenario interdisciplinary research is foundation of every country and humanity has directly benefited from its results. Interdisciplinary research grounding and education are essential to future competitiveness, because knowledge creation and innovation frequently occur at the interface of disciplines. Inter disciplinary agendas widen the horizon of knowledge and aids to ensure better educational programs. This conference offered opportunity to connect all researchers, scientists and faculties together at one single platform to share their innovative ideas and skills which is helpful to carry out future research in well-organized way.

Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh

Professor

Convenor IQAC

Prof. (Dr) Chandra. K. Dixit,
Dean Faculty Science
Dr. Shakuntala Misra National Rehabilitation University,
Lucknow

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023)**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to national and international students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to interact and involve in Research and Innovation. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge and work experience in the field of Research, Analytics and Innovation.

I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Date: 23/03/2023

Prof.(Dr.) C. K. Dixit

University of Lucknow
Lucknow, UP, India, 226007

Department of Commerce
Lucknow University
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Email: Prof.someshshukla@gmail.com

Prof. Somesh Kumar Shukla
Director,
Bhao Rao Devras Shodhpeeth
University of Lucknow,
Lucknow,
UP, India

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023) during April 07-09, 2023**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to national and international students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to interact and involve in Research and Innovation. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge and work experience in the field of Research, Analytics and Innovation. I sincerely appreciate the humble efforts of the Institute in providing a platform for students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to share their ideas and research outcome through the forum of this Conference. I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Date: 25/03/2023

[Prof. Somesh Kumar Shukla]

लखनऊ विश्वविद्यालय
University of Lucknow

Department of Physics
University of Lucknow
Lucknow-226007 U.P. (India)

Mobile No. 09451309994
Email: rajeshkumarshukla_100@yahoo.com

Prof. R. K. Shukla,
Professor,
University of Lucknow, UP

Message

It is indeed matter of great pleasure that the **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023)** during **April 07-09, 2023**. The invited speakers are experts in their area of specialization. I hope that the interaction between various participants will serve as a springboard for newer opportunities and challenges. I am confident that the participants of this conference and students will greatly benefit from attending this meeting and interacting with experts in the field. I compliment organizing committee for this great effort.

Your sincerely

[R. K. Shukla]

Date: 05/04/2023

MANRAJ KUWAR SINGH EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860)

Reg. Office : Hydell Nahar Chauraha, Housing Society Sarojini Nagar, Lucknow - 226008, UP India

Head Office : 1ST Floor Building No.85 A (Nanak Arcade) Near Shani Mandir,
Parag Road, LDA Colony, Kanpur Road, Lucknow-226012, UP India

Contact No. : +91 9838298016, +91 8299547952 | E-mail : manrajkuwarsec@gmail.com

Mrs. Shweta Singh
Chairman,
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP, India

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to share that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023) during April 07-09, 2023.**

The conference will offer a great opportunity to discuss important issues, researches and topics from varied fields and will allow exchange of knowledge, ideas.

This conference is also an opportunity to meet virtually many eminent faculty, scholars and public health specialists of national and international repute on a common platform.

I & my team ensure that the audience will experience the exchange of scientific knowledge and return with a satisfactory take home message.

[Shweta Singh]

Date: 05/04/2023

SCIENCE TECH INSTITUTE

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. Higher Education Department & Ordinance No. 8 of 2002)

Run by : **MANRAJ KUWAR SINGH EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY**

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Reg. Office : Hydell Nahar Chauraha, Housing Society Sarojini Nagar, Lucknow - 226008, UP India

Head Office : 1ST Floor Building No.85 A (Nanak Arcade) Near Shani Mandir,

Parag Road, LDA Colony, Kanpur Road, Lucknow-226012, UP India

Contact No. : +91 9838298016, +91 8299547952 | E-mail : sciencetech487@gmail.com

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary,
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP

Message

On behalf of the whole organizing team, share that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023) during April 07-09, 2023.**

I am sure that this online gathering will provide a common platform for academicians of different branches (Medical Sciences, Humanities etc.), public health experts & researchers to put forth their research studies and works.

I take this opportunity to acknowledge all the concerned authorities or persons for their permission, continuous support and guidance in arranging this conference. I am sure that this conference will succeed in the walk on Commerce this path for improving the various soft skills of faculties and students in varied fields.

Date: 04/04/2023

[Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh]

Dr. Neha Singh (PhD, Postdoc)
(Sr. Scientist)
Virology lab, Dept. of Microbiology
Pt. JNM, Medical College, Raipur, C.G. India
Email: nevi0007@gmail.com

Message

I'm incredibly happy to send my greetings on this historic occasion to the core committee of the share that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to **organize 2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023) during April 07-09, 2023**. In current scenario interdisciplinary research is foundation of every country and humanity has directly benefited from its results. Interdisciplinary research grounding and education are essential to future competitiveness, because knowledge creation and innovation frequently occur at the interface of disciplines. Interdisciplinary agendas widen the horizon of knowledge and aids to ensure better educational programs. This conference offered opportunity to connect all researchers, scientists and faculties together at one single platform to share their innovative ideas and skills which is helpful to carry out future research in well-organized way.

Date:03/04/2023

Dr. Neha Singh

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav
Assistant Professor
National Institute of Health & Family Welfare
(NIHFW), New Delhi, India
Email: drdkyadav@nihfw.org

Organizing Secretary-ICAIR-23

Message

I feel great pleasure and pride in hosting the **International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023)** during April 07-09, 2023, organized by **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize. The conference is envisaged to be a congregation of academicians, researches, practitioners, educators and students. The deliberations and discussions shall enable the participants to take up new challenges and initiatives in the field of interdisciplinary research. We are pleased to present this souvenir to the academic and research community. The abstract of the papers included shall be helpful to chart a road-map in future. I welcome you all in **ICAIR-2023** and hope that your presence turns out to be intellectually stimulating and professionally enriching. I am sure **ICAIR-2023** leaves long lasting memories and a strong legacy to emulate.

Date:05/04/2023

[D. K. Yadav]

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

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2nd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2023)

Details of Program

Schedule DAY-1

(7th April, 2023)

For Technical Support Contact

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh (8299547952)

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav (8840112492)

WhatsApp group Chat link: <https://chat.whatsapp.com/HYtO0q8i6Y19468Y1Wb01E>

Inaugural Session Hosted by: Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83682456140?pwd=N0lHaZibm52RDdGeDFycVQrNjF6dz09>

Meeting id- 879 0963 7493

Password- 034792

11:15 AM	INAUGURATION AND WELCOME ADDRESS BY Conference Chair/Conveners/ Organizing Secretaries
11:45-12:15 PM Key Note Speaker	Prof. Sharvari Shukla (Director and Professor) Symbiosis Statistical Institute (SSI)
12:15-12.45 PM IT01	Prof. N.B. Singh: - “Green synthesized Silver Nanoparticles and their Applications “
Session Chair Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83682456140?pwd=N0lHaZibm52RDdGeDFycVQrNjF6dz09 Meeting id- 879 0963 7493 Password- 034792	
12:45-1:10 PM IT02	Dr. Neha Singh: - “COVID-19 and Pregnancy: Placental Histopathological Features and Adverse Outcomes”
1:10-1:35 PM IT03	Dr. S.K Yadav :- “Different Sampling Techniques in Research”
1.35-2.00 PM IT04	Dr.Kamakhya Prakash Mishra:-“Microstrain and Optical Properties of RE Doped ZnO Nanostructures”

2.00 to 3.30 PM Day 1 (7th April,2023)

Session Chair: Prof. Susheel kr. Singh

Dr. Dinesh Kumar Singh

Mobile No.- 9450210623

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83682456140?pwd=N0lHalZibm52RDRCGeDFycVOrNjF6dz09>

Meeting id- 879 0963 7493 Password- 034792

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A1	Dr. Lini G.R	Parental intervention and sustainable development :A case study among children in Female headed household
A2	Dr. ASHWINI KUMAR	Charged particle fluctuation in heavy ion collisions
A3	Dr. ANU SAINI	Facile Synthesis of Imine linked Naphthalimide Derivatives Based Hybrid Nanoparticles: Determination of Chloramphenicol in Milk Samples
A4	Dr. Sunitha K	To study the aggressive behavioural changes observed in school children between 8-18years age after the restart of offline regular classes post covid -19 lockdown r
A5	Mrs. Soma karan	Agrilture
A6	Dr. Anoop Kumar	Screening of some antipathogenic botanicals invitro and field conditions against colletotrichum falcatum causing Red rot of sugarcane
A7	Dr. Rajesh Chaudhary	I will submit it later
A8	Dr. Monika Mishra	A questionnaire based survey on student's opinion on the prevailing methods in medical education during Covid Pandemic
A9	Dr. Susmita Abhijit Mandavgane	Comparative study of degradation of ortho toluic acid and para toluic acid by Ozonation, Peroxone, Photo-ozonation and Photo-peroxone Processes

2.30 to 3.30 PM Day 1 (7th April,2023) **Parallel Session**

Session Chair: Dr. Shweta Singh

Email: susheelsingh489@gmail.com

Mobile No.- 8299547952 **Oral**

Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us04web.zoom.us/j/71341807449?pwd=jmCTW0bV051VpwYWbAh2Uawsgl7rlz.1>

Meeting id- 713 4180 7449 Password: 3kCmLW Note:

You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A10	Dr. Anandhi Santhosh	Mathematical Modelling on the Interaction between Tomato Fruit Borer and Biological Pest Control
A11	Mrs. JYOTHI MANI VG	PLANT DISEASE PREDICTION USING DEEP LEARNING
A12	Dr. Dr.Shantala Herlekar	Anaemia among working women with different job ranking, prevalence and grading.
A13	Dr. Munish Kumar	I will submit later
A14	Dr. Sattyam Wankhade	Evaluation of effect of grafting materials on implant stability and bone regeneration in patients with transcresal approach for sinus augmentation at three different time intervals - An Experimental study
A15	Mrs. Srilatha Toomula	Crop Yield Prediction using Machine Learning Techniques

3.30 to 4.30 PM Day-1 (7th April,2023)

Session Chair: Dr. Seema Tripathi

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83682456140?pwd=N0lHaIZibm52RDRGeDFycVQrNjF6dz09>

Meeting id- 879 0963 7493 Password- 034792

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A16	Dr. Ritu Mahajan	Phytochemical analysis and evaluation of antioxidant activity in methanolic extracts of <i>Macrotyloma uniflorum</i> (Lam)
A17	Prof. Geetu Gambhir	A Study of thermal stability of multi component Functionalized Biocomposite materials
A18	Mrs. M.NAZEEM BANU	REUSABLE VERSUS DISPOSABLE SURGICAL GOWNS: A PREFERENCE COMPARISON AMONG THE SURGICAL STAFF BASED ON COMFORT AND PROTECTION PERFORMANCES OF THE SURGICAL GOWNS
A19	Dr. SHREE PRAKASH	Decoding the Economic Revitalization Strategy of Uttar Pradesh: Opportunities and Challenges
A20	Dr. Manisha Verma	A Study of thermal stability of multi component Functionalized Biocomposite materials
A21	Dr. Aradhana Anuraag Gokhale	Development of Modules for Understanding the Concept of Staff Meeting Among B.Ed. Student-teachers.

3.30 to 4.30 PM Day1 (7th April,2 023)

Parallel Session

Session Chair : Dr. S.K. Singh

Email: susheelsingh487@gmail.com

Oral Presentation

Mobile Number: 8299547952

Zoom link:

<https://us04web.zoom.us/j/72972296721?pwd=63J7vcbac0t3p2g5sP55gQxovI0Fct.1>

Meeting id- 729 7229 6721 Passwords6fBs

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A22	Prof. Jagmohan Singh Negi	Analysis of Soil Samples for its Physico-Chemical Parameters from Kumaun region Uttarakhand, India.
A23	Miss. Sneha Kulkarni	China and International Law and Order: A Case Study of South China Sea and Indian Ocean Region
A24	Dr. Premalatha B.R	Collaboration of AYUSH with Dentistry: An Evidence-based Perspective
A25	Dr. ANITA KUMARI	Covid 19: Neurological and Psychological Effects (A Review Study)
A26	Miss. Shweta Chauhan	Factors affecting job satisfaction & job loyalty of employees in higher education
A27	Dr. Yogesh S, Ingole	Occlusal Wear of CAD-CAM fabricated restorations.

4.30-5.00 PM INVITED TALK (IT05-IT06)

Session Chair: Dr. Shiba Shethi
Mobile No. 7082859537

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83682456140?pwd=N0lHaIZibm52RDRGeDFycVQrNjF6dz09>

Meeting id- 879 0963 7493 Password- 034792

IT 05: Prof. Mohammad Miyan: - "MOTION OF HYDRODYNAMIC FLUID FOR ROTATORY THEORY OF INCLINED BEARINGS"

IT06: Dr. Puspendra Singh: "Synthesis and Characterization of Unsymmetrical Selenoether"

IT 07: Abhilasha Motghare: "Evaluation of NIPE in pediatrics patient"

5.00 - 6.00 PM Day-1 (7th April,2023) **Session Chair : Dr. Praveen Kumar**
Misra Oral Presentation **Dr. Nirmal Srivastava**
Mobile No. -9807025822
Zoom link: https: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83682456140?pwd=N0lHalZibm52RDRGeDFycVQrNjF6dz09>
Meeting id- 879 0963 7493 Password- 034792
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A28	Miss. Sneha Gupta	Factors affecting jobsatisfaction and job loyalty of employees in a higher education
A29	Dr. Dr. Rajinder kaur	WATER QUALITY INDEX OF FRESHWATER BODY WITH REFERENCE TO WATER QUALITY PARAMETERS FROM PUNJAB (INDIA)
A30	Dr. BANSI RAJNIKANT SHAH	Transforming India Through Self-reliance, Atmanirbhar Bharat.
A31	Dr. JAYKUMAR RAJNIKANT SHAH	An Alopecia Universalis - Ruhya in Ayurved (loss of hair from the entire body parts) patient with growing of hair on all the hair growing parts of the body by Ayurvedic Nasya procedure
A32	Dr. Sunila B sangappa	Salivary Lactate Dehydrogenase as a salivary Biomarker in Periodontitis and tooth loss
A33	Mrs. Shreya Kotnala	Removal of pesticides from water by using sustainable adsorbents: A review

5.00 - 6.00 PM Day1 (7th April, 2023) **Parallel Session** **Session Chair: Dr. Shweta Singh**
Email:sciencetech487@gmail.com
Oral Presentation
Zoom link: https://us04web.zoom.us/j/79107293572?pwd=vthVOY0mF8NqW6WwKiWwJHQX3hMMHf.1
Meeting id- 791 0729 3572 Password- VA8i0
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A34	Dr. Sheelu Sengar	Exploring New Horizons : Research and Innovation in Arts, Humanities and Culture Education
A 35	Mrs. Dr.M.Usha Rani	IMPACT OF TEAM BASED LEARNING ON 1st PHASE MBBS STUDENTS IN PHYSIOLOGY
A 36	Dr. Jyoti Sattyam Wankhade	Photoacoustic Imaging in Dentistry
A 37	Dr. Sheetal S. Paliwal	Only participation
A 38	Dr. SABITHA NAGUBUDI	ROLE OF GENETIC ENGINEERING IN CROP IMPROVEMENT
A 39	Dr. Dr. Amita Singh	Ferrocene Appended Asymmetric Sensitizers with Azine Spacers with Phenolic/Nitro Anchors for Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells

6.30 to 7.30 PM Day-1 (7th April,2023) Session-Chair: Dr. Alka Singh Bhatt
Oral Presentation
Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83682456140?pwd=N0lHaIZibm52RDRGeDFycVQrNjF6dz09>
Meeting id- 879 0963 7493 Password- 034792
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A 40	Dr.	Saroj Rai	Kitchen herbs and Probiotics fortified in milk improved the health and growth performance of neonatal calves
A 41	Dr.	Shweta Wadhawan	Biogenic synthesis of non-toxic iron oxide NPs via Syzygium aromaticum for the removal of methylene blue
A 42	Dr.	RUBY AHMED	VOC Sensing Studies on Electrically Conductive Polyaniline@MoS ₂ Nanocomposites
A 43	Dr.	Divya S	Orthodontic Effects based on Analogical Concepts
A 44	Dr.	AWANINDRA KUMAR TIWARI	NA
A 45	Miss.	Deepika Ramdas Tambe	RICE WATER FERMENTATION- ANTIOXIDANT AND PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

6.30 to 10.30 PM Day-1 (Aprilth April, 2023) Parallel Session Session Chair: Dr. Sangeeta Yadav Dr. Shalni Rai
Oral Presentation
Mobile No.- 8299547952
Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83682456140?pwd=N0lHaIZibm52RDRGeDFycVQrNjF6dz09>
Meeting id- 879 0963 7493 Password- 034792
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A46	Dr. PRITIKA DUA	Is Corporate Environmentalism rewarded by Market? Empirical Evidence from Indian IT Firms
A47	Dr. Neha Nainwal	Is Corporate Environmentalism rewarded by Market? Empirical Evidence from Indian IT Firms
A48	Dr. Sharmila Saren	A Stackelberg game approach in a vendor-buyer model with carbon emission and setup cost reduction
A49	Dr. Nitin Joseph	Practices of personal protective measures against SARS-Cov-2 among undergraduate medical students in Mangalore, India
A50	Dr. Sabiha Tabassum	On E-Statistical Summability of Bounded Sequence
A51	Dr. Archana Bhaskar	Entrepreneur: Build your own dreams
A52	Dr. Rupesh Sharma	Host preference and effect of pulse beetle, <i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i> (F.) on quality of different pulses
A53	Dr. Manisha Verma	Animated Monte Carlo Simulations of Pi on a Platonic Solid - The Icosahedron
A54	Dr. Sanjeeta Rani	Animated Monte Carlo Simulations of Pi on a Platonic Solid - The Icosahedron
A55	Dr. Vikas Moreshwar Mohture	Aeromycoflora incidence over Rice Field
A56	Dr. Ashish Mukhopadhyay	Nutritional Study of Adult Tribal Population of India with Special Emphasis on Santal Population of Birbhum District, West Bengal, India
A57	Dr. Bhuvana Venkatraman	Exploring Banking Efficiency of Public and Private Sector Banks in India using DEA
A58	Dr. Dr.Shital Deshmukh	Medicinally Important Leeches in churani region Melghat
A59	Mr. Samiran Mandal	Impact of capping agent on structural and optical properties of zinc sulphide nanoparticles
A60	Mr. MAHENDRA KUMAR PATRE	Nanotechnology : current and future applications

A61	Dr.	Anil Bhatt	Detached Society: A Sociological Perspective
A62	Dr.	Vandana Gaur	Psychology of gender identity
A63	Miss.	Hera Azmi	Production of alginate from Azotobacter sp. and its application
A64	Dr.	Vandna Bhalla	Review of Wearable Technology Applications and Advancements
A65	Dr.	Vandna Bhalla	Learning and Classification with Small Size Datasets: Challenges and Solutions
A66	Dr.	RASHMI JAISWAL	A
A67	Dr.	Abhilasha Motghare	Comparison of intrathecal clonidine and intrathecal buprenorphine in different doses and in combination for vaginal hysterectomy under subarachnoid block
A68	Dr.	Manisha Verma	Efficacy of Simulators in Sustained Science Education : Black Body Radiation, a Comparative Study
A69	Dr.	SHIVAKUMAR K V	Sensitivity nature of Phytophthora capsici isolates causing foot rot of black pepper in Karnataka to oomycetes specific fungicides

DAY-2(8th April 2023)

9.00 AM to 12.00PM Day 2 (8th April,2023)

Session Chair: Prof. S.K. Shukla

Dr. Shiba Shethi

Mobile No. -9450210623

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/84251187059?pwd=T2IzeXdTYUJvMU1pYkovQEVNbn08vUT09>

Meeting id- 842 5118 7059 Password- 865671

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A70	Miss. Prashasti Sinha	A Review on In-Silico Approaches for Drug Designing and Drug Discovery
A71	Mr. Uday Raj Devaraju Juttuka	Quality of life among Hemophiliacs of Kadapa district based on their severity
A72	Mr. Shivam Srivastava	Study of some elastic properties of nano TiO ₂ from EOSs
A73	Dr. H Prasad	Inflammation in oral cancer - Cause or effect?
A74	Miss. Khushboo	Molecular role of Long non coding RNA, microRNA and BRCA1 assay in female Breast cancer Pre & Post chemotherapy in tertiary care Hospital
A75	Dr. MINI V G	Therapeutic potential of Ayurveda management in Atrial Fibrillation with special reference to Paroxysmal and Lone AF
A76	Dr. C Nitya Kala	Current trends in herbal medicine for periodontitis
A77	Miss. Roshni Kumari	Advanced Applications of Hybrid Nanomaterials: A review
A78	Mrs. KIRAN SHARMA	Lived Experiences of Incarceration
A79	Mr. Aman Chand	Viable disposal of crumb rubber (CR) in bitumen modification to enhance its rheological properties
A80	Dr. PAVITRA A MENASINKAI	SOCIAL AUDIT : A POWERFUL TOOL IN THE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY
A81	Mr. VISHNU PRASAD YADAV	Preformulation studies of Roxatidine acetate ,first step towards before the developing stable floating drug delivery system
A82	Mr. KUWAR SINGH	"Dhyaan" - Aanand Ka Mukhy Dvaar
A83	Mrs. D DEVAKIRUBANITHI	On Odd Graceful and Cordial Labeling of Super Subdivision of certain classes of Path and Star graphs
A84	Mr. MANOJ KUMAR	A new multi-steps iteration scheme for approximating fixed points of nonexpansive mappings with applications
A85	Mrs. Sugandha Asthana	Effect of different carbon sources on lipid production of Bacillus velezensis DAA1
A86	Dr. Komal Khond Warghane	Systematic review on Socket shield technique
A87	Mrs. Neh Dubey	THE RISING EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON YOUTH
A88	Mr. BRIJESH SHIVHARE	HEPATO AND NEPHRO PROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF SARACA INDICA METHANOLIC EXTRACT ON LEAD ACETATE INDUCED TOXICITY IN RATS
A89	Miss. Anita Chauhan	Identification of a sub network as a predictive dynamic biomarker for Non Small Cell Lung Cancer
A90	Miss. Twinkle	Removal of Organic Dyes by Activated carbon Adsorption: A Review
A91	Mrs. N K VINODHINI	ANTIMAGIC LABELING OF CERTAIN FAMILIES OF TREE GRAPHS
A92	Mr. ARCHANA VERMA	Effect of copper concentration on structural, morphological and optical properties of tin oxide (Sn ¹⁺² xCu _x O ₂)
A93	Miss. GOWTHAMI G A	Production of metabolites from mutant strains of Rhodotorula minuta upon varied temperature

A94	Miss.	Supriya Gautam	Impact of COVID-19 on Small and Marginal Farmers in India
A95	Mrs.	ISHU PRIYA	Detection of pathogen Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus (CLas) causing Citrus Greening Disease by gene primer method
A96	Mr.	BHUKYA ANIL	Tribal health problems and reasons in Telangana state a review study

12.00 to 4.00PM Day 2 (8th April,2023) **Session Chair: Dr.Sangeeta Yadav & Dr. Shalni Rai**
Dr. Alka Singh Bhatt
Mobile No. -9450210623
Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/84251187059?pwd=T2IzeXdTYUJvMUlpYkoyOFVNb08vUT09>
Meeting id- 842 5118 7059 Password- 865671
0Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A97	Dr. Brajesh Dammani	Minimally Invasive Implantology : SIMO Concept
A98	Miss. Vanshika Gairola	A review on activated carbon-based nanomaterials derived from bio-wastes for high performance supercapacitor application
A99	Mr. Sandeep Pattnaik	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A DIAGNOSTIC TOOL FOR PROLAPSED INTERVERTEBRAL DISC: A LITERATURE REVIEW
A100	Mrs. Rittu Sharma	Perspectives of patients having Diabetes Peripheral Neuropathy about Physiotherapy intervention: A Literature Review
A101	Dr. Jitendra M. Pawara	Synthesis, Thermal, Spectral Characterization and biological study of Som Mixed Ligand Nickel (II) Complexes
A102	Miss. Lovely Gupta	f(T) gravity and Domain wall in Bianchi V space – time
A103	Mr. A B M Tanvirul islam	How Bollywood effects fashion trends.
A104	Mrs. Jyoti	Wheat Quality Evaluation: Physical, Chemical and Functional Properties
A105	Miss. Isha Kumari	CROCHET GARMENTS: DESIGN CHALLENGES
A106	Mr. Dhanabal R	Biogenic amphoteric transition metal-based nanomaterial for pharmaceutical pollution reduction
A107	Mr. Rohit Rangnath Paithane	Phytochemical Analysis and Antioxidant Potential of Weedy Plant Amaranthus Viridis and Portulaca Oleracea: A Review
A108	Miss. Uma Sharma	Medicinal uses of bioactive compounds of family Lamiaceae
A109	Mrs. nithya karnam	phytochemical analysis of evolvulus alsinoides linn extract in determining nootropic activity by GCMS
A110	Mr. SAMER J H ABUOWDA	Semantics Cohesive Devices in Compositions: The case of Arab EFL learners
A111	Mr. Awadhesh Kumar	Cyber Crimes Related to Online Fraud: Laws and Challenges
A112	Mrs. Mrs. Vinita Nilesh Jamdade	knowledge regarding warning signs of cancer among home-maker women
A113	Mrs. Sana Fatima	Efficient Removal of Fluoride ions and Anionic dyes by Zirconium-2-Imidazolidinethione Functionalized Reduced Graphene Oxide Aerogel
A114	Miss. Faiza Iqbal	Probiotic effect in preterm neonates with sepsis: A systematic Review
A115	Mrs. KIRAN KISHORE	IDENTIFICATION AND HYDROLYTIC ENZYME POTENTIAL OF ACTINOMYCETES FROM THE MANGROVE SEDIMENTS OF NORTH KERALA
A116	Miss. Maiby Thankachan	Species diversity and vectoral status of Culex Mosquitoes in Mananthavady Taluk, Wayanad, Kerala
A117	Mrs. Hardeep Kaur	Mechanistic investigation of formation of highly-dispersed silver nanoparticles using sea buckthorn extract
A118	Mrs. Ramyasree	post covid syndrome ith relation to vaccination status in PCR conformed patients prospective tudy
A119(Poster)	Miss. Sonakshi Modeel	Mitochondrial COI-based population genetic structure of Labeo rohita

A120	Mrs.	K SHIRISHA	Phenotypic and genotypic detection of extended spectrum beta lactamase enzyme in Klebsiella pneumoniae isolates from the clinical specimens of the patients in a tertiary care hospital.
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4.00 PM to 7.00 PM Day-2 (8th April,2023 Session Chair: Dr.Deepti Wadhwa
Oral & Poster Presentation

Mobile. No.8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/84251187059?pwd=T2IzeXdTYUJvMU1pYkoyOFVNb08vUT09>

Meeting id- 842 5118 7059 Password- 865671

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A121	Miss. ANJU	Structural and Optical Characterization of MoS ₂ for its Potential Applications in Biosensing
A122	Miss. bhavna singh	Spatiotemporal Analysis of Faridabad district, India Using Remote Sensing and GIS Approach
A123	Mr. SARVESH NARAYAN TIWARI	Position and Rights of the Unborn child
A124	Mrs. Renu V V	Exploring the scope of embryo-toxicology in post-mortem examination: A promising future tool
A125	Mrs. Desai Krishnaben	Biochemical Characterization of Different Mungbean (<i>Vigna radiata</i> (L). R. Wilczek) Accessions
A126	Miss. Cooshalle Wilson	Digitizing the upcoming Indian Census
A127	Dr. Deepti N Wadhwa	Not applicable
A128	Miss. Nithya K	Antibiogram and phenotypic detection of virulence genes among clinical isolates of <i>Klebsiella</i> species from CKD-UTI patients
A129	Miss. Hasiba Salihi	Addressing harmful effects of Microaggression at Workplace
A130	Mrs. Neha Parveen	Taxonomic studies of some genera of subfamily Entedoninae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Eulophidae)
A131	Miss. Meenakshi Verma	Online Education: Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Teachers with Visual Disability
A132	Miss. Poonam Patel	Post-Decisional Dissonance among Young Adults
A133	Mr. PRAKASH	Design and Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Derivatives having Pyrrole moiety
A134	Mr. ANANT RAM	Photophysical Properties, Effect of Substituents and Solvent on the Nature of the Transition of Benzimidazole Derivatives
A135	Mrs. Rahila K	Transcriptome based identification of genes responding to the organophosphate pesticide Acephate in <i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> (meigen, 1830)
A136	Miss. Vidya Raisagar	Exploring Banking Efficiency of Public and Private Sector Banks in India using DEA
A137	Dr. PRAVEENA. M	A cross sectional study on effect of glycaemic status and duration of type II diabetes mellitus on the pulmonary function
A138	Miss. Kaneez Fatima	Studying the impact of the capping agents on the surface modifications of ZnO Nanoparticles by Chemical Method

7.00 PM to 10.00 PM Day-2 (8th April,2023)

Session Chair: Dr. Deepthi Wadhwa

Oral & Poster Presentation

Mobile. No.8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/84251187059?pwd=T2lzeXdTYUJvMUlpYkoyOEVNb08vUT09>

Meeting id- 842 5118 7059 Password- 865671

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A139	Miss. JULEKHA SULTANA	CARDIO-PULMONARY DISFUNCTION IN COAL MINERS WITH ADVANCED FIBROTIC LUNG IMPAIRMENT-A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY
A140	Miss. Hiralben Kishorbhai Chaudhary	Investigation of anticancer and antioxidant efficacy of <i>Calocybe indica</i> P&C along with quantitative profiling of bioactive compounds
A141	Mr. BASIR AHMAD SHARIFI	Why The State Building Process in The Post-2001 In Afghanistan Failed?
A142	Mr. S PARASHURAM	synthesis and characterization of bismuth nanoparticles using endocoma macrocoma leaves and screening for its antibacterial, antioxidant activity
A143	Mrs. GAYATHRI M	Visualisation of early developmental stages of the wandering glider, <i>Pantala flavescens</i> (Fabricius, 1798) embryos (Odonata: Libellulidae): A future biomarker
A144	Miss. MAMPI DEBNATHI	INFLUENCE OF SOCIO- ECONOMIC AND SOCIO- DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS ALONG WITH STRESS LEVEL IN MENSTRUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE BENGALI ADOLESCENT GIRLS OF DARJEELING DISTRICT
A145	Mr. Amul darwari	The Effect of Azole Derivatives Bearing Hydrazone Moiety on Anticancer Activity
A146	Mr. Ramu Yadav	Plant spacing on the growth and yield, Nitrogen level of the basmati rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.)
A147	Mr. Hemanta Kumar	A GENERALISED CLASS OF ESTIMATORS FOR POPULATION MEAN UNDER STATIFIED RANDOM SAMPLING USING AUXILIARY ATTRIBUTE
A148	Mrs. Revathy S.	Comparison of different DNA and RNA extraction methods to obtain high quality DNA and RNA from <i>Cullenia exarillata</i>
A149	Mr. Srinivasa K	Inhibition of colorectal cancer cell (HCT-116) proliferation through an apoptosis dependent pathway with methanolic leaf extract of <i>Olea dioica</i> and in vitro cytotoxicity
A150	Miss. Anjali Yadav	Some LRS Bianchi Type-I Bulk Viscous Magnetized String Universes With Decaying $\hat{\rho}$ Terms.
A151	Miss. RASHIMI YADAV	Applications of Magneto Plasmonic for Advance Technology
A152	Miss. PRIYANKA RAWAT	Identification of monogeneans parasite from <i>Cyprinus carpio</i> and <i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> in the Ghaghra River, Uttar Pradesh
A153	Mr. Vinay Rawat	Preparation of Activated carbon for removal of organic contaminants from wastewater
A154	Mr. Satish Kumar Yadav	Participate
A155	Mr. SHIBIN FELIX P	Ploidy analysis and estimation of \hat{P}^2 -asarone content in <i>Acoru calamus</i> Linn., from Tamil Nadu regions of the Western Ghats
A156	Dr. Archana Yadav	Natural History of tube-dwelling spider genus <i>Ariadna vansda</i> (Araneae: Segestriidae) (Siliwal, Yadav & Kumar, 2017) from Vansda National Park, Gujarat, India

DAY-3 (9th April 2023)

9.00 - 12:00 PM Day-3 (9th April,2022) Session-Chair: Prof. S. K Shukla & Dr. Gunjan Singh
Mrs. Neha Dubey & Seema Tripath
Mobile No- 8299547952
Oral & Poster presentations
Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85704417508?pwd=eFpLU1ZZWUF1RlJ2RzBXcmc2MW9BUT09>
Meeting id- 892 1706 6872 Password- 386076
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation & 05 min for Poster presentation

ABSTRACTID	SPEAKER		TOPIC
A157	Dr.	Surekha	Observational study on prescription patterns of systemic antifungal medications in critically ill patients at tertiary care ICU
A158	Dr.	EMIL SANKAR S	Safety and Efficacy of Intermittent Fasting in Type II Diabetes Mellitus Patients on Insulin Therapy
A159	Dr.	PANKAJ KUMAR RAI	A Comparative Study Of Different Anthropometric Parameters Of Obesity With Cardiovascular Autonomic Functions
A160	Dr.	Sai Shanmukh Vemparala	IMPACT OF TEAM BASED LEARNING ON FIRST PHASE MBBS STUDENTS IN PHYSIOLOGY
A161	Miss.	Aparna Matpathi	Tenofovir induced Nephrotoxicity- A Case Report
A162	Miss.	Himani vijay borkar	Separation of Toxic Metals on Chromatographic layer of Aminoplast Impregnated with Sodium Acetate.
A163	Dr.	VIPIN KUMAR	Importance of dried blood spot card samples in neonatal screening
A164	Miss.	Sakshi Nagdeve	Computational Chromatographic Behaviour of Heavy Metals by modified Aminoplast Absorbent
A165	Dr.	RESHMI A.S	Utility of Principles of Ayurveda in Myocardial Reperfusion Injury : A Review
A166	Mr.	Vaibhav Mishra	Nano materials: Analysis and Synthesis
A167	Mr.	UTKARSH SAXENA	Role of magnetic resonance imaging in assessment of valvular heart diseases
A168	Miss.	Rifa Ansar	Higher Education in India: Challenges and Opportunies
A169	Miss.	Nishita	A Study of thermal stability of multi component Functionalized Biocomposite materials
A170	Miss.	RUSHALIMAKKAR	A Study of thermal stability of multi component Functionalized Biocomposite materials
A171	Miss.	Sanghita P. Nath	Optimal Release Time for Modular Software in Random Field Environment
A172	Dr.	Adesh Agarwal	EFFECT OF COVID-19 ON PREGNANCY
A173	Dr.	Anurag kapoor	Effect on covid 19 on pregnancy

12.00 - 6:00 PM Day-3 (9th April,2023) Session-Chair: Dr. Anuradha Misra & Dr. Sushma Singh
Dr. S,K.Singh
Mobile No- 8299547952
Oral & Poster presentations
Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85704417508?pwd=eFpLU1ZZWUF1RlJ2RzBXcmc2MW9BUT09>
Meeting id- 892 1706 6872 Password- 386076
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation & 05 min for Poster presentation

ABSTRAC TID	SPEAKER		TOPIC
A174	Dr.	Priyanshi srivastava	Effect of covid 19 on pregnancy
A175	Mr.	Vijay. S	Investigation of bioactive molecules of R. Communis by Gas Chromatography mass Spectrometry

A176	Dr.	Raj kamal Maurya	Effect of covid 19 on pregnancy
A177	Dr.	Bryan Adriel	Adverse childhood events and their effect on stress and depression levels
A178	Mr.	Vaibhav Thapliyal	Animated Monte Carlo Simulations of Pi on a Platonic Solid - The Icosahedron
A179	Dr.	Dr Deepak Anil	Web-based intervention in improving the mental health status among patients with Type 2 Diabetes in southern India
A180	Mr.	Jayanth D R	MICROBES USED AS A TOOL FOR BIOREMEDIATION OF HEAVY METALS FROM WASTEWATER
A181	Mr.	Ayush Mishra	Animated Monte Carlo Simulations of Pi on a Platonic Solid - The Icosahedron
A182	Miss.	Jigisha Bhosale	Acute exposure of flubendiamide disrupts sonic hedgehog signalling during eye development in domestic chick Gallus domesticus
A183	Mr.	Nishant bhojraj Dhobale	To Determine the Physico-chemical Parameters of Water of Lakes in Nagpur City
A184	Miss.	Eesha Prasad	Microbes used as a tool for bioremediation of heavy metals from waste water
A185	Miss.	Sarah Fatima	Descriptive Statistics
A186	Mr.	BHAVYA	Efficacy of Simulators in Sustained Science Education : Black Body Radiation, a Comparative Study
A187	Mr.	UTSAV BHARADWAJ	TO REUSE THE FABRIC WASTE: IMPLEMENTING THE JAPANESE TECHNIQUE OF KINTSUGI
A188	Mr.	ARKADIP MAJUMDER	Synthesis and Characterization of Cu-BiVO ₄ /g-C ₃ N ₄ nanocomposites for enhanced photocatalytic activity
A189	Miss.	K.poornima	Removal of dye from aqueous solution using ion exchange resins
A190	Mrs.	Vandana Kumari	Relationship between sleep habits And Smartphone Dependence in Adolescents
A191	Mr.	Swapnil Gaur	Influence of materialism on consumer buying behavior in India
A192	Ms.	Kirti	The future of chemotherapy lies in drug Nano carriers for advanced cancer therapies.

9.00 AM to 10.30 AM Day-3 (9th April,2023) **Parallel Session**

Session Chair: Dr. Shweta Singh

Email: susheelsingh489@gmail.com

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us04web.zoom.us/j/71133407062?pwd=XvIZUiwBk91dFWKT8OSw0avqhjRRqL.1>

Meeting id- 711 3340 7062

Password: 0GkH8R

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A193	Mrs.	Snita Bhunia	ASSES KNOWLEDGE GAP ON MORBIDITIES, ITS PRVENTIVE, CONTROL MEASURES & PRACTICE OF USING PREVENTIVE MEASURES RELATED TO AIR POLLUTION AMONG TRAFFIC POLICE IN WB(KOLKATA)
A194	Mrs.	USHA MALLICK	THE PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT AND COPING MECHANISM OF COVID-19 ON STAFF NURSES - RETROSPECTIVE STUDY
A195	Mrs.	Rumi Sen	Use of E-learning and Face to Face learning strategies for Nursing students in relation to their some personal variables
A196	Dr.	Dhyanadipta Panda	The Vital Role of Artificial Intelligence In The Developing Human Resource Field
A197	Dr.	Rashmi MATHUR	2023: THE INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF MILLETS
A198	Dr.	Ritika	Development and evaluation of gluten-free noodles prepared from foxtail millet and orange peel powder
A199	Dr.	Vidyadevi Chandavarkar	CO levels in smokers and non smokers: A review.
A200	Dr.	Nilesh Hiralal Chitte	Exploring the Role of Culture in English Language Teaching
A201	Dr	Sanjeeta Rani	Efficacy of Simulators in Sustained Science Education : Black Body Radiation, a Comparative Study

10.30 AM to 12.00 PM Day-3 (9th April,2023) **Parallel Session**

Session Chair: Dr. S.K. Singh

Email: susheelsingh487@gmail.com

Mobile No.- 8299547952 **Oral**

Presentation

Zoom link:

<https://us04web.zoom.us/j/73014788845?pwd=hbI7oaPcR3uaNfkINOxgIaeFPziWkL.1>

Meeting id- 730 1478 8845

Password: k50r9w

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A202	Dr.	Mrudula Wadekar	Lanthanide Chelates of Isometric 3-Bromolawsone and 3-Bromojuglone
A203	Dr.	Pramod D. Ghogare	DEVELOPMENT OF SYNBIOTIC DARK CHOCOLATE ENRICHED WITH PINEAPPLE PEEL AS PREBIOTIC AND ISOLATED PROBIOTIC
A204	Dr.	Mithilesh Narayan Mishra	Lichen Planus: A review.
A205	Dr.	Kirandeep Sandhu	Heavy cluster emission in the decay of Z=112-116 superheavy nuclei
A206	Dr.	Shibin Chacko	One pot Three Component Mannich Reaction for the Synthesis of 2-substituted Piperidine and Pyrrolidine Natural Products
A207	Dr.	Anija Mol T Philip	Total Synthesis of 4-Hydroxy ornithine Using Proline Catalysed $\hat{\pm}$ -hydroxylation Reaction
A208	Miss	Km. Nishi	Zero Waste Pattern Making Challenges For Denim Products
A209	Mrs.	JYOTI CHAPRANA	Nanoparticle infused hydrogel as a sustainable approach in wastewater remediation: A mechanistic and comprehensive review
A210	Mr.	Mohd sadiq	An Analytical Study of Development in UT Ladakh after the abrogation of Article 370, especially in Tourism sector

12.00 - 1.30 PM Day-3 (9th April, 2023) Parallel Session Session Chair: Dr. Shweta Singh

Email:sciencetech487@gmail.com

Oral Presentation

Zoom link:

<https://us04web.zoom.us/j/76129761465?pwd=RNihsI7zWPA5WWxICfJ7AkdosJpRSZ.1>

Meeting id- 761 2976 1465

Password- qJMiE2

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A211	Miss.	Rituparna Priyadarshini	Poetic Analysis of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Religion and Spirituality in Odisha
A212	Miss.	Vasundhara Saluja	A RESEARCH ON REPOSITIONING KHADI AS A SUSTAINABLE FASHION TEXTILE
A213	Miss.	Km Babita	Effect of drought stress on the physiological, biochemical property, callusing and shooting frequency on medicinal plant <i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L.) DC
A214	Mr.	Jay Prakash Jha	Revolutionizing Chronic Myeloid Leukemia Treatment with miR-486-5p Biomarker Insights
A215	Mr.	KARTHIK M B	<i>Rigidoporus vinctus</i> , an endophytic fungal with antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, from the shoot of <i>Bambusa tulda</i> .
A216	Miss.	Khushboo Anjum	Case report of inhibiting synergy pattern by kinesiotaping in stroke patients: A challenging aspect
A217	Miss.	Saliha Rafat	Upper limb Myofascial Release to improve Motor functions in patient with Stroke: A Case report
A218	Miss.	Sadiya Rafat	Conjunct effect of low level laser therapy and kinesiotaping in patient with cervical radiculopathy : A case report
A219	Miss.	Sumayya Chaudhary	Zero waste: A pattern making techniques to reduce the fabric waste.

2.00 - 3.30 PM Day-3 (9th April, 2023) Parallel Session Session Chair: Dr. Shweta Singh

Email:headofficestilko@gmail.com

Oral Presentation

Zoom link:

<https://us05web.zoom.us/j/86499230324?pwd=dVYySG5PaGJsbk5lNVo3NTRVU1dGUT09>

Meeting id- 864 9923 0324

Password- VMRH3U

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A220	Miss.	DAYANA VINCENT	Sentiment Based Topic Modelling on Reviews
A221	Dr.	Vemuri Keerthi	Medicine as a career! Apprehensions and Aspirations among 1st year undergraduates.
A222	Miss.	Vartika Mishra	Impact of COVID-19 on Quality of Life -A Scoping Review
A223	Miss.	Iram Shaikh	DEVELOPMENT OF SYNBIOTIC DARK CHOCOLATE ENRICHED WITH PINEAPPLE PEEL AS PREBIOTIC AND ISOLATED PROBIOTIC
A224	Miss.	Anjali Raghuvanshi	Variation of Reaction Time in Professional and Recreational Players
A225	Dr.	NEELIMA	A STUDY OF EVALUATION OF EMOTIONAL REGULATION IN MEDICAL STUDENTS
A226	Mrs.	Shalini Kumari	Inland water quality monitoring using Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8: A case study of natural and artificial lakes in Uttarakhand, India

A227	Mr.	Shubham kumar mishra	The Mechanism of Aristotle's categories in the study of knowledge: An Epistemological Appraisal
A228	Mr.	Hariom Mishra	Air pollution and it's influence on health in lucknow : A Geographic Perspective
A229	Dr.	RAKESH SINGH	Efficient Flood Mapping Using Multi-Criteria Decision-Making and GIS: A Case Study of Kosi River Basin, North Bihar, India
230	Mrs.	Leeba Cible	Professional role tranfition of new graduate nurses
A278	Dr.	Jomon Lonappan	Emerging trends in entrepreneurial training in higher education
A279	Dr.	Meera Jacob	CROSSECTIONAL STUDY ON BUILDING A FRAMEWORK FOR PROFESSIONALISM AMONG HEALTH CARE PROFESSIONALS.
A280	Miss.	RINKI MISHRA	Rethinking of Descartes substance Dualism; an analytical appraisal.
287	Dr.	Susheel Kumar Singh	Strength of Dielectric constant of CuO doped Polyaniline

Announcement of Winners of Awards & valedictory session: 6:00 PM

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85704417508?pwd=eFpLU1ZZWUF1RIJ2RzBXcmc2MW9BUT09>

Meeting id- 892 1706 6872 Password- 386076

Note: All Participants will Join this session.

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Green synthesized Silver Nanoparticles and their Applications

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Abstract

Nanotechnology has made a significant contribution in different areas of scientific research. Nanotechnology is involved in the preparation and application of nanoparticles which can be used in different sectors. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) having properties useful for different applications have received lot of attention. Due to applications of Ag NPs in different areas such as chemistry, optical sensors, medicine, adsorption, water management, and drug administration, the green synthesis has become one of the most important areas of research. Green methods of synthesis of Ag NPs are eco-friendly, cost-effective, and efficient. In general plant extracts are more advantageous as compared to microorganisms due to reduced biohazard, and simplicity. Alkaloids and metabolites present in plants act as antimicrobials, insect repellents and herbivore defences. In green synthesis of Ag NPs, the plant extract reduces silver ions (Ag^+) into metallic silver (Ag^0). Biological molecules act as reducing agent and simultaneously as capping agents also. This capping agents reduce nanoparticle agglomeration. Due to capping, the surfaces of silver nanoparticles may change, modifying their dissolving capabilities to destroy the microbial cell. Number of parameters such as pH, temperature and incubation time for synthesis of AgNPs have been discussed. Applications of green synthesized AgNPs in different sectors have also been highlighted.

IT-02

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**Significance of Microstrain in Impacting Band Gap and Photoluminescence of Sol-Gel
Microstrain and Optical Properties of RE Doped ZnO Nanostructures**

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Abstract

Here, we elucidate the significance of microstrain in impacting optical properties such as band gap and photoluminescence (PL) intensity of sol-gel synthesized RE-doped ZnO nanostructures. Microstrain is seen to affect the crystallite size, which results in band structure modification thereby causing a substantial impact on transitions happening within the band gap. Rare earth (RE) elements, particularly when they are doped in ZnO during the process of nucleation, they are found to influence the microstrain. In a study on spin coated Ce doped ZnO thin films, the crystallite size varied from 25-50 nm, and micro-strain observed a significant decrease on doping with Ce. Increase in band gap was in the range of 3.19 to 3.44 eV for Ce-doped ZnO. PL spectra showed no shift in the peak of UV emission on doping with Ce. However, the reduction in PL intensity was governed by microstrain induced by doping ZnO with Ce. Similar study was carried out with Eu doped ZnO system, that too demonstrated significant changes in the band gap and PL properties of ZnO governed by microstrain. In a further analysis Li was used a co-dopant where band gap found to follow

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the similar as that of microstrain, with increase in Eu concentration. Such microstrain governed optical properties can to the development of mechano-optical devices.

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COVID-19 and Pregnancy: Placental Histopathological Features and Adverse Outcomes

Neha Singh

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Abstract: The placenta, a marvellous multi-functional organ of foetal origin, performs a crucial role during pregnancy by closely linking mother and baby together. A total 396 pregnant women were enrolled in our study and out of 396, 55 placentas were collected from the mothers infected with novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) for the expression of genes specific for the SARS-CoV-2 via RT-PCR. So far, congenital transmission of SARS-CoV-2 seems to be remarkably uncommon in spite of many cases of COVID-19 during pregnancy. Out of the 55 placental tissue samples collected, none has shown gene expression of SARS-CoV-2 when confirmed by RT-PCR. At the same time, nasal and throat swab samples collected from new-borns of SARS-CoV-2-positive mothers correspondingly tested negative by RT-PCR. The shielding properties of placental barriers against viral infections from mothers to new-borns remains a mystery. During intrauterine fetal life placenta is the main metabolic, respiratory, excretory, and endocrine organ. COVID-19 affects the placental morphology during pregnancy. Histopathologic findings of placenta in pregnant women with confirmed COVID-19 positive findings have been recorded as choriodecidual tissue with necrosis, intramural fibrin deposition, chorionic villi with fibrosis, and calcification. Although recent findings are insufficient to prove direct placental transmission of COVID-19, but the abundance of angiotensin-converting enzymes-2 (ACE-2) on the placental surface could potentially contribute to unpleasant outcomes during pregnancy as SARS-CoV-2 gains access to human cells via ACE-2.

Keywords: COVID-19; Pregnancy; Adverse outcomes; RT-PCR; SARS-CoV-2; Pathology; Placenta.

Dr. S. K. YADAV
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Different Sampling Techniques in Research

Dr. Subhash Kumar Yadav

Associate Professor

Department of Statistics

Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow

Abstract

Sampling is important whenever the population is large as it is very time consuming and costly to get information on every unit of the population under consideration. In this talk, I will be discussing different sampling techniques such as Simple Random Sampling, Stratified Random Sampling, Systematic Sampling, Cluster Sampling, Two-Stage Sampling, Multi-Stage Sampling etc as random sampling techniques and Quota Sampling, Snowball Sampling, Convenient Sampling etc as non-random sampling techniques along with their applications in different situations and areas of applications.

Keywords: Random Sampling, Non-Random Sampling, Census, Sampling Frame.

Dr. Mohammad Miyan
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MOTION OF HYDRODYNAMIC FLUID FOR ROTATORY THEORY OF INCLINED BEARINGS

Prof. Mohammad Miyan

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Abstract

The second order rotatory theory of fluid mechanics lubrication was supported on the expression obtained by retaining the terms containing initial and second powers of rotation range within the extended generalized Reynolds equation. Within the present paper, there are some new glorious basic solutions with the assistance of geometrical figures, expressions, calculated tables and graphs for the bearing of type $h = h_0 \text{Exp.}(\theta); \theta = f(y)$ within the second order rotatory theory of fluid mechanics lubrication. The analysis of equations for pressure and load capability, tables and graphs reveal that pressure and load capability aren't freelance of viscosity of fluid and increase linearly, slightly with viscosity. Conjointly the pressure and load capability each increase exponentially with increasing values of rotation range. Within the absence of rotation, the equation of pressure and load capability provides the classical solutions of the classical theory of fluid mechanics lubrication. The relevant tables and graphs make sure these necessary investigations within this paper.

Keywords: Rotation number, Taylor's number, Reynolds equation, Viscosity.

, Dr. Puspendra Singh
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Synthesis and Characterization of Unsymmetrical Selenoether

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 University Lucknow-226017.

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Abstract:

We have developed an easiest methodology to isolate *meta*-bromo substituted unsymmetrical selenoether. In this piece of work, we first prepare *meta*-bromo benzylbromide following the literature procedure [1,2]. Then we have treated *meta*-bromo benzylbromide with in situ generated air and moisture sensitive reagent *p*-tolylselenate anion in 1:1 ratio under inert atmosphere [3]. From the reaction mixture we are able to isolate a white crystalline solid of (3-bromobenzyl)(*p*-tolyl)selane in good yield. This compound has been characterized with the help of several spectroscopic techniques.

Scheme: Synthesis of (3-bromobenzyl)(*p*-tolyl)selane

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**Evaluation of Newborn Infant Parasympathetic Evaluation (NIPE) monitor as
an indicator of nociception in pediatric patients undergoing surgery.**

Introduction

Systems controlling cardiovascular function are closely coupled to perception of pain. Heart rate variability (HRV) is a well-established non-invasive measure of cardiac autonomic control. We hypothesized that pain may alter HRV and that HRV analysis could be used as an indicator of acute intraoperative nociception in infants and children. We aimed to validate the NIPE monitor for pain assessment in infants and young children under general anaesthesia. The primary outcome measure was to correlate NIPE scores with heart rate at various specified time points during surgery.

Methods

It was a prospective observational pilot study on 15 children less than 2yrs of age undergoing elective surgery. Patients on Inotropes/ ongoing fluid resuscitation, raised Intra-cranial tension (ICT), cardiac malformations / arrhythmias, on anti-arrhythmics or beta- blockers, those who had received ephedrine or atropine perioperatively were excluded.

Baseline values of HR and NIPE were recorded after induction of general anesthesia. Both values were then recorded at initial stimulus, and then at every 5 min interval till 60 min of maintenance phase.

Statistical analysis:

Correlation between NIPE values and HR measurements were tested using the Pearson's correlation coefficient (R²). P value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

NIPE did not reliably correlate with heart rate at any of the time points studied. Values of NIPE showed weak positive correlation with values of heart rate at baseline, initial stimulus, 5 mins, 15 mins and 45 mins with R² values 0.17,0.14,0.20, 0.13, 0.01 respectively. At 30 min and 60 min. R² values showed a weak negative correlation (R² = -0.06, -0.12). All values of Pearson's correlation coefficient were statistically not significant.

Conclusion: Isolated NIPE values were not found to be a reliable indicator of nociception for intraoperative analgesia in infants and toddlers upto 2 years of age.

Key words

Neonates, infants, heart rate variability, nociception

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Strength of Dielectric constant of CuO doped Polyaniline

ABSTRACT:

Polyaniline/CuO NCs at different weight percentages are synthesized by chemical oxidative polymerization method. The composites have been synthesized with various compositions (10, 15, and 20 wt %) of cupric oxide in Polyaniline (PANI), the chemical characterization are made using XRD (X-ray diffraction). The surface morphology of these composites have been studied with scanning electron micrograph (SEM). The dielectric properties have been studied at different wt% CuO doped Polyaniline (PANI) with function of frequency range from 100 Hz to 5 MHz and also at temperatures range 303 K to 343 K. The dielectric loss decreases with increasing the frequency and increases with increasing CuO concentration. The maximum dielectric loss is found to be at lower wt %CuO doped Polyaniline (PANI) NCs.

KEYWORDS: Conducting Polyaniline, XRD, SEM, Nanocomposites, Dielectric constant.

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Fuzzy Soft Sets and Decision-Making Under Uncertainty: A Comprehensive Analysis

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This paper uses the soft-set theory to handle the challenge of making decisions. Decision-making under uncertainty is a common problem in various fields, such as finance, engineering, healthcare, and business. Fuzzy soft sets have emerged as a promising approach for dealing with uncertainty in decision-making problems. In this paper, we provide a comprehensive analysis of fuzzy soft sets and their applications in decision-making under uncertainty. First, we introduce the concept of fuzzy soft sets and their mathematical properties. Then advantages and limitations of fuzzy soft sets compared to other decision-making models is discussed. Next, a review of several applications of fuzzy soft sets in different decision-making scenarios, including multi-criteria decision-making, group decision-making, and decision-making in complex systems, is done. Finally, we identify some of the current challenges and future directions in the use of fuzzy soft sets for decision-making under uncertainty. Our analysis shows that fuzzy soft sets can provide a flexible and intuitive framework for handling uncertainty in decision-making and that they have a wide range of potential applications in different fields. However, further research is needed to address some of the current limitations and to explore the full potential of fuzzy soft sets for decision-making under uncertainty.

Keywords: Soft Sets; Fuzzy soft sets; Decision making; Parameter reduction

OP 1

Charged Particle Fluctuation in Heavy-Ion Collisions**Ashwini Kumar****Department of Physics and Electronics****Dr. Rammanohar Lohia Avadh University, Ayodhya-224001, UP, India**

Abstract: The major physics goal of heavy-ion collision experiments at relativistic energies is to analyse and to understand Quantum chromodynamics (QCD) phase diagram, the nature of phase transition from normal hadronic matter to Quark-gluon plasma (QGP) phase as predicted by Quantum chromodynamics (QCD) theory. QCD theory is a well-established quantum field theory of strong interactions. The detection of experimentally accessible quantities plays a key role in the exploration of new/exotic phenomenon happening during the collision process and to develop a better understanding of the physics involved in charged particle production in these collisions at relativistic energies. Theoretical and experimental investigations of fluctuations of measurable physics quantities are vital to draw any firm conclusion. Therefore, a detailed investigation of the possible sources of statistical and non-statistical fluctuations present in the experimental data is performed and discussed in the present work to deepen our physics understanding of the phenomenon.

Keywords: Heavy-Ion collisions, Correlations, Fluctuations, Quantum chromodynamics, Relativistic energy.

OP 2

Facile Synthesis of Imine linked Naphthalimide Derivatives Based Hybrid Nanoparticles:**Determination of Chloramphenicol in Milk Samples****Anu Saini^{1,2*}, Navneet Kaur³ and Narinder Singh⁴**¹Centre for Nanoscience and Nanotechnology (UIEAST)

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Rupnagar, Punjab, India, 140001,

Abstract: The detection of antibiotics in a convenient and rapid manner is vital these days as their presence in food products and aquatic environment is a threat to humankind and microorganisms. In this paper, three fluorescent probes bearing naphthalimide moieties coupled with imine linkages have been developed and processed into organic nanoparticles. These organic nanoparticles **N3a-c** are used as a platform to develop hybrid nanoparticles **AgNPs@N3a-c** in which AgNPs are immobilized on the surface of organic nanoparticles. Among these **AgNPs@N3a** turned out to be selective for Chloramphenicol as it responds as a turn on fluorescence mode on binding with Chloramphenicol. The sensor responded in less than a minute and detection limit was 137 nM. More interestingly sensor exhibits pretty good selectivity among other competing drug molecules.

OP 3

To study the aggressive behavioural changes observed in school children between 8-18 years age after the restart of offline regular classes, post covid-19 lockdown

Dr. Sunitha K and Aishwarya Pathalavath

Professor, Practice of medicine

Bhagawan Buddha Homeopathic Medical College, Bangalore

Abstract: Aggressive behavioural changes in children can be described as being impulsive, throwing temper tantrums, destroying objects / property, being cruel and with an inability to be calm. If not treated, it can lead to behavioural disorders, conduct or pervasive development problems. After Covid -19 many children had problems in adjustment from online classes taken in the comfort of their homes to offline classroom classes, coming with different set of etiquettes, discipline and social interactions. Academic performances were also badly affected. Children showed an inability to concentrate in studies, slowness, poor performance in examination and being restless. They would rather be occupied in playing mobile video games than doing homework. A Google form of the Questionnaire was shared among one hundred parents. Out of these, fifty children were studied with the help of Child Academic Behaviour Checklist. Behaviour performances, grade of aggressiveness, etc. were the parameters assessed. Results reported more changes towards aggressive behaviour and poor progress in academic and classroom performances, mild changes in social-skills and moderate changes in their self-esteem. More changes were seen in children between 8-14 years & moderately in 15-18 years of age. These children could be managed with appropriate homoeopathic medicines, controlled usage of mobile, more outdoor games/ activities and counselling. One case study was done to showcase the aggressive changes in a child and its treatment by homoeopathic approach.

OP 4

Betel Leaf Farming: A case study of Purba Medinipur District, West Bengal**Soma Rani Karan¹ and Shahid Matangin Hazra²**¹Assistant Professor Department of Economics²Government General Degree College for women
Purba Medinipur, West Bengal

Abstract: The scientific name of the betel plants is *piper betel* L., popularly known as paan in India. It is grown as a cash crop in southern parts of India. It is also cultivated in West Bengal. In West Bengal major betel vine growing districts are Purba Medinipur, South 24 parganas, Howrah, Paschim Medinipur, North 24 parganas. It is one of the profitable plantation crops that may give huge income to the betel leaf farmers. It is also the Agri farming business that incurs huge investments as like other plantation crops. Despite of high prospect in betel leaf farming faced various common problems. Chief problem of betel leaf farmers are periodic wastage and non-availability of storage facilities, lack of Government support, lack of loan facilities and subsidies after natural calamities etc. Local authorities of Tamluk have recently tried to extent the betel leaf acreage by providing financial assistance for Boroj construction. This outreach needs to be extended credit measures to mitigate the effect of crop failure. They are ensuring a minimum support price. Establishment of a betel leaf research centre to explore high-yielding and conduct training programs on disease control and pesticide application can benefit farmers, together with creating accessible and adequate storage facilities. As in other parts of India, betel leaf cultivation in Tamluk subdivision needs greater Governmental support to flourish since the issues faced by it are probably greater than by other crops.

Keywords: Betel vine (*piper betel* L), Cultivation

OP 5

**Screening of some antipathogenic botanicals in vitro and field conditions against
Colletotrichum falcatum causing red rot of sugarcane****Anoop Kumar*, Satya Pal Verma**, Jagjeet Singh**and Zafar Abbas********Assistant Professor of Botany, Govt. Degree College (M.J.P. Rohilkhand University)
Kant, Shahjahanpur - 242223, U.P., India******Research Scholar, Post Graduate Department of Botany, G.F. College, (MJP Rohilkhand
University), Shahjahanpur -242001, U.P., India*******Principal, Maulana Azad Institute of Humanities, Science and Technology (Lucknow
University), Mahmudabad Avadh, Sitapur 261203, U.P., India.**

Abstract: The present study evaluated with the antipathogenic perspectives in vitro impact of (Aqueous and Ethanolic) antifungal plant (foliar) extracts (0, 5, 10, 15 conc. %) of eight indigenous plants *Psidium guajava*, *Sonchus oleraceus*, *Chenopodium album*, *Cassia tora*, *Achyranthus aspera*, *Euphorbia hirta*, *Euphorbia thymifolia* and *Phyllanthus niruri* against *Colletotrichum falcatum*, the pathogen of red rot disease of sugarcane. Pour plate method was used to determine the effect of different leaf extracts (Aqueous and Ethanolic). On mycelial radial growth of *C. falcatum*. The aqueous and ethanolic leaf extracts of all the botanical species have significant effect on tested pathogen. The gradient of efficacy of the leaf extracts of 8 types of leaf extracts tested for antifungal efficacy against *C. falcatum* was: *Psidium guajava* > *Cassia tora* > *Phyllanthus niruri* > *Euphorbia hirta* > *Achyranthus aspera* > *Sonchus oleraceus* > *Euphorbia thymifolia* > *Chenopodium album*. Ethanolic extracts proved more effective as compared to aqueous leaf extract regardless of the extract and its concentrations used in this study. Maximum inhibition 86.44% by ethanolic and 69.4% by 15% aqueous extract was found as a result of the *Psidium guajava* leaf extract followed by *Cassia tora* and *Phyllanthus niruri*. The poorest efficacy was noted with *Chenopodium album* and *Sonchus oleraceus* irrespective of the type of the extractant used. In another (field) experiment conducted during 2018-2019 (spring planting) with four red rot disease susceptible (CoPk 05191, CoO238, CoO118 and CoJ64) sugarcane varieties to evaluate the impact of leaf ethanolic extracts (15 % conc) of eight antipathogenic botanicals sprayed at 180 DAP for the study of leaf nutrient contents (NPK %) at 240, 300 DAP and at harvest together with final cane yield at harvest only. It was observed that highest cane yield 16.44 % more than the control (sprayed with water only) T1 was noted with

Psidium guajava (PS), T2 which was statistically equal to *Phyllanthus niruri* (PN), T9 followed by *Cassia tora* (CT), T5 which was associated with high leaf phosphorus and potassium percentages found at almost all stages studied. The lowest cane yield was noted with *Chemopodium album* (CA), T4 leaf extract as compared to control (T1). Variety CoO238 responded most followed by CoO118 in final cane yield. CoJ64 was poorest in performance. There was an accumulation of nitrogen content in the untreated plants (T1) at all growth stages studied. The magnitude of accumulation varied according to the degree of resistance of cane varieties.

Keywords: Antipathogenic leaf extracts, in vitro, field conditions, red rot of sugarcane.

OP 6**A Questionnaire Based Survey on Student's Opinion on the Prevailing Methods in Medical Education during the COVID Pandemic****Dr. Monika Mishra****PHOD, Pharmacology, SMS Medical College,
Jaipur, Rajasthan**

Abstract: Covid pandemic has caused disruption in health care system worldwide including the medical education. Facing the challenges for the faculty to deliver the lectures safely while ensuring the integrity and continuity of medical education for students, we moved on to complete on-line teaching and learning methodology from the conventional class-room lectures, practicals, tutorials and group discussions. A questionnaire based study was planned for 150 medical students in SMS Medical college, Jaipur who were to appear in the University Examination. 19 questions were framed pertaining to the subject of Pharmacology, methodology of teaching, comparison with the traditional teaching, satisfactory level of teaching methods and also the assessment patterns and send to the students through online platform. They responded promptly and the results were then analyzed. Results showed that the new era students are no longer interested in attending monotonous theory based lectures but have keen interest in clinical application with reasoning skills through innovative methods of teaching like problem solving interactive clinical seminars and case studies to prepare them for medical practice and henceforth, the medical education system in India needs significant restructuring and reforms with emphasis on rational use of medicines.

Keywords: Pharmacology, Assessment, Clinical seminars, Medical education.

OP 7

Comparative study of degradation of ortho toluic acid and para toluic acid by Ozonation, Peroxone, Photo-ozonation and Photo-peroxone Processes**Susmita A. Mandavgane****Department of Chemistry, D. R. B. Sindhu Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur – 440017 (India)**

Abstract: In the present work ortho toluic acid and para toluic acid in its aqueous solution was treated by ozonation, photo-ozonation, photoperoxone and photoperoxone processes. The experiments were carried out in a batch photoreactor using 8W low pressure mercury vapour lamp to examine the effects of different combinations of ozone, H_2O_2 and UV and their degradation rates are compared. Substrate concentration was determined by using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The photo degradation processes were adhered to first order kinetics. The degradation rate of both the substrates obey the following sequence: photoperoxone (UV/ O_3/H_2O_2) > photoozonation(UV/ O_3) > peroxone(O_3/H_2O_2) > ozonation (O_3).

Keywords: ortho toluic acid, para toluic acid, ozonation, photo-ozonation, photoperoxone, photoperoxone.

OP 8

A Mathematical Modelling approach to analyse the stability of the interaction between the Tomato Fruit Borer and its Biological Control**Dr. Anandhi Santhosh**

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Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract: Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) is one of the most commonly and extensively grown vegetables all over the country. This vegetable being a rich source of vitamins and minerals, occupy an important place in the food basket of Indian consumers. Tomato is highly susceptible to the fruit borer attack. Tomato fruit borer *Helicoverpa armigera*, a major pest on developing fruits is responsible for major yield loss. Eggs are laid singly, generally on leaves and flowers in the upper canopy of the plant. The young larvae feeds on the tender foliage and the fourth larval instar bores inside the fruits and eats away the internal content of the fruits. Such fruits are not preferred by consumers. The holes made on the fruits are circular and the larva feeds on keeping the head portion only inside the hole. A female lays approximately 500 eggs. *Trichogramma chilonis* is the most naturally efficient and frequent parasitoid of the borer. It is an egg parasitoid belonging to the family Trichogrammatidae. The adult parasitoids parasite the egg of the *Helicoverpa armigera* and kills the pest before it can damage the fruit.

In this paper, the main focus is to analyse the stability of the impulsive control system that represents the interaction between Tomato fruit borer and its biological control. The stability of the system is analysed by indentifying the parameters that helps to maintain the pest population in an equilibrium level below the economic injury level.

Keywords: Tomato Fruit Borer, Trichogrammm Chilonis, Impulsive differential equations, Economic Injury level, stability

OP 9**Evaluation of effect of grafting materials on implant stability and bone regeneration in patients with transcrestal approach for sinus augmentation at three different time intervals****- An Experimental study****Dr Sattyam V Wankhade****Associate Professor, Department of Prosthodontics, crown and Bridge
Government Dental College, Nagpur - 440003**

Abstract: The application of Dental implants for the prosthetic rehabilitation of missing teeth has provided a multitude of treatment options for patients. Loss of teeth in posterior maxillary area can lead to adverse consequences. Maxillary sinus pneumatization is one of these that precludes placement of implants due to anatomical constraints. In this anatomical situation, it can be very difficult to obtain effective primary stability. Maxillary sinus augmentation has been shown to be a predictable method to increase posterior maxillary bone height, and allow placing dental implants when the residual alveolar ridge is deficient in bone volume. Following post extraction resorption amounting to deficient bone volume in posterior maxilla, many approaches have been described to augment the residual bone ridge by ensuring sinus membrane elevation up to 5mm without tearing it. Boyne and James first described the sinus lift technique based on a modification of the Caldwell-Luc sinus revision, involving a lateral approach to the sinus that allows a remarkable bone augmentation upto >10mm even in atrophic ridges.

This paper evaluates the effect of grafting materials on implant stability and bone regeneration in patients with transcrestal approach for sinus augmentation at three different time intervals- An Experimental study

Keywords: Maxillary sinus, dental Implants, sinus lift, transcrestal approach, Platelet-rich fibrin

OP 10

Intelligent Crop Yield Prediction and Recommendation using Deep Learning Techniques**Srilatha Toomula¹ and Dr. P.V. Sudha²****¹Research Scholar, Osmania University & Assistant Professor,
Department of Computer Science,
RBVRR Women's College, Narayanguda, Hyderabad.****²Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering,
Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana State**

Abstract: In recent days, crop yield prediction and recommendation is a major area of research, where the information about the suitable crop to cultivate will be very much useful for the farmers. The crop yield prediction and recommendation in agriculture helps the farmers to know how much yield they can expect from the cultivation. It also helps in minimizing the loss to the farmers when unfavourable conditions occur. The proposed work is to predict the yield of the crop based on the suitable crop parameters like Temperature Min, Temperature Max, Humidity, Wind speed, Pressure using a Neural Network Model and recommending the crop. In this research paper, crop yield prediction and recommendation using Feed Forward Neural Network, LSTM and Recurrent Neural Network model were implemented. The performance of neural network models was evaluated using the metrics like Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Loss.

Keywords- Yield Prediction, Crop Recommendation, Feed Forward Neural Network, Recurrent Neural Network, Long Short-Term Memory.

OP 11

**Phytochemical analysis and evaluation of antioxidant activity in methanolic extracts of
Macrotyloma uniflorum (Lam)****Ritu Mahajan*, Muskaan Sharma and Shajaat Hussain
School of Biotechnology, University of Jammu, Jammu (J&K)**

Abstract: *Macrotyloma uniflorum* locally known as kulth, is a minor legume belonging to Fabaceae family. It is an underutilized crop with high nutritious and ethno-medicinal importance. Seed of *Macrotyloma* are used in the treatment of uterine stones, asthma, bronchitis, piles, diseases related to eyes, and liver. Methanol extracts of seeds of *M. uniflorum* were screened for the presence of phytochemicals. Antioxidant activity was evaluated by free radical scavenging activity and Ferric ion reducing power assay. Phytochemical screening of extracts revealed the presence of phenolics, tannins, saponins, terpenoids and flavonoids. Phenolic content observed was 34.1 ± 0.004 mgGAE/g extract while the flavonoid content was 81 ± 0.04 mgQE/g extract in the methanol extract. All the extracts inhibited DPPH radical in a concentration-dependent manner although methanol extract showed highest inhibition as compared to n-Hexane extract. DPPH assay of methanol seed extracts revealed good antioxidant properties with IC_{50} values of 7.80 ± 0.15 μ g/ml while ferric ion reducing antioxidant power was observed to be 11.2 ± 0.048 μ mol/g dry wt \pm SD Fe^{2+} reduced. The antioxidant activity in the seed extract is attributed to the presence of the identified phytochemicals. The reported phytochemical studies and antioxidant potential supports its traditional uses and thus *M. uniflorum* could be used as a natural antioxidant, preservative and medicinal agent in food and pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords: *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, antioxidants, phytochemicals, flavonoids, phenolics, free radicals.

OP 12

**A Study of thermal stability of multi component Functionalized Biocomposite materials
Rushali Makkar^{1,4}, Nishita^{1,4}, Geetu Gambhir², Manisha Verma³ * and Sunita Hooda⁴**¹Amity Institute of Applied Sciences, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida, India²Advance Chemistry Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Acharya Narendra Dev College, University of Delhi, Kalkaji, New Delhi- 110019³*Department of Physics, Acharya Narendra Dev College, University of Delhi, Kalkaji, New Delhi- 110019⁴Polymer Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Acharya Narendra Dev College, University of Delhi Kalkaji, New Delhi- 110019

Abstract: Chitin, a naturally occurring biopolymer, has multifunctional and versatile applications due to its wide ranging properties. Furthermore, EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) i.e., amino polycarboxylic acid is generally used for the binding of ferric oxide and ferrous oxide and calcium ion to make them a water soluble complexes even at the neutral pH. We report the successful synthesis and characterization of EDTA-Chitin (ECH) biocomposite. The decomposition kinetics and thermal stability of the material was studied to estimate the lifetime of the product and analyzed by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). We further investigated the effect on the properties of ECH when iron oxide nanoparticles were co-precipitated with ECH. The ECH and Magnetic ECH biocomposite were characterised for the determination of structure, composition, numerous functional groups and analysis of thermal stability. The XRD spectra of ECH (Fig.a) showed the characteristic peaks of EDTA at 29.5°, 53.34°, 57.5° as well as the characteristic peaks of chitin at 9.3° and 19.4° confirming the successful synthesis of the multicomponent sample. Additionally, the presence of characteristic peaks of Fe₃O₄ at 35.4° confirmed the successful and efficacious incorporation of crystalline Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles in magnetic ECH. The TGA curve (Fig.b) of ECH revealed a multi-step degradation pattern. The first weight loss of 5 % occurs between 95.65-142°C and the major weight loss of 28 % is seen between 206-308 °C. This is in contrast to the TGA curve of Magnetic ECH in which onset degradation temperature was 226°C which indicates enhanced thermal stability. The development and characterization of a material with improved thermal stability could find applications in various Textile industries, Cosmetics and Pharmacological fields.

Fig.a

Fig.b

OP 13

REUSABLE VERSUS DISPOSABLE SURGICAL GOWNS: A PREFERENCE COMPARISON AMONG THE SURGICAL STAFF BASED ON COMFORT AND PROTECTION PERFORMANCES OF THE SURGICAL GOWNS**¹M. Nazeem Banu & ²Dr.Shabiya Thaseen****¹Assistant Professor & Ph.D. Scholar, Department of P.G. Studies and Research in Home Science, Justice Basheer Ahmed Sayeed College for Women, Chennai- 18.****²Associate Professor & Research Supervisor, Department of P.G. Studies and Research in Home Science, Justice Basheer Ahmed Sayeed College for Women, Chennai- 18.****Abstract**

Background: Surgical gowns act as a barrier to protect both the patient and the surgical staff by preventing the transmission of microorganisms and body fluids. The fabric construction of the surgical gown (woven/non-woven) affects the comfort when worn for prolonged hours. This study aimed to determine the preference of surgical staff for reusable (woven) and disposable (non-woven) surgical gowns, and analyse their opinions on the reusable surgical gowns using recycled fabric.

Methodology: Descriptive research design with a sample size of 35. The study participants were surgical staff with an average age of 42 years. An online survey using Google form was done to collect data. Wilcoxon Ranked Test was used for statistical analysis of the data.

Results: Statistically significant differences at $p < 0.01$ were revealed for parameters such as comfort, increase in body temperature and environmental impact of the surgical gowns. Fluid repellency and movement restriction showed significance of $p < 0.05$. No significant difference for moist free and itch free properties.

Conclusion: Reusable gowns scored high on comfort and thermal properties, and its use could be encouraged, even with lower fluid repellency due to large pore size of the fabric, and reduced barrier protection after repeated washing and sterilisation cycles. Disposable gowns were preferred by fewer surgical staff for the superior barrier protection; however it raised environmental concerns due its non-biodegradability.

Keywords: Reusable Surgical Gown, Disposable Surgical Gown, Comfort properties, Thermal Properties, Recycled Polyester.

OP 14

Decoding the Economic Revitalization Strategy of Uttar Pradesh: Opportunities and Challenges**Dr. Shree Prakash****Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce
DDU Government P.G. College, Saidabad, Prayagraj, UP**

Abstract: Recently, Uttar Pradesh (UP) has indeed emerged as the torchbearer of a rising new India, spearheading economic transformation across many different economic sectors of the state. It is most populous state accounting for approximately 17 percent of India's population with third largest economy. Its Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) has grown 10 percent in the last three years (2017-18 to 2019-20). The current contribution of UP to the national GDP is 8 percent. In line with the Union Government target of becoming USD 5 trillion economy by 2025-26, the Government of UP has also set target of becoming USD 1 trillion economy by 2027. As per the statistical reports of UPDES, 25 percent of state's output is contributed by the primary sector followed by secondary sector contribution at 25.9 percent and the remaining is contributed by the tertiary sector in 2017.

UP has traditionally been an agrarian economy primarily driven by agriculture but recently it has been witnessing a substantial upsurge in industrial manufacturing due to relentless efforts of UP Government towards attracting investment in different sectors of state economy. UP is gradually emerging as attractive investment destination in different sectors of the state economy due to series of steps taken by the State Government in terms of developing expressways, waterways modernization of railways including dedicated freight corridors, maintenance of law and order situation and skill development of youths for employability among others. The Government of UP has come out with a new UP Industrial Investment and Employment Promotion Policy, 2022 to streamline faster and transparent investment process and various employment generation schemes. In 2018, the Government of UP has come out with a unique scheme 'One District, One Product (ODOP)' wherein it is envisioned to brand and promote 75 unique district specific products separately in its 75 different districts by setting up new MSMEs and helping existing MSMEs involved in production and distribution of those products. Agriculture and allied sectors are among important pillars of state economy and therefore a new approach for inclusive growth of agriculture is being adopted in the current scenario of economic challenges. This calls for

modernization of agriculture and economic empowerment of farmers. The Union Budget, 2023 also provides for promotion of 'digital agriculture' to make farming more profitable and internationally competitive. Renewed efforts to develop digital infrastructure in UP is expected to help agriculture based industries and start-ups and provide impetus for their growth. Moreover, in recent years many steps have been undertaken by the state to promote natural farming which is considered beneficial for the environment, farmers and consumers.

This study attempts to decode economic revitalization strategy of UP Government and also to assess its impact on economic growth of UP. Further, the study would tender a picture about different future challenges and available opportunities.

OP 15

Efficacy of Simulators in Sustained Science Education: Black Body Radiation, a Comparative Study**Bhavya[#], Sanjeeta Rani, Mamta Bhatia, Manisha Verma*****Department of Physics, Acharya Narendra Dev College,
University of Delhi, New Delhi 110019, India**

Abstract: With the COVID 19 limiting in-person laboratory experiences due to shutting down of educational institutions, simulators have played a significant role in sustaining science education during pandemic times. Simulators not only provided a virtual platform for students to simulate experiments and gain hands-on experience in a variety of scientific fields, but also bridged the gap in resource availability during the COVID times between institutions, providing students with equal access to quality education regardless of their location. As such, simulators are likely to remain an important part of science education even after the pandemic has passed. In view of this, it becomes imperative to examine the efficacy of the simulators vis-a-vis the hands-on accuracy of results. Keeping this objective in mind we have analyzed Planck's law of black body radiation comprehensively through a computational code developed by us on Scilab, an open source computational software and calculated its vital constants like Wien's constant and Stefan's constant numerically and graphically. It was also seen that the spectrum obtained by us showed a λ^{-4} dependence (Rayleigh-Jeans law) at high wavelengths and $e^{-x/\lambda T}$ dependence (Wien's law) at short wavelengths. The same were compared with those obtained on multiple simulators and analyzed. We report the values of Wien's constant and Stefan's constant as calculated numerically to be 2.899 mm-K and $5.66 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Jm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{K}^{-4}$ through the code developed by us respectively, which are in good agreement with the theoretical values thus showing the success of our code. The values as determined using various simulators were compared against these and were found to be in good agreement. Therefore, simulators have played a crucial and efficient role in sustaining science education during COVID times by providing an alternative means of learning and practicing scientific concepts, enabling remote learning, and promoting equality in access to quality education.

Keywords: Planck's Law, Rayleigh Jeans Law, Wien's Constant, Stefan's Constant

OP 16**Development of Modules for Understanding the Concept of Staff Meeting among B. Ed. Student-Teachers****Dr. Aradhana Gokhale****Assistant Professor, Guru Nanak College of Education and Research, Bhandup**

Abstract: Teacher educators play an important role in developing abilities, knowledge, skills and values of future teachers. B.Ed. curriculum is constructed in order to provide training and experience to the student-teachers to take responsibilities and cope up with the expectations. The purpose of this paper is to emphasize the Development of Modules for Understanding the Concept of Staff Meeting among B.Ed. student-teachers. Researcher used Cooperative Techniques and Role play and sample was collected from 40 student-teachers. The study was carried out by Pre-Test and Post-Test only Experimental Group Design. Researcher in this study found that the Development of Module as more effective to understand the concept thoroughly and aroused the curiosity and interest among the B. Ed. student-teachers.

Keywords: Staff Meeting, Modules, Student-Teachers

OP 17

**Analysis & Assessment of Soil Samples for Their Physico-Chemical Properties from
Kumaun region (Uttarakhand) India****Prof. Jagmohan Singh Negi****Department of Chemistry, P. N. G. Govt P. G. College Ramnagar
Nainital, Uttarakhand, India**

Abstract: In the present study it was preferred to investigate the soil soil samples for its physico-chemical analysis of some parameters. A proper soil analysis helps to analyse nutrients which are available to plant and which must be supplied to them for a productive crop, through soil variation can be seen within and a small region a small analysis of Kumaun region, Nainital district, The natural environment is clean, but due to multifarious activities of man, it gets polluted resulting in what is called environmental pollution. Uttarakhand State, soil has been done with major macronutrients present. These results will empower future the product development by identifying target in soil microorganisms and the most viable fields. . it was preferred to investigate the soil samples for its physico-chemical analysis of some parameters. Ten representative samples were obtained and analyzed for its pH, EC, Phosphorus, Potassium, Sulfur and Organic Carbon

Keywords: Physico-chemical, EC, PH, Sulfur and Carbon, Phosphorus, Potassium.

OP 18

China and International Law and Order: A Case Study of South China Sea and Indian Ocean Region**Ms Sneha Kulkarni****Assistant Professor, Department of Defence and Strategic Studies, Bhonsala Military College, Rambhoomi, Dr. Moonje Path, Nasik - 422005, Maharashtra, India**

Abstract: The research inquiries into India's current approaches to Maritime Security Policies in general and the South China Sea from the perspective of an Indian Act East Policy in the East Asian security super complex. China refuses to address jurisdiction through formal dispute settlement processes, and has so far resisted multilateral approaches to resolve the fate of the island groups. China continues to assert its claim of jurisdiction in the heart of the South China Sea, enclosed by China's "9-dash line". Beijing's not just keen to annex the South China Sea and Taiwan; it has its eyes set on whole other island chains to dominate the Indian and Pacific Oceans. India is currently the undisputed power in its maritime neighbourhood. The Indian Ocean and South China Sea comprise a region with three significant maritime powers; India, China and the US and India must reassure China of its position. China is seeking to unchain itself from what it sees as the shackles of Western cultural, military and economic dominance. Shaped by theoretical insights from defensive realism and security studies and based on empirical analysis of India's policy decisions from 2013 to the present, the research evaluates India's reach and limitations over its diplomatic and naval strategic policies with key Southeast Asian and extra regional states. While identifying the need to update current India's Naval Strategy with the follow up of UNCLOS to better protect freedom of navigation in the South China Sea; the study finds relevant provocations for a closer India-China cooperative engagement; so as to both improve the security architecture in this Maritime Region and for the sake of India's own security at large.

Key Words: UNCLOS, IOR, SCS, Indian Ocean Region, South China Sea, Maritime Security

OP 19

Collaboration of AYUSH with Dentistry: An Evidence-based Perspective
Dr. Premalatha BR¹, Dr. Sunila BS², Dr. Vidyadevi Chandavarkar³ Dr. Mithilesh Mishra⁴
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Research, Mysuru, Karnataka, India. ^{3,4}School of Dental Sciences, Sharda University, Greater
Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract: Traditional medicine modalities are practiced since time immemorial across the world. AYUSH is an acronym for: Ayurveda, Yoga and Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy. These are the six indigenous systems of medicine practiced in India.

Oral diseases are considered as a major global health problem. The global need for safe, effective, economical preventive and treatment options for oral diseases arises from the fact that there is an increase in disease incidence, microbial resistance to antibiotics, opportunistic infections and financial considerations in developing countries.

Although new treatments and medical technologies are plentiful, nonetheless many are now looking for simpler, gentler therapies for improving the quality of life and avoiding iatrogenic problems. We often forget that modern medicine reaches only a relatively small group of people. Traditional medical systems are easily accessible, cheaper and relatively safer.

The techniques and natural phytochemicals used in traditional medicine are considered as good alternatives to synthetic chemicals. Systematic exploration of AYUSH may lead to development of novel preventive or therapeutic strategies for oral health thus heralding in a new era of Integrative Dentistry which will unite the best practices from both traditional and modern systems. This paper focuses on the AYUSH modalities that can be collaborated with modern Dentistry with an evidence-based perspective.

Keywords: AYUSH, Dentistry, Integrative Dentistry, Traditional medicine.

OP 20

Covid-19: Neurological and Psychological Effects (A Review Study)**Dr. Anita Kumari****Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology
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Abstract: Covid-19 is a zoonotic viral pandemic that started in Wuhan city of China and spread all over the world. It is caused by SARS-Cov-2 which belongs to the genus Betacoronavirus and subgenus Sarbecovirus of coronaviruses. These viruses are reported to cause severe acute respiratory syndrome. SARS-Cov-2 shares 80% sequence homology with SARS-Cov and 88% with bats SARS-like corona virus while genetically distant from the SARS and MERS viruses. SARS-Cov-2 is a novel form of coronaviruses. It is ellipsoidal in shape with characteristic crown-shaped appearance. Spike proteins provide characteristics appearance to SARS-Cov-2. The copy number of spike protein is 10 times higher than that of the influenza virus. It is RNA virus. Here RNA is present together with ribonucleoproteins in the lumen. Human gets infection from infected animals like bats and pangolins. After entering human body, it becomes contagious as infection spreads from human to human via respiratory droplets. It is initially a respiratory tract infection transmitted via air droplets. Subsequently, it spreads to majority of organs due to virus binding to angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors located on several different human cells. The SARS-CoV-2 virus has caused a worldwide pandemic with a major impact on health care systems and economies. Pathophysiology is associated with majority of the organs. On an average one third of infected patients develop a broad spectrum of neurological symptoms followed by psychological effect. Effects produced by Covid-19 on the central nervous system are headache, delirium, cerebrovascular attacks, seizures, encephalopathy, meningitis, dysexecutive syndrome. Moreover, effects produced on peripheral nervous system are dysosmia, anosmia, dysgeusia, ageusia, acute myelitis, Guillain-Barre syndrome, Miller Fisher syndrome, polyneuritis cranialis. Psychological effects of Covid-19 include uncontrolled fears related to infection, pervasive anxiety, disabling loneliness, frustration and boredom.

OP 21

Factors affecting job satisfaction & job loyalty of employees in higher education**Ms. Shweta Chauhan¹ and Ms. Sneha Gupta²**¹Assistant Professor, Allenhouse Institute of Management, Kanpur, UP²Assistant Professor, Allenhouse Business School, Kanpur, UP

Abstract: The present study investigates the factors affecting job satisfaction and job loyalty among employees in higher education using SPSS. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, and data were collected from 150 employees working in universities and colleges in Uttar Pradesh. The study used a structured questionnaire to collect data on demographic characteristics, job satisfaction, job loyalty, and factors affecting these constructs. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Internal Consistency, Reliability and factor analysis. The results showed that job satisfaction and job loyalty were positively correlated with factors such as organizational commitment, job security, and work-life balance. The findings suggest that higher education institutions need to pay attention to factors such as organizational commitment, job security, and work-life balance to improve job satisfaction and job loyalty among their employees. The study provides insights for higher education policymakers and administrators to design effective strategies and policies that enhance employee well-being and organizational performance.

OP 22

Occlusal Wear of CAD-CAM fabricated restorations**Dr. Yogesh S. Ingole****Assistant Professor, Department of Prosthetic Dentistry,
Government Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur**

Background: The computer-aided design computer-aided manufacturing (CAD-CAM) systems have been advanced dramatically over the last two decades. Recently, technological developments in CAD-CAM systems have enabled clinicians and dental laboratories to manufacture various kinds of restorations using different materials. Wear of tooth structure is a natural unavoidable process which occurs when tooth and tooth, or tooth and restoration are in contact and slide against each other. However, this natural process may be accelerated by the introduction of restorations whose properties of wear differ from those of the tooth structure that they slide against. So, this review evaluates the wear of different CAD-CAM fabricated crowns and their antagonists; which may influence the occlusal contact areas between these occluding surfaces.

Methodology: This is a traditional or narrative type of review.

Discussion: The review includes the articles involving various CAD-CAM fabricated crowns like Zirconia, Lithium Disilicate, Resin matrix ceramic, PEEK, Zirconia-reinforced Lithium Silicate materials exhibiting their own wear, as well as the wear of opposing natural teeth over a long-term period.

Summary: Contrary to the general belief, CAD-CAM Zirconia crowns caused comparatively less occlusal wear of the opposing natural teeth as compared to Lithium Disilicate and Zirconia-reinforced Lithium Silicate.

Conclusion: The CAD-CAM based restorations as well as their opposing natural teeth both showed significant occlusal wear over a long-term period which does have an influence on the occlusal contact areas between these occluding surfaces.

OP 23

**Water Quality index of FreshWater Body with Reference to Water Quality Parameters
from Punjab (India)****Sandeep Kaur¹, Rajinder Kaur^{2*} and Abhinav Saxena³**¹Department of Zoology, Baba Farid Group of Institutions, Deon (Bathinda) 151001^{2*}Department of Higher Education, Government of Punjab, Mohali, 160062³Department of Zoology, Akal University, Talwandi Sabo, Bathinda-151302

Abstract: Monitoring of various water parameters of pond water and its fluctuations are useful not only to assess the natural conditions for various purpose such as fish farming, domestic purposes, but also be cautions to environmental damages. Water Quality Index is a method that enables an easier interpretation of the monitoring data. The present study was undertaken to determine the water quality of pond situated in Mansa district, Punjab during June 2017 to May 2018. Eight physico-chemical water parameters were evaluated from different selected sites of pond (S1 to S8). Different physico-chemical water parameters were analysed seasonally by following the standard methods given in APHA (2012) and Trivedi and Goel (1984). The values of WQI of different sites observed as S1:143.3, S2:103.8, S3:142.6, S4:127.2, S5:75.6, S6:68.5, S7:56.1 and S8:62.4 which indicate very poor water quality at site S5, poor water quality at site S6, S7 and S8 and unsuitable as S1, S2, S3 and S4 sites. This represents the water quality is highly unsuitable for commercial purpose and can be used for irrigation, industrial purpose and fish culture for suitable fish species.

Keywords: physico-chemical parameters, pond quality, water pollution, WQI.

OP 24

Transforming India through Self-reliance, Atmanirbhar Bharat**Dr. Bansi Rajnikant Shah****Assistant Professor, JJCET Commerce College, Junagadh (Gujarat)**

Abstract: The present research paper focuses on one of the most effective ways to make India Self-reliant which is Entrepreneurship Development. Atmanirbhar Bharat or Self-reliant India is a vision for the country's economic development to create a self-sustaining economy by reducing dependence on foreign imports. However, unemployment remains a significant challenge in the country, particularly among young people and women. The present paper represents the role of Entrepreneurship to overcome the problem of unemployment in the developing countries like India. In recent years, various reports and studies have shown high levels of joblessness, and the COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated the unemployment crisis in the country.

The researcher found from the secondary data from the National Statistical Office, the unemployment rate in India stood at 6.9% in September 2021. Initiatives taken by the Indian government to address the issue of unemployment include Skill India Mission, Make in India, Startup India, National Career Service, Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, Pradhan Mantri Rozgar Yojana, and Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana. Student Start-up and Innovation Policy (SSIP) is also initiative taken by government to build and support the innovation and start-up qualities in students studying in any field.

To fight unemployment in India will require concerted efforts from policymakers, employers, and civil society groups to create more job opportunities, improve skills and education, and address structural barriers that prevent certain groups from accessing employment.

Keywords: Unemployment, Entrepreneurship, Self-reliant, Innovation, Start-up, SSIP

OP 25

An Alopecia Universalis - Ruhya in Ayurved (loss of hair from the entire body parts) patient with growing of hair on all the hair growing parts of the body by Ayurvedic Nasya procedure

Dr. Jay Rajnikant Shah

Medical Officer (Assistant Professor on deputation) Institute of Teaching and Research in Ayurveda, Jamnagar (Gujarat)

Clinical Case Study

Abstract: The present research work discusses a case study of a 42-year-old housewife who complained of complete hair loss from all the parts of her body. The patient had undergone allopathic treatment and Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) therapy for about five years but with no positive outcome. The patient was diagnosed with *Ruhya* in Ayurved, a rare and challenging disease that can have a profound effect on physical and emotional well-being. The treatment plan included various *Ayurvedic* procedures such as *Nasya karma*, *Shirolepa*, *Shiro Abhyanga*, *Rasayana*, and *Dosha Pachana*. After the 13th sitting of *Marsha Nasya*, the patient experienced hair growth in the lid margin, eyebrow region, inside the nose, and the occipital part of the head. The patient had 11 follow-ups, and during the last follow-up, the patient had a full head of hair. The discussion highlights the importance of using Ayurvedic procedures for treating hair loss caused by chronic illness, premature aging or nutritional deficiency.

Keywords: *Ruhya*, Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) Therapy, *Marsha Nasya*, *Shirolepa*, *Shiro Abhyanga*, *Rasayana*, *Dosha Pachana*, Chronic Illness.

OP 26

Salivary Lactate Dehydrogenase as a salivary Biomarker in Periodontitis and tooth loss**Dr. Sunila B Sangappa****Associate Professor, Department of Prosthodontics
JSS Dental College & Hospital Mysuru**

Aim: This study aims at evaluating the association between salivary lactate dehydrogenase (SLDH) levels among type II diabetes mellitus (T2DM) subjects with chronic periodontitis (CP) and tooth loss to check the diagnostic value of SLDH as a noninvasive biomarker. **Materials and methods:** Seventy-six subjects aged from 30 to 70 years with at least 15 remaining teeth were selected for the study. Hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels confirmed diabetic status while CP was assessed based on periodontal parameters with a full-mouth periodontal examination, following which the subjects were classified into four groups. Group I: controls—systemically healthy individuals (HbA1c levels $\leq 6.4\%$), without CP; group II: non-T2DM with CP—systemically healthy individuals (HbA1c $\leq 6.4\%$) with CP; group III: T2DM (HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$) with CP; group IV: T2DM (HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$) with CP and tooth loss due to periodontitis. Unstimulated whole saliva in fasting was collected from subjects and quantitatively assessed using a colorimetric lactate dehydrogenase assay kit. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post hoc test was used for statistical analysis. Statistical significance was set at 5% level ($p < 0.05$). Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient compared the relationship between different variables.

Results: ANOVA of the four groups' mean scores yielded significant variation in SLDH levels ($F = 11.2889$, $p < 0.05$). The relationship between variables of HbA1c levels with SLDH activity levels (mU/mL) and average periodontal pocket depth (APPD) was statistically significant and a moderate correlation was found with Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient. **Conclusion:** Study outcomes indicate a high prevalence of CP in T2DM. The severity of periodontitis and tooth loss significantly altered LDH enzyme activity and exhibited elevated LDH levels indicating a valuable noninvasive salivary biomarker in the detection of periodontitis.

Clinical significance: In view of saliva as a mainstay noninvasive screening method of periodontal disease, SLDH can assume a significant role in detecting elevated glycemic levels and distinguishing the severity of periodontitis. Routine use in general practice and dental offices can ensure early detection and monitoring.

OP 27

Removal of pesticides from water by using sustainable adsorbents: A review**Shreya Kotnala^{1*} and Twinkle²**¹Department of Chemistry, School of Basic & Applied Sciences, SGRR University, Dehradun, India²Department of Physics, School of Basic & Applied Sciences, SGRR University, Dehradun, India

Abstract: Pesticides, persistent chemicals that are of concern due to their predominance in different ecosystems, are the primary organic pollutants in the world. Pesticide residues undergo physical, chemical, and biochemical degradation in nature, but due to their high stability and, in some instances, water solubility, they continue to be present in the ecosystem. Pesticides have been eliminated using a variety of methods that fall under the categories of biological, chemical, physical, and physicochemical processes of remediation from a variety of substrates, including water and soil. Adsorption is thought to be the most effective treatment technique due to its low cost, universal applicability, and simplicity of use. The use of inexpensive, non-polluting materials as a workable substitute for pesticides, as well as their metabolite adsorption method and removal technology, are highlighted and given an overview in this review. This review incorporates the classification of pesticides and the impact of pesticides on the ecosystem as well as on human health. In this review, older and more recent methods and materials including bioremediation using microorganisms, clay, activated carbon, and polymer materials, as well as chemical treatment based on oxidation processes are described that were created to remove particular pesticides according to a previous classification.

Keywords: Pesticides; adsorption; sustainable adsorbents; eco-friendly

OP 28

Asses Knowledge Gap on Morbidities, its Preventive, Control Measures & Practice of using Preventive Measures Related to Air Pollution among Traffic Police in WB (Kolkata)**Snita Bhunia****Senior Lecturer, College of Nursing CNMCH, Kolkata****Abstract**

Back ground: Air pollution is a major problem of present scenario, which has serious toxicological impact on human health and environment Air pollution is considered as the major environmental risk factor in the incidence and progression of some diseases such as asthma, lung cancer. Traffic police by their profession doing well for our society. They are vulnerable people to developed morbidities related air pollution.

Aims and objectives: To assess Knowledge gap of the traffic regarding morbidities, its preventive, control measures and practice of preventive and control measures related to air pollution among Traffic police in W.B (Kolkata) and to examine the association of knowledge gap with practice measures.

Materials & Methods: A descriptive study was conducted “Assess knowledge gap on morbidities, its preventive, control measures and practice of using preventive measures related to air pollution among Traffic police in W.B (Kolkata). Conceptual frame work of the study was based on Pender’s health promotional model. Study was done with 200 Traffic Police under different Kolkata traffic guard, W.B. sample selection was done by probability sampling technique through lottery method. Data regarding knowledge were collected through structured questionnaire.

Results: Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. Study findings revealed that Maximum 47.5 % traffic police have good knowledge regarding morbidities, its preventive, and control measures related to air pollution. Mean of the knowledge score is 6.5, median 7, mode 15.375, SD 3. There is significant association between Knowledge level of traffic police & practice of using preventive measures for prevention of morbidities regarding Air pollution among traffic police as at one degree of freedom calculated chi-square value (8.8551), yates correction (7.7944) is greater than p value at level 0.05.

Conclusion: It has implication on control and prevention of occupational health hazards. Based on the study findings information booklet to be developed for increase their knowledge and practice of preventive measures during their working period.

Keywords: Traffic Police, Knowledge, Morbidities, Prevent, Control, Air pollution, Information booklet.

OP 29**The Psychological impact and coping mechanism of COVID -19 on Staff Nurses: A retrospective study****Usha Mallick¹ and Dr Ratna Chhaya Singh²****¹Associate Professor, HOD (Officiating) Department of Nursing Aliah University****Introduction**

The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has affected people in more than one way. It is accompanied by various morbidity and mortality trajectories with long lasting effects impacting public health, with psychosocial consequences across the globe. This upsurge in COVID-19 cases has heavily burdened and in many cases overwhelmed and impaired the healthcare systems. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus. Healthcare professional face lot of difficulties in maintaining the quality of healthcare in these days. Investigator herself worked a lot during that period and could able to see the impact of the staff nurses of covid -19.

Objectives

- To assess psychological impact of covid19 in anxiety, depression, stress.
- To assess coping mechanism of the staff nurse in total and due to their intra variables.
- To find out the relationship of psychological impact with demographic variables of the staff nurses.
- To find out the relationship of coping mechanism with demographic variables of the staff nurses.

Research Methodology-

Research Design-Descriptive survey research design

Population of the study- Staff nurses of Govt and Private Hospitals

Total sample size-300

Sampling technique- Non probability convenience sampling technique

Research TOOL- A. Standardized tool (DASS 21 SCALE) was used to measure the depression, anxiety and stress level of the staff nurse due to Covid19.

B. Brief cope scale was used for measuring coping of the staff nurses.

Results: Majority of the staff nurses 51.6% (155) are from the age group of more than 30 years. Majority of the staff nurses 50.6% (152) are from the Govt Hospital. Study revealed that 98 (32.67%) staff had moderate level of depression. 121(40.33%) staff had moderate level of anxiety. 103 (34.33%) staff had moderate level of stress. 162 (54%) staff had moderate coping.

Conclusion: The results of the study show that the main psychological impacts of caring for people with COVID-19 manifested by the nurses were fear, anxiety, stress, social isolation, depressive symptoms, uncertainty, and frustration.

Keywords: Covid-19, Anxiety, Depression, Stress, Coping

OP 30

Use of E-learning & Face to Face learning strategies for Nursing students in relation to their some personal variables**Rumi Sen¹ and Dr. Ratna Chhaya Singh²**¹Associate Professor, Department of Nursing, Aliah University, Kolkata²Dean Nursing, Mansarovar Global University, Bhopal

Abstract: For effective teaching learning process and to cover the divergent need and aspiration of the Nursing students a number of strategies are adopted by the teachers. Among them E-learning and Face to Face learning are the two strategies which are very relevant in the present changing situation. Hence it is a very burning current research area.

This study aims to investigate use of E-learning and Face to Face learning strategies for Nursing students in relation to their parental educational variation, occupation and income.

Convenient sampling method was used to select 300 nursing students studying in different nursing colleges of Kolkata. A 5 point likert scale questionnaire was used.

Result shows that obtained “t” value $0.92 <$ the tabular value at 0.05 levels so there exist no significant difference between the use of E-learning of nursing students in relation to parental education variation whereas there exist significant difference between the face-to-face learning of nursing students in relation to parental education variation as the obtained “t” value $2.92 >$ the tabular value at 0.05 levels so .

There exist significant difference between the use of E-learning and face to face learning of nursing students in relation to parental occupation variation as the obtained “t” value 3.00 & 2.99 respectively $>$ the tabular value at 0.05 level .

There exist significant difference between the use of E-learning and face to face learning of nursing students in relation to parental income variation as the obtained “t” value 3.82 & 3.18 respectively $>$ the tabular value at 0.05 level .

It is concluded that parental education have no relation with E-learning of nursing students but parental occupation and income have significance relation with E-learning and Face to Face learning strategies for Nursing students.

Keywords: E-learning, face-to-face learning, nursing, students

OP 31

The Vital Role of Artificial Intelligence in the Developing Human Resource Field**Dr. Dhyanadipta Panda****Asst. Professor-II KIIT Deemed to be University**

Abstract: Artificial Intelligence, the term heard and recited in complete abundance since the oncoming and surge of digitalization in the modern world. In the organization field, with its vast division of sectors, technological development and the mark of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the peri sphere has opened the vast gates of progressive and unhindered growth. Human Resource (HR) or human resource management (HRM) system, does not only deal with the recruiting, onboarding and managing process but supervises the organization as a whole along with its contribution in the field of important decision making in order to form a productive and effective workforce which is an asset for any organization. A few years back, the adherence and effectiveness technologically advanced utilities and the major component of artificial intelligence was just a theory in the contrast of organization development. With the passage of years and in minimal time, the importance and revolution caused by Artificial Intelligence has not only made its inevitable position at the core of the organizational mainframe but also procrastinated the idea of slow development with its extensive and utterly useful features. In this paper we will discuss about the importance and developments of HRM by Artificial Intelligence. We will discuss upon various factors that determine the developmental flow and also take insights of the revolutionary changes in the long processes caused by AI.

Keyword: Digitalisation, Artificial Intelligence, Human Resource Management

OP 32

2023: The International Year of Millets**¹Dr. Rashmi Mathur and ²Dr. Isha Gunwal****¹Associate Prof. Botany Department, Sri Aurobindo College, University of Delhi****²Assistant Prof. Botany Department, Swami Shraddhanand College, University of Delhi**

Abstract: Millets were among the first food grains to be domesticated. The cultivation of millets started in Asia almost 4000 years ago, to be used as animal feed and subsequently also for human consumption. Millets are annual grasses with small seeds that are farmed as grain crops in dry, subtropical, and tropical areas. Millets are a type of coarse cereal grain with a granular, textured surface. They pack more protein, fibre, iron, and calcium per serving than either rice or wheat. They are promising diabetes defence foods with a low glycaemic index. To make it easier for consumers to understand the benefits, the government changed the name from coarse grains to nutricereals. Following a proposal by India, which hopes to become a global hub for millets, the United Nations has designated 2023 as the International Year of the Millets. This year the focus will be on the nutritional and health benefits of millets, the suitability of the sturdy and hardy millet crops for cultivation under adverse and changing climatic conditions, and the creation of sustainable market opportunities for many countries around the world to benefit farmers and consumers globally. Processing millets uses 40% less energy, takes 50% less time to cultivate than wheat, and requires 70% less water than rice. Millet is grown in several Asian and African countries, and India is the largest producer. Indian millets include *Eleusine coracana* (Ragi), *Sorghum vulgare* (Jowar), *Pennisetum glaucum* (Bajra), *Panicum sumatrense* (Samai), and *Panicum miliaceum* (Chena). As the world's agri-food systems struggle to meet the needs of a growing population, resilient cereals like millets offer a cost-effective and nutritional solution. Therefore, efforts should be ramped up to promote their cultivation. Millets are excellent ancient crops that have a number of nutritional benefits. Millets are an affordable and nutritious option that has immense potential to aid in overcoming the current global problem of hunger, mitigation of the effects of climate change, the overall transformation of our food and farming systems, empowerment of smallholder farmers, sustainable development, and the advancement of biodiversity.

Keywords: Nutricereals; Low GI; Adverse Climatic conditions.

OP 33

Development and evaluation of gluten-free noodles prepared from foxtail millet and orange peel powder**Ritika B. Yadav*, Devansh Chandel****Department of Food Technology****Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak (Haryana)-India**

Abstract: In recent times, millets are gaining attention due to their good nutritional value and health benefits. Foxtail millet contains protein, fiber, minerals, and other nutrients. The orange peel powder (OPP) is a good source of antioxidants and fiber. Foxtail millet flour (FMF) and OPP can be used in gluten-free foods to enhance the nutritional and sensorial properties. The objective of the research was to assess the suitability of foxtail millet flour and orange peel powder for gluten-free noodle preparation and also to analyze the impact of addition of FMF and OPP on the cooking and sensorial characteristics of noodles. The noodles were developed from the foxtail millet flour with the addition of orange peel powder in different concentrations which were coded as A₁ (control, 100% refined wheat flour), A₂ (5% OPP: 95% FMF), A₃ (10% OPP:90% FMF), and A₄ (15% OPP:85% FMF). Foxtail millet flour, orange peel powder and different blends were analyzed for their functional properties such as water absorption capacity, oil absorption capacity, bulk density, and solubility index. The developed noodles were analyzed for their cooking, nutritional, and sensorial properties. The significant difference in cooking properties of noodles was reported. An increase in cooking time and cooked weight was noted in noodles after substitution of FMF as compared with control. However, the cooking loss decreased in FMF noodles than control noodles. A significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in flavonoid and phenolic content of noodles was found with the increase in level of OPP. The addition of FMF and OPP also affected the sensory properties of cooked noodles. The noodles developed from blends of FMF with OPP were darker in color than control noodles. The overall acceptability of noodles prepared from 5% OPP and 95% FMF was highest than other blends and very close to control noodles.

OP 34

Carbon Monoxide (CO) levels in Smokers and Non-smokers: A Review of Literature**Dr. Vidyadevi Chandavarkar¹ and Dr. Mithilesh Mishra²**¹Associate Professor, School of Dental Sciences, Sharda University²Associate Professor, School of Dental Sciences, Sharda University

Abstract: For a long time now, it has been known that smoking is associated both etiologically and prognostically with numerous diseases of the respiratory system. However, despite this knowledge, many subjects continue to smoke. It has been reported that the use of carbon monoxide (CO) monitor to demonstrate an immediate and potentially harmful consequence of smoking increased further the number who complied with advice to quit. Levels of CO in exhaled air have been widely used as indication of smoking cessation. The measurements of exhaled CO level may provide an immediate, non-invasive method of assessing smoking status, although other sources of pollution including exhaust gases causes elevations in the fractional concentrations of CO in expired air. Several research studies have been conducted using breath analyser to measure end expiratory CO concentrations in Smokers and Non-smokers and concluded that breath analysis was rapid to assess the risk of CO poisoning. This paper will review the various research studies on CO levels in Smokers and Non-smokers.

OP 35

Exploring the Role of Culture in English Language Teaching**Prof. Dr. Nilesh H. Chitte****Pratap College, Amalner, District- Jalgaon**

Abstract: The importance of culture in English language teaching has been widely acknowledged in recent years. By taking into consideration of its significance, it becomes indispensable to integrate the cultural elements into the curriculum. This paper aims to explore the role of culture in English language teaching. The paper begins by defining culture and its relationship to language teaching. Later it explores the different ways in which culture can be integrated into language teachings, such as through literature, film, music, and art. While incorporating cultural elements into language teaching, it emerges challenges. This paper makes language teachers aware of these challenges and suggests developing strategies to address them. Thereafter, the paper examines the benefits of integrating culture into language teaching. It argues that by exposing learners to different cultural perspectives and practices, language teachers can help develop learners' intercultural communicative competence. If the learners are made culturally aware, they can communicate effectively in multicultural and multilingual settings. In all, the paper claims that this fusion enhances language learning and also fosters intercultural understanding and competence.

The paper also argues that in blending culture into language teaching, language teachers play a vital role. Therefore, it is expected that they should be knowledgeable about the cultures of their learners and be able to adapt their teaching practices accordingly. In a nutshell, this paper highlights the importance of culture in English language teaching, the benefits of integrating culture into language teaching, latent challenges and how to deal with them and the conscious role of teachers in creating a classroom environment in diverse cultural backgrounds.

Keywords: Culture, language teaching, intercultural understanding, diversity, and communication.

OP 36

A study of evaluation of emotional regulation in medical students**Dr. Neelima.P¹ and Dr. R. Ravi sunder²****¹Professor & Head, Department of Anatomy, GIMSR, GITAM deemed to be University,
Visakhapatnam-530045****²Professor & Head, Department of Anatomy, GIMSR, GITAM deemed to be University,
Visakhapatnam-530045**

Abstract: Rampant advances in technology turned out to be a double edged sword resulting in both positive and negative challenges. The victims are the young generation adolescents who compete for updating and ever changing technology. In fact artificial intelligence is controlling the emotional regulation of these adolescents. Emotional regulation is the ability to recognize, manage and respond to the emotions. It may be upregulation or down regulation depending on the circumstances. There are two components in emotional regulation- cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression. The present study is questionnaire based, done to evaluate the emotional regulation in medical students of north costal Andhra Pradesh. Cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression components have been analysed separately. The aim of the study has been explained to the target group. Emotional regulation questionnaire with 10 questions was the study tool. After taking informed consent, the google forms with the questionnaire were circulated. Identity was kept anonymous. A total of 238 students (126 girls, 112 boys) participated in the study. The google forms have been evaluated and reports were illustrated graphically. Gender wise tabulation also has been done. Interesting results were derived which will be presented at the conference. The present generation is gradually becoming reliant on the technology and it is not a surprise that the artificial intelligence will control human brains in near future. This study can be expanded to be done on various age groups as well to derive at conclusions reflecting the importance of emotional regulation.

Keywords: Emotional regulation, adolescents, cognitive reappraisal, expressive suppression.

OP 37

Inland water quality monitoring using sentinel-2 and Landsat-8: A Case Study of natural and artificial Lakes in Uttarakhand, India**Shalini Kumari¹, Rakesh Singh² and Virendra Bahadur Singh²**¹School of Basic & Applied Sciences, Shri Guru Ram Rai University (SGRRU), Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India²Department of Petroleum Engineering, Graphic Era Deemed to be University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India

Abstract: The integration of Sentinel-2A and Landsat-8 satellite data provides a comprehensive understanding of inland water quality over time, enabling water resource managers to make informed decisions for protecting these valuable resources. This study aims to demonstrate the applicability of harmonizing Sentinel-2 MSI and Landsat-8 SRP satellite imagery products to estimate various water quality parameters, including chlorophyll-a, mean Secchi depth (Zsd), mean Trophic State Index (TSI), and mode Trophic State Index class (TSI class), for natural and artificial reservoirs/lakes such as Naini Lake, Dodi Tal, Tehri Lake, Naukuchia Lake, and Ramganga Reservoir. The investigation was motivated by climate change and anthropogenic influence on inland water bodies. To monitor lake conditions, this study proposes an atmospheric correction hypothesis based on standard ocean-color approaches.

Keywords: Lake monitoring, Google Earth Engine (GEE), Secchi Depth, Chlorophyll-a, Trophic State Index.

OP 38

Efficient Flood Mapping Using Multi-Criteria Decision-Making and GIS: A Case Study of Kosi River Basin, North Bihar, India**Rakesh Singh¹, Parvesh Saini² and Shalini Kumari³**¹**Department of Petroleum Engineering, Graphic Era Deemed to be University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India**²**Department of Geology, DBS (PG) College, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India**³**School of Basic & Applied Sciences, Shri Guru Ram Rai University (SGRRU), Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India**

Abstract: Flood mapping is crucial for appropriate land use planning in flood-prone areas to identify areas of risk and prioritize mitigation and response efforts. Structural measures along dynamic rivers like Kosi are not rational and minimizing flood risk and damage is a better approach. This thesis presents an efficient methodology to accurately delineate flooded areas in the Kosi River Basin, North Bihar, India, using a multi-criteria decision-making technique in a GIS environment. The flood map is generated by computing a composite index of flooded regions derived from topographical, land cover, geomorphic, and population-related data. The study uses digital elevation data from the US Geological Survey's EROS Data Center and remotely sensed data from Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) for change detection. The research aims to increase awareness among the scientific community about the need for flood mapping and non-structural flood management measures to reduce short-term and long-term damages. The study uses SAR Sentinel1 to generate a flood extent of the Kosi basin area, a straightforward change detection approach, JRC Global Human Settlement Population Layer to estimate the number of exposed people, and MODIS Land Cover Type product to estimate affected cropland.

Keywords: Kosi River, Google Earth Engine (GEE), Flood extent detection, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), MODIS

OP 39

Emerging Trends in Entrepreneurial Training in Higher Education**Dr. Jomon Lonappan¹ and Dr. Meera Jacob²**¹M.B.A, Ph.D, Assistant Professor, SDM PG Centre, Mangalore²M.B.B.S, M.D, Associate Professor, Yenepoya Medical College, Derlakatte

Abstract: Introducing entrepreneurship courses in higher education builds core competence among students, even though not all students who are exposed to entrepreneurship education would start their own venture immediately or at a later date. The question whether entrepreneurship can be taught has been a major debate in entrepreneurship research and even led to the question whether entrepreneurship can actually be learnt [Edwards&Muir2004; Rae, 2000]. Basic outcome of this study has been the identification of different aspects in entrepreneurship education of which some are teachable with the help of classical education tools and formats, while others do not seem to be teachable in the same manner. Against the background of these findings, active learning concepts were increasingly integrated into entrepreneurship education [Shepherd&Douglas, 1996]

Wealth and a high majority of jobs are created by small businesses started by entrepreneurially minded individuals, many of whom go on to create big businesses. People exposed to entrepreneurship frequently express that they have more opportunity to exercise creative freedoms, higher self-esteem, and an overall greater sense of control over their own lives. As a result, many experienced business people, political leaders, economists, and educators believe that fostering a robust entrepreneurial culture will maximize individual and collective economic and social success on a local, national, and global scale. It is with this in mind that the National Standards for Entrepreneurship Education were developed: to prepare youth and adults to succeed in an entrepreneurial economy.

OP 40

Crosssectional Study on Building A Framework for Professionalism among Health Care Professionals**Dr. Meera Jacob¹ and Dr. Jomon Lonappan²**¹Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Yenepoya Medical College²Assistant Professor, SDM Centre for postgraduate studies and research**Abstract:**

Background: The concept of professionalism involves a set of attitudes and behaviours that one has towards his profession. This can bring about positive changes in the life of the students in academic achievements, personal and professional beliefs. It is also expressed as a commitment to perform professional responsibilities, adhere to ethical values and be sensitive to patients of varying diversity. Medical professionalism is facing a transition from autonomy to accountability, teamwork and evidence-based medicine. So, it has come to a point that professionalism should be taught than being learned from role models.

Methods: present cross-sectional study recruited 90 participants including medical interns, postgraduates and faculties. Questionnaire designed by researchers and tested for validity and reliability was used. Questions were grouped as scenarios for various attributes of professionalism.

Results: Based on practices of attributes of professionalism maximum good response were for accountability and equity. Average response was obtained for honesty and least for altruism

Conclusion: Considered as one entity this decline has to be addressed in formal education in this area followed by assessment of the levels of professionalism.

Keywords: Medical professionalism, medical education, .attributes, altruism, honesty.

OP 41

**Exploring New Horizons: Research and Innovation in Arts, Humanities and Culture
Education****Dr. Sheelu Sengar****Department of English, Dayanand Vedic College, Orai**

Abstract: Since the dawn of civilization, research and development have been fundamental and essential components of human existence. Innovation and progress are crucial, and research forms the foundation of these processes. Research is inherent in all aspects of our lives and has consistently been the driving force behind a nation's progress and development. Research precedents are adapting to meet evolving societal, cultural, environmental, economic, industrial, technological, and scientific criteria. This paper highlights the role of research in improving teaching methods, enhancing the quality of education, and promoting cultural awareness. It also emphasizes the need for innovation in curriculum development and technology integration to create a more engaging and interactive learning experience. Through an interdisciplinary approach this study argues that by exploring new horizons in arts, humanities, and culture education, we can equip students with the knowledge and skills necessary to succeed in a rapidly changing world. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of arts, humanities, and culture education in fostering critical thinking, creativity, and empathy among students. However, to fully realize the potential of these disciplines, it is essential to engage in research and innovation to improve teaching methods, curriculum development, and technology integration. Innovation in arts, humanities, and culture education can also transform the way students learn and engage with these disciplines. By incorporating emerging technologies such as virtual reality, augmented reality, and gamification, educators can create immersive and interactive learning experiences that can inspire creativity and foster critical thinking. Additionally, innovation in curriculum development can help to incorporate interdisciplinary learning, promoting a holistic approach to education that recognizes the interconnectedness of different fields of knowledge.

Keywords- Innovation, Interdisciplinary, Technology, Disciplines, Holistic

OP 42

Photoacoustic Imaging in Dental Sciences for Caries Detection: A Novel Diagnostic Technique**Dr. Jyoti Wankhade¹****¹Assistant Professor, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Government Dental College and Hoospital, Nagpur.440003**

Background: The photoacoustic (PA) effect refers to the generation of acoustic waves by the absorption of electromagnetic (EM) energy. Photoacoustic imaging also called optoacoustic or thermoacoustic imaging has the potential to image animal or human organs. Nonionizing waves, such as short laser or radiofrequency (rf) pulses, are often used to excite megahertz ultrasound waves, referred to as photoacoustic or thermoacoustic signals, in biological tissues. Unlike ionizing x-ray radiation, non-ionizing waves pose no health hazard.

The penetration depth of photoacoustic imaging is greater than that of purely optical imaging techniques, which are usually affected by the strong optical scattering of tissue. Furthermore, photoacoustic imaging retains the high spatial resolution of optical methods, which cannot be achieved by conventional ultrasound imaging. Photoacoustic imaging has been used in a variety of medical diagnostic applications.

Dental Application: PA methods have been demonstrated in studies of caries diagnostics, periodontology, dental implants, and blood detection in dental pulp.

Novel Device: Photoacoustic imaging principle - "light in, sound out". Here, a near infrared laser excites a light-absorbing target. The target then undergoes spatially confined heating followed by thermoelastic expansion. This generates wideband acoustic waves that can be detected with ultrasound transducers for image generation. With this device Photoacoustic imaging will be performed by pulsing light through two optical fiber bundles integrated with both sides of a rectangular, linear array transducer. The laser excitation (Q-switched Nd:YAG/ Diode Laser) used 5 ns to 9 ns pulses at 10 Hz to 20 Hz (6 Hz to 8 Hz frame rate) for detection of Dental Caries.

Keywords: Photo-Acoustic (PA) Imaging, Dental Caries

OP 43

Ferrocene Appended Asymmetric Sensitizers with Azine Spacers with Phenolic/Nitro Anchors for Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells**Amita Singh¹, Gabriele Kociok-Köhn², Ratna Chauhan³, Suresh W. Gosavi^{3*} and Abhinav Kumar^{1*}****¹Department of Chemistry, Dr Rammanohar Lohia Awadh University, Ayodhya-224001, UP, India****^{1*}Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Lucknow, Lucknow 226007, UP, India.****²Materials and Chemical Characterisation Facility (MC2), University of Bath, Claverton Down, Bath, BA2 7AY, UK****³Department of Environmental Science, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, 411007, India**

Abstract: Two extensively conjugated asymmetric ferrocene appended compounds with azine spacers, and phenolic and nitro groups as terminal groups with the following formulas $\text{Fc-CH} = \text{N-N} = \text{CH-p-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-OH}$ (Fc-OH) and $\text{Fc-CH} = \text{N-N} = \text{CH-p-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NO}_2$ (Fc-NO₂) (Fc = ferrocene) have been synthesized and characterized using micro-analyses, FTIR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR, UV-Vis and for Fc-NO₂ single crystal X-ray diffraction. The structural studies reveal that Fc-NO₂ possess an extensively conjugated system where C₅H₄ (Cp)-CH = N-N = CH-p-C₆H₄-NO₂ is nearly planar which suggest strong electron communication from the ferrocene moiety to the p-C₆H₄-NO₂ group *via* a -CH = N-N = CH- spacer. Both compounds have been used as sensitizers in titanium oxide based dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) which indicate that amongst both sensitizers the Fc-OH one exhibited a better cell performance with J_{sc} 12.91 mA · cm⁻², V_{oc} 0.710 V, η = 5.88% and incident photon to a current conversion efficiency of 53%. Electron injections in the conduction band of the titanium oxide semiconductor have been authenticated with the help of density of states calculations.

OP 44

Kitchen herbs and Probiotics fortified in milk improved the health and growth performance of neonatal calves**Saroj Rai*, Milan Kumar, TK Dutta, Anupam Chatterjee and Champak Bhakat
ICAR-National Dairy Research Institute, Eastern Regional Station, Kalyani, West Bengal, India**

Abstract: Some common culinary herbs (*Trachyspermum ammi*, *Curcuma longa*, Cinnamon) and probiotics (*Lactobacillus fermentum* NCDC605 and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* NCDC610 @ 10^{10} cfu/ml) were fed to the neonatal crossbred calves upto the weaning age of 3 months. The herbs and probiotics have been found to be effective against some diarrheagenic *E coli* pathotypes reportedly are Enterotoxigenic *E coli* (ETEC) and Shiga toxin producing *E coli* (STEC) etc. ETEC produces heat stable (st) and heat labile (lt) enterotoxins while STEC produces *stx1* and *stx2* gene determinants. The calves fed herb probiotics mix showed increase ($p < 0.05$) in weight gain, dry matter intake ($p < 0.01$), heart girth ($P < 0.05$) and total protein ($p < 0.05$). The duration of sick days in calves were reduced with higher shedding of fecal *Lactobacillus* sp. ($p < 0.05$). The feeding of herb and probiotics during the weaning period proved to be beneficial for the calves.

OP 45

Biogenic synthesis of non-toxic iron oxide NPs via *Syzygium aromaticum* for the removal of methylene blue**Ayushi Jain¹, Shweta Wadhawan^{1*}, S.K. Mehta²**¹Department of Chemistry, GGSDS College, Sector 32, Chandigarh, 160030, India²Department of Chemistry and Centre of Advanced Studies in Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh, 160014, India

Abstract: The discipline of nanotechnology plays an incredible role in environmental remediation. The synthesis of non-toxic, eco-friendly and safe nanomaterials is the current focus of research. The present work portrays a non-toxic and simple method for preparing iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) NPs by employing the bud extract of *Syzygium aromaticum* (clove). The synthesized Fe₂O₃ NPs were characterized by different spectroscopic and microscopic techniques. The toxicological studies were performed using bioassays which revealed its non-toxic behaviour towards gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*), gram negative (*Pseudomonas aureginosa*) bacterial strains and black gram seeds. The calcined counterpart i.e. c-Fe₂O₃ was also prepared via calcination of as synthesized NPs at 700 °C. To inquire the effect of plant extract on the adsorption performance, both Fe₂O₃ NPs and c- Fe₂O₃ NPs were examined for their use in the removal of methylene blue (MB) dye from aqueous solution. The bio-synthesized Fe₂O₃ NPs showed better removal percentage (92 %) as compared to c- Fe₂O₃ (88 %) towards MB.

OP 46

A Realistic Approach for Fluorescence Quenching of Nitrogen containing Heterocycles with Picric Acid**Ruby Ahmed¹ and Farman Ali²****¹Associate Professor, Chemistry at Shibli National College, Azamgarh, UP, India ²Department of Applied Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, UP, India**

Abstract: A series of phenanthroimidazole (PI) derivatives (M1-M3): 2-phenyl-1H-phenanthro [9,10-d]imidazole (M1), 2-anthryl-1H-phenanthro[9,10-d]imidazole (M2), 2-pyrenyl-1H-phenanthro[9,10-d]imidazole (M3) were synthesized and characterized using various spectroscopic techniques. The fluorescence quenching studies or sensing properties of the molecules M1-M3 with picric acid (PA) were studied. The molecules (M1-M3) exhibit strong fluorescence with peak emission wavelength at 386, 486 and 456 nm. This emission gets quenched with the addition of PA. The mechanism of fluorescence quenching involves proton transfer from PA to M in the ground state, followed by complex formation between cation (M⁺) and picrate anion (PA⁻). The proton transfer breaks the conjugation inside the imidazole ring which in turn leads to loss of fluorescence. The proof of proton transfer was evident from single X-ray crystal structure of the co-crystals (M1⁺-PA⁻ and M3⁺-PA⁻) and their Hirshfeld surface analysis. Time-resolved fluorescence measurements reveal that quenching is static. The Abstract: complex formation constant (K_s) and life-time for are all the molecules is measured.

OP 47

Orthodontic Effects based on Analogical Concepts**¹Divya S and Arun S Urala²****^{1,2}Department of Orthodontics, Manipal College of Dental Sciences, Manipal, MAHE- 576104**

Abstract: Understanding the biomechanics of any force system, regardless of the appliance used for mechanotherapy, is essential in orthodontics. Even when simple tooth movements are performed during treatment, force systems must be used with caution.

Insufficient knowledge and inappropriate mechanics can lead to unintended consequences such as improper occlusion in this task. Furthermore, the operator is constantly exposed to advances in material science and application configuration. During our daily clinical practice, we encounter many desired and undesired tooth movements, which we can mention as certain Effects in Orthodontics. These effects are compared to analogies to make them easier to understand. This narrative review paper discusses the Effects of Orthodontics which are named after various analogical concepts. The different effects in Orthodontics which we encounter are

1. Roller coaster effect
2. Wagon wheel effect
3. Trampoline effect
4. Row boat effect
5. Bauschinger effect
6. Wash board effect
7. Ratchetting effect
8. Snubbing effect
9. Cue ball effect
10. Transverse bowing effect
11. Vertical bowing effect
12. Rainbow effect
13. Door wedge effect
14. Draw bridge effect

Keywords: orthodontics, effects, analogy, concept

OP 48

Rice Water Fermentation: Antioxidant and Phytochemical Analysis**M. Ramdas¹ and D. Tambe^{2*}****Department of Microbiology, SIES College of Arts, Science and Commerce (Autonomous) Sion
Mumbai 400022, Maharashtra**

Abstract: Rice is the staple food for most people around the world and due to population growth; the consumption is expected to increase in future. Before consuming rice, it is washed, and water is normally discarded. Reusing this water via fermentation would be beneficial as rice is known to have antioxidants, minerals, and phytochemicals which get leached out in the water and usually wasted. In addition, using specific agricultural-wastes during fermentation, like citrus fruit peels which are also rich in terms of antioxidants improves the phytochemical profile of the final product. The aim of this study is to study phytochemical and microbial profile of the fermented rice water and compare the characteristics of raw rice water and rice water augmented with orange peels post fermentation. According to established literature fermented rice water, which is rich in antioxidants play an important role in enhancing hair quality and thickness. Hence, the Fermented rice water was also tested on small group of people to establish its hair quality enhancing properties. This study shows that the rice water augmented with orange peels give higher antioxidant levels compared to raw rice water. Both samples showed presence of Lactic acid bacteria and yeasts during the fermentation time of 72 hours. Antioxidant stability was analysed for the period of one month and both samples showed maintenance of good levels of antioxidants under refrigeration condition. The fermented rice water effectively enhanced the hair quality for group of people and was liked by many as a natural alternative to the chemical-based conditioners.

Keywords: Antioxidants, Fermented Rice water, Phytochemicals, Fruit peels.

OP 49

Is Corporate Environmentalism rewarded by Market? Empirical Evidence from Indian IT Firms**Dr. Pritika Dua¹ and Dr. Neha Nainwal²**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Business Economics, Aryabhata College, University of Delhi²Assistant Professor, Shaheed Bhagat Singh College of Commerce, University of Delhi

Abstract: Information Technology (IT) sector has been a prominent player in the Indian Growth Story by accelerating economic growth and advancing standards of living. The sector has reaped rich dividends during the pandemic with world transforming to digitalisation at a berserk pace. While the contribution of the IT sector is widely appreciated, the environmental consequences in form of e-waste and high energy consumption cannot go unnoticed. Indian IT firms are proactively adopting environmental management practices (EMPs) with the aim of addressing environmental concerns and growing consumer awareness. We build a unique dataset of 89 listed IT firms over a thirteen period from 2008-09 to 2021-22. Impact of corporate environmentalism on firm performance is studied using three market valuation based measures (Tobin q, Market to Book Value Ratio and Excess Valuation to sales ratio). Empirical results show that environmentally pro-active firms experience improvements in financial performance two years post EMPs implementation.

OP 50

A Stackelberg game approach in a vendor-buyer model with carbon emission and setup cost reduction**Sharmila Saren¹ and Biswajit Sarkar^{2*}**¹**Department of Mathematics, Government General Degree College, Gopiballavpur-II, Beliaberah, Jhargram, West Bengal 721517, India**²**Department of Industrial Engineering, Yonsei University, 50 Yonsei-ro, Sinchon-dong, Seodaemun-gu, Seoul 03722, South Korea**

Abstract: This research constructs an inventory model with Stackelberg game approach to optimize the vendor-buyer system's joint total cost. In this paper, buyer applies an inspection policy for obtaining defective items after receiving the lot from the vendor. After the inspection process, imperfect items are sent back to vendor for reworking purpose. Due to enhancing quantity of deliveries, fixed and variable transportation along with carbon emission are assumed. For this reason, this research becomes more sustainable. For minimizing the vendor's setup cost, a discrete setup cost reduction function is included to maximize the system's total profit. Additionally, players of this model are considered with unequal power and with the technique of Stackelberg game approach, this research obtains global optimum solution. Moreover, an illustrative numerical experiment is derived to understand this model very clearly.

Keywords - Vendor-buyer model, Setup cost reduction, Fixed and variable transportation cost, Carbon emission, Stackelberg game approach.

OP 51

Practices of personal protective measures against SARS-Cov-2 among undergraduate medical students in Mangalore, India**Nitin Joseph****Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine
Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore, Karnataka****Abstract**

Introduction: The use of personal protective measures holds relevance despite mass immunization coverage of COVID-19 vaccination in the population. This is because vaccination only gives protection from severe COVID-19 and does not prevent the risk of infection. Medical students can be vital in training people in infection control practices.

Objectives: To assess the practices of undergraduate medical students regarding personal protective measures against COVID-19.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was done among first to final year students at a private medical college in Mangalore. Data were collected using a Microsoft form.

Results: The mean age of the 302 participants was 21.2 ± 1.6 years. Majority of them were females [179(59.3%)]. Face mask was worn by 295(97.7%) participants. Non-recommended type of face masks like using cloth masks [108 (36.6%)] and handkerchiefs [7(2.4%)] were reported by participants. 35(11.9%) of them wore the face mask incorrectly. Periodicity of replacement of disposable type mask was not done every day by 181(61.4%) participants. 142(48.1%) of them did not dispose of masks whenever it became moist on every occasion. Only 79(26.8%) always practiced proper disposal of face masks. Hand sanitizer to disinfect hands was always used by 102(33.8%) participants. Only 42(13.9%) participants practiced correct practice of hygienic hand wash always. Only 58(19.2%) participants had a good level of practice. Practice level was significantly poorer among males and first-year students.

Conclusion: Several gaps in preventive practices against COVID-19 were identified, particularly among males and first-year students. These issues need to be addressed among medical students in future training programs.

Keywords: Undergraduate medical students, Personal protective measures, Practices, COVID-19

OP 52

On E-Statistical Summability of Bounded Sequence**Sabiha Tabassum and Ruqaiyya Fatma****Department of Applied Mathematics****Zakir Husain College of Engineering and Technology****Aligarh Muslim University Aligarh-202002, India**

Abstract: A summability method is said to be regular if it preserves the limit, i.e., it sums all convergent series to its Cauchy's sum. In this paper we have introduced the sequence space $X(E)$ defined by Euler matrix for the spaces $X = l_\infty, c, c_0$ and $l_p, (1 \leq p < \infty)$. Some fundamental properties and relation related to these spaces are examined. A new regular statistical summability method (Euler statistical summability) is given. The graph for Euler and Euler statistical summability are given by using MATLAB (2018a).

MSC: 40B05, 40CXX, 54A20

Keywords: Sequence spaces, Banach spaces, Statistical convergence, Regular Matrix, Summability

OP 53**Entrepreneur: Build your own dreams****Dr. Archana Bhaskar****Assistant Professor, Rajiv Gandhi Govt. College Arts and Commerce College
Lormi, District - Mungeli 495115**

Abstract: In developing countries due to increased population, there is economic crisis and unemployment is continuously rising. Therefore, it has become a necessary to implement an important events that will help public with self-employment and, ultimately, in achieving a venerable life. An individual who creates a new business, bearing most of the risks, discouragement, disillusionment, hard labor, high stress, no social life until the enterprise stabilizes and enjoying most of the rewards with profits are known as entrepreneur and the process of setting up a business is known as entrepreneurship. The entrepreneurs are an innovator, having a source of new ideas, goods, services, and trust for fame, visionary and opportunistic.

Everyone in the world has a dream. It is a better to run after your own dreams instead of working for another people dreams. Today, with the advancement of new technology and increased access to capital for starting new business, entrepreneurship has become the career path of choice for youths. Entrepreneurship is one of the greatest weapons to counteract many issues that the youth is facing. Entrepreneurship is not only a money-driven venture but also a passion-driven, that facilitates positive change in the society and helps in building an individual own dreams. It also helps in the economic development of the nation. The government has taken many initiatives to empower the youth with their energize to explore new territories and take up new challenges and risks to become entrepreneur and generate more jobs for others.

OP 54

Host preference and effect of pulse beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.) on quality of different pulses**Rupesh Sharma¹ and Renu Devi²**¹OPJS University, Churu, Rajasthan²CCSHAU Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Sirsa, Haryana

Abstract: Pulse beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus* F. (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) is a serious pest of pulses in fields and also stored grain products. The damage due to this pest affects quantitative as well as qualitative value of the seed grains. A laboratory experiment was conducted on the host preference and qualitative losses of pulse beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.) on six different pulses viz., Black gram, Green gram, Pigeonpea, Chickpea (*Desi*), Cowpea and Pea. The comparison of egg laying under no choice and multiple-choice condition revealed that egg laying was less on the seeds of all the pulses under multiple-choice condition. However, under no choice condition maximum eggs were laid on cowpea (89.3), whereas in multiple-choice condition the egg laying was maximum on pigeonpea (66.3). Similarly low seed damage was recorded in all the pulses under multiple-choice condition except in case of pigeonpea (28.3%). Maximum standard germination, seed viability and seedling vigour index was found in black gram (55.1%, 56.0% and 1410.1) and minimum in cowpea (33.6%, 22.0% and 679.0), respectively. Shoot, root and seedling lengths of all the pulses were affected adversely due to the incidence of pulse beetle. The shoot length was 10.2 cm (black gram) to 18.1 cm (pigeonpea). The root length was 7.2 cm (chickpea) to 10.8 cm (cowpea) and seedling length varied from 21.1 cm (chickpea) to 27.1 cm (black gram). So, the results showed significant differences among the host preferences in terms of oviposition rate of different pulses. ANOVA test was used to analyze the results.

Key words: *Callosobruchus maculatus*, host preference, pulses

OP 55

Animated Monte Carlo Simulations of Pi on a Platonic Solid - The Icosahedron**Vaibhav Thapliyal¹, Ayush Mishra¹, Manisha Verma^{1†} and Sanjeeta Rani^{1*}****¹Department of Physics, Acharya Narendra Dev College,
University of Delhi, New Delhi 110019, India**

Abstract: Icosahedron, a polyhedron with 20 equilateral triangle faces, 12 vertices, and 30 edges, one of the five Platonic solids in mathematics, is used in the construction of many other geometric shapes and is a key element in the study of crystallography. It has significant importance and applications in various fields, ranging from mathematics to art and biology, making it a fascinating and versatile shape to study. High symmetry of icosahedron ensures that the distribution of points inside it is uniform, making it easy to generate random points for use in computer graphics and cryptography using Monte Carlo simulations. Even though the value of Pi is known for a long time, estimating Pi using Monte Carlo simulations on different geometries can not only be a fun and challenging mathematical exercise but also, can be important for benchmarking numerical methods, generating high-quality random points, simulating physical phenomena, and exploring new geometries. It can help improve our understanding and appreciation of the beauty and complexity of mathematics. This motivated us to successfully design an animated simulator involving icosahedron inscribed inside a sphere using HTML (HyperText Markup Language), CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) and JS (JavaScript) to visualize and simulate the data. Our work involves a simulation-based computational method to implement Monte Carlo (MC) simulations in icosahedron, a non-Euclidean 3D geometry vis-a-vis circle, a Euclidean 2D geometry. To visualize the MC simulations and generate data, codes in python programming language were developed efficiently. The data were generated by varying the number of simulations in range 100 - 1000000(10⁶) for both the geometries. It has been reported that with an increase in the number of simulations, the value of pi successfully attains better stabilization and conforms more to the normal distribution for icosahedron also in the same way as for circle. A stabilization in variance in pi of the order of 10⁻⁴ was obtained for icosahedron as well against the 2D reference geometry.

Keywords: Monte Carlo Simulation, Estimation of pi, Icosahedron, Computational Method

[†] Presenting Author

OP 56

Aeromycoflora Incidence over Rice Field**Dr. Vikas M. Mohture****Department of Botany, R.M.G. Arts and Science College Nagbhid, Dist. Chandrapur (M.S)**

Abstract: The present systematic investigation was carried out over rice field for one year from June 2018 to May 2019 during both Kharip and Rabi season using Rotorod Air Sampler. The meteorological factors like humidity, rainfall and temperature were found to have influence on the occurrence of fungal spores. In Nagbhid region rice is grown mostly as kharip crop but due to the irrigation in some part it is grown as a rabi crop also. Two peaks of fungal spores were found the highest concentration was occurred in the month of October during kharip crop and in the month of February in rabi crop. Variation in concentration of fungal spores may be due to change in temperature, rainfall, relative humidity. A total of 48 different fungal spore types were identified among them *Alternaria* (18.25%) showed the highest percentage of occurrence followed by *Cladosporium* (11.40%) *Curvularia* (10.27%), *Helminthosporium/ Dresclera type* (8.02%), Smut spores (4.28%). More concentration of fungal spores was observed during kharip crop. Among the recorded taxa, members of Deuteromycotina were predominant in their occurrence followed by the members of Basidiomycotina and Ascomycotina. An attempt was made to forecast atmospheric fungal concentration which will be useful for controlling the diseases.

Keywords: Rotorod Air Sampler, Fungal spores, meteorological factors, kharip/rabi crop.

OP 57

Nutritional Study of Adult Tribal Population of India with Special Emphasis on Santal Population of Birbhum District, West Bengal, India**Ashish Mukhopadhyay****Department of Anthropology, Acharya Prafulla Chandra College
New Barrackpore, West Bengal, India**

Abstract: Indian tribal population comprises 8.2% of the total population of the country. They cover approximately 15% of the country's area. At present, there exist 697 tribal groups recognized by the central government. Around 75 of them are recognized as Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTG). The nutritional profile of adult tribal population of India is very serious. Women and old age people among them are more vulnerable than their male counterpart. Till date out of the total tribal communities residing in India, the anthropometric data is lacking. This is our responsibility as an anthropologist to study anthropometrically the different ethnic groups and keep anthropometric data for not only comparison with other tribal groups but also to understand their contemporary health and nutritional status as compared to the other non-tribal groups.

A cross-sectional study was undertaken to determine anthropometrically determined health profile and nutritional status of adult Santals, a tribal population of Birbhum District, West Bengal, India. Santals (aged > 18 years) of Bolpur Sriniketan Block in Birbhum District were studied. Anthropometric measurements including height, weight, circumferences and skinfolds as well as BMI were measured using standard protocol. Overall, the extent of undernutrition (BMI < 18.5) was found to be very high (55.3%). The prevalence of undernutrition was higher in females (58.5%) compared to males (52.5%) although this difference was not significant. Using the World Health Organization criterion (WHO, 1995) the prevalence of undernutrition (based on BMI) is very high and the situation is critical. In conclusion, this study provided evidence that the prevalence of adult undernutrition was very high among Santals, a tribal population of Birbhum District, West Bengal. Similar prevalence of undernutrition is also reported by the researchers among the Santals of other states as well as other tribal groups of India. Thus, immediate appropriate nutritional intervention programs are needed for implementation among the Indian tribal people. Moreover, further research is needed not only among this ethnic group

but also other tribal populations of India for the preparation of large scale ethnic specific data base and to understand the causes and consequences of adult undernutrition.

OP 58

Medicinally Important Leeches in Churani Region Melghat**Shital S. Deshmukh****Department of Zoology Science College Pauni**

Abstract: Leeches have traditionally been used for bloodletting. The use of medicinal leeches is preferred because of their ability to bite deeply and cause prolonged bleeding, even after detachment. Different species of leeches secrete varying compounds with differing hematological actions. In 2004 the FDA approved the use of medicinal leeches in reconstructive and plastic surgery. The medicinal leech is an excellent example of the use of invertebrates in the treatment of human disease. Leeches secrete more than 20 identified bioactive substances such as antistasin, eglins, guamerin, hirudin, saratin, bdellins. They have analgesic, anti-inflammatory, platelet inhibitory, anticoagulant and thrombin regulatory functions. Hirudotherapy technique is cheap, effective, easy to apply. Leeches can be found almost anywhere in Churani region where there are suitable damp areas. Mostly they are sanguivorous, that is they feed as blood sucking parasites on preferred hosts. These leeches can ingest several times their own weight in blood at one meal. After feeding the leech retires to a dark spot to digest its meal. Digestion is slow and this enables the leech to survive during very long fasting periods.

Keywords: Medicinal leeches, Hirudotherapy, bioactive compound.

OP 59

Impact of capping agent on structural and optical properties of ZnS nanoparticles**Samiran Mandal^{1*}, Sk Irsad Ali², Subhamay Pramanik³ and Atis Chandra Mandal²**¹Government General Degree College at Pedong, Pedong, Kalimpong-734311, West Bengal, India²Department of Physics, University of Burdwan, Golapbag, Burdwan 713104, West Bengal, India³School of Nanoscience and Technology, IIT Kharagpur-721302, West Bengal, India

Abstract: Nanocrystalline samples of pristine capped and uncapped zinc sulphide were synthesized via the sol-gel technique. The nanocrystallinity of the samples were confirmed by the X-ray diffraction technique, where size of the particle size decreases with the increasing of mol. concentration ($x = 0.00, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04$ Mol) of capping agent sodium dodecyle sulphate. The obtained crystallite sizes were found to be in the range 4.6 nm to 2.7 nm respectively. The optical band gaps of the samples were estimated by using ultra-violet visible spectroscopic techniques and the band gap values were in the range 3.8 eV to 4.4 eV. All the samples showed quantum confinement behavior compared to bulk sample. Fluorescence (FL) spectra showed three emission peaks at the emission wavelengths around 434 nm, 520 nm, 545 nm, 628 nm, and 694 nm. The FL intensities were proportional to the concentration of capping agent.

OP 60

Nanotechnology: Current and future application

Mahendra Kumar Patre

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Abstract: In the current Era the application of Nanotechnology have increase rapidly over the last few decades and continue to have great potential to provide substantial benefits to society. Nanotechnology is helping to considerably improve, even revolutionize, many technology and sectors: information technology, energy, environmental science, medicine, homeland security, food safety, and transportation, among many others. Today's nanotechnology harnesses current progress in chemistry, physics, materials science, and biotechnology to create novel materials that have unique properties because their structures are determined on the nanometer scale. This presentation give a broad overview of the current and future applications of nanotechnology.

OP 61

Detached Society: A Sociological Perspective**Dr. Anil Bhatt****Assistant Professor, Department of Sociology
SDM Govt PG College Doiwala, Uttarakhand**

Abstract: The literal meaning of the word *detach* is separation or aloofness. Sociologically, this word assumes its connotations in a more varied spectrum of society. The human emotions as empathy, sympathy, self-less love, affection, social relationships seem to be at stake. In other words it is journey from 'we' feeling of a community to 'I' feeling of formal societies. The question arises are we getting detached from the social circle of true relationships and drifting more towards a virtual space that holds a value of nothingness. To be more exact, we all are experiencing a detached, aloof and colder society around us. New applications like Face book, Whatsapp, Instagram, Skype, etc have made it rather difficult to keep mobile phones away. As a result we overlook people in close relationships like those in a home, marriage, class rooms and social functions but leave no opportunity to give in to the temptation of overhearing something or gather news about somebody, or gossip. Ironically little do we realize that no one on social media is interested in the real you, and the relationship with primary group is as cold as fridge water. It is just that we feel that we are associated with so many people, which can be termed as un-attached, distant relationship. Is technology driven equipments or machines being used by us or are we getting consumed by it at the cost of social relationships which were earlier considered to be the anchors in times of distress? Priorities have changed with the advent of technology in our daily life. It is more important to respond on phone than to reply someone in person. Eventually this silent drift is the precarious distress approaching silently with challenging outcomes for the future.

People are getting terribly self-absorbed, emotionally unavailable, inaccessible, unresponsive, and indifferent. It is being witnessed that society is lacking empathy, tolerance and compassion. Parents are busier, engrossed in their own world. Children in today's times are inheriting the world of technology and artificial intelligence .This would result in their love towards parents, siblings, friends in early age getting shattered and replaced by ones of fear, despair, and irrelevance. It cannot be denied that the foundations of personal/ social relationship are linked to human emotions. As a matter of fact, we are on our path of making emotionless world or

experiencing over emotional virtual reality leading to losing our sense of balance in 'Purushartha' (*Dharma, Artha, Kama, Moksha*). Furthermore, social engagement holds significance in contributing towards successful ageing. Additionally, more is the involvement with societal activities, better are the positive outcomes for people in older age. But apathy towards older people in terms of neglection by new generation is an indispensable sad story. In sociological terms the word detachment is synonymous to social alienation which is a feeling of disconnection from the group with a low degree of integration and a higher degree of isolation. The basic social fabric has become frayed, and our sense of place and community diluted. A society devoid of emotions and human values, overtly influenced by technology shall convert humans leading a mechanized life like robots. The merits of Technological advancement in any society is a boon but it's impact on humanity in general social relationships in particular is in a way leading us towards social alienation in its truest sense.

OP 62

Psychology of Gender Identity**Dr. Vandana Gaur****Associate Professor, Department of Psychology
SDM Govt PG College, Doiwala, Dehradun**

Abstract: Gender identity is the psychological view of a person as either male, female, neither, both, or somewhere in between. Although a person's gender identity is usually consistent with their biological sex, it does not have to be. The subjective experience of one's own gender and how it manifests, or one's gender identity, is a hotly debated issue. It is one's personal perception of and subjective experience of being a man, a woman, or another gender. It is the degree to which one identifies with a specific gender. It frequently takes shape early on and consists mainly of accepting (or rejecting) one's membership in a gender category.. In the majority of societies, males and females are given different gender traits. However, some people do not identify with all (or even some) of the aspects of gender that are attributed to their biological sex in all cultures. Cisgender people are those who continue to identify as the gender that corresponds to the sex given to them at birth (for instance, if they are assigned female at birth, they will continue to identify as a girl, then a woman, etc.). People who identify as a gender other than their biological sex are referred to as transgender in many Western societies. For instance, if a person is assigned the gender female at birth but feels internally that they are a boy or a gender other than a girl. If they have access to resources and medical treatment, some transgender people elect to undergo medical procedures like surgery and hormone therapy to change their bodies in order to better match their gender identity. The four main agents of gender socialization are family, schooling, peer groups, and the media. By establishing and upholding normative expectations for gender-specific conduct, each agent reinforces gender roles. Secondary agents like faith and the workplace can also expose people. People who are exposed to these agents repeatedly over time get the impression that they are acting in accordance with their gender naturally rather than conforming to a socially created role. Thus we must understand that gender roles and traits for men and women are dynamic.

Keywords: Cisgender, biological sex, socialization, culture

OP 63

Production of alginate from *Azotobacter* sp. and its application**A. F. Meeran¹ and H. Azmi^{2*}****Department of Microbiology, SIES College of Arts, Science and Commerce (Autonomous)
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Abstract: Alginate is a naturally occurring polysaccharide currently produced from marine brown algae. Alginate is also produced by the soil bacterium *Azotobacter* sp. Alginate is a linear polymer of mannuronic acid and guluronic acid. Alginate, due to its colloidal behavior is of great use in food, biomedical, and pharmaceutical industries. An algal source may give varied alginate composition with different batches; however, a bacterial source may give unlimited and better quality alginate. Three potential alginate producing isolates were obtained from rice rhizosphere soil, of which one was selected based on maximum alginate production using EDTA and isopropanol. Obtained alginate was confirmed using Carbazole assay. Among tested mediums, Ashby's mannitol broth gave maximum alginate production (4.2 mg/mL). Maximum alginate was obtained after 5 days of incubation at shaker condition (10.7 mg/mL). The optimum temperature and pH for production were found to be 29°C (RT) and pH 7 respectively. The addition of urea as a nitrogen source increased alginate production to 26.7 mg/mL. Sucrose, when used as a carbon source, gave 4.7 mg/mL and 15% of sucrose gave 24.7 mg/mL of alginate. 5% of inoculum gave maximum alginate production. An alternative carbon source will be used for reducing the production cost. The obtained alginate gave 62% bioflocculant activity with kaolin clay. Further, alginate can be used for enzyme immobilization, metal absorption, etc.

Keywords: Alginate, Mannuronic acid, *Azotobacter*, Carbazole, Immobilization

OP 64**Learning and Classification with Small Size Datasets: Challenges and Solutions****Dr. Vandna Bhalla^{1*}****Department of Electronics, Sri Aurobindo College, Malviya Nagar
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Abstract: Small data is the opposite of big data, data available in small quantity. Recent years have seen a growth in learnings related to small datasets. The size of a data set used for training any learning model plays a critical role to prevent overfitting. If the sample set has little data and is undersized with a multitude of features, the model may end up being biased as patterns not existing are very likely to be visualized by outliers. The data is not big enough to manifest reality. Consequently, models trained do not converge that sharply. Our personal collection repositories do not have huge amount of data for training and learning these collections are getting more and huger with numerous classes and are not limited to text only. The common notion is that building a classifier based on learnings from a small sized training dataset is challenging. Many techniques are in use to combat this challenge like using models with simpler algorithms, removing outliers, more prudent selection of features, combining varied models, transfer learning and augmenting datasets to name a few. One serious repercussion of existing data augmentation techniques is that there is a strong possibility of the basic structure of patterns getting transformed. Actually, even a small and limited number of synthetic samples can boost a dataset favourably provided the data augmentation approach is skilful. In this work we highlight the challenges of small datasets and present an approach to efficiently augment it.

Keywords: Dataset, augmentation, training, learning, classification, overfitting, outliers.

OP 65

Sensitivity nature of *Phytophthora capsici* isolates causing foot rot of black pepper in Karnataka to oomycetes specific fungicides**K. V. Shivakumar^{1,2,*}, Y. M. Somasekhara¹, N., Nagaraju¹, R. L. Ravikumar³, K. T. Rangaswamy¹**¹Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, Karnataka 560065, India²ICAR- Directorate of Floricultural Research, Pune, Maharashtra 411036, India³Department of Plant Biotechnology, College of Agriculture, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, Karnataka 560065, India

Abstract: Black pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.), an economically important spice crop widely used in all major cuisines around the world. Globally, India is the fourth largest producer of black pepper next to Vietnam, Brazil and Indonesia, contributing more than 8% of the world's black pepper production, is susceptible to various pathogens, in particular to *Phytophthora capsici* which causes foot rot, considered as the most devastating disease of black pepper, has been reported to cause an annual crop loss of 5-10 per cent. This disease is mainly managed by the use of fungicides as host resistance to *Phytophthora capsici* is not available. Diseased samples were collected from major growing districts of Karnataka, India during 2017. A total of six isolates were recovered representing each district sampled and identified as *P. capsici* by amplifying the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region of the conserved ribosomal DNA using primers ITS1 and ITS4 which yielded 770 bp and nucleotide similarity search with already available database in GenBank. All six field isolates of *P. capsici* studied for its sensitivity nature for oomycetes specific fungicides viz., metalaxyl, dimethomorph, fosetyl-Al and potassium phosphonate. The results of present study categorized isolates in to two main groups. Group I consisted of two isolates viz., PC1 and PC2 from Kodagu district of Karnataka that are resistant to three fungicides, namely fosetyl-al, dimethomorph, and potassium phosphate, but sensitive to metalaxyl and group II consisted of four isolates viz., PC3, PC4, PC5 and PC6 which are intermediate to metalaxyl, resistance to fosetyl-Al and potassium phosphonate, but sensitive to fungicide dimethomorph. Further, cluster analysis of all isolates showed maximum correlation between cluster pattern and grouping of isolates based on its fungicidal sensitive nature. These results are now pose new challenges for management of this important disease.

OP 66

**Lanthanide Chelates of Isomeric 3- Bromolawsone and 3-Bromojujlone
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Abstract: C-3 Bromolawsone (2 hydroxy 3 bromo 1,4 naphthoquinone) and C-3 Bromojujlone (5 hydroxy 3bromo 1,4 naphthoquinone) are two important ligands belonging to the Juglone series derived from hydroxy 1, 4 naphthoquinone . Both these isomeric ligands possess strong chelating ability , appreciable analytical utility and powerful antimicrobial activity .Our research group has carried out extensive and intensive advanced research work on the metal chelates of these ligands. This communication is a part of this work in which isomeric lanthanide chelates of La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III) with C-3 bromolawsone and C-3 bromojujlone are reported with special reference to their synthesis characterization and a comparative study based on physical as well chemical characterization and structural investigations based on infrared and electronic spectroscopy and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

The synthesis of these two ligands and their six lanthanide chelates was done using the literature methods which are well established in our laboratory. Their characterization was done through elemental analysis, melting points / TGA and TIC.

All the lanthanide 3 -bromolawsونات are brownish red in color while their corresponding 3-bromojujlونات are intense red violet in color. The molecular composition of all the chelates corresponds to $ML_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ with an exception of Sm(III)- 3- bromojujlonate which is anhydrous. The magnetic moments of all these chelates are close to those of the corresponding tripositive lanthanide ions with an exception of Sm(III) chelates which are diamagnetic . Their solid state infrared spectra recorded in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} are analyzed with special reference to C –O stretching , chelated and unchelated C=O stretching C-Br stretching and M-O stretching frequencies. A Comparison of these IR spectra of two isomeric series shows that it is easy to distinguish the two isomeric series in terms of these stretching frequencies which are quite distinct. Electronic spectra of the two series in chloroform in the range 200-800 nm involving

BET (benzenoid electronic transitions), QET (Quinonide electronic transitions) and $n-\pi^*$ transitions are also quite distinct for each series providing another important tool for their easy identifications and to compare the ring isomerism within two series.

Keywords: 3Bromo Lawsonates and Juglonates, Lanthanides

OP 67**Development of Synbiotic Dark Chocolate Enriched with Pineapple Peel as Prebiotic and isolated Probiotic****Iram Shaikh, Shweta Chaudhary and Dr. Pramod D. Ghogare******Department of Microbiology, SIES College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Sion, Mumbai 400 022, Maharashtra, India**

Abstract: There is increase in demand for food products with health benefits beyond basic nutrition. This trends direct research towards the development of synbiotic functional foods maintaining a healthy gut flora and general wellbeing. Synbiotic foods containing probiotics and prebiotics have well-known health benefits, and several clinical trials have demonstrated these effects. Chocolate is a food product universally popular among all age groups and the presence of cocoa provides protective passage for probiotic which makes chocolate an ideal carrier. The aim of the current study was to prepare synbiotic dark chocolate amended with pineapple peel (PP) as prebiotic and isolated probiotic bacteria. The isolated LAB culture showed the property of probiotic culture viz. higher tolerance to bile salt and hydrophobicity. The isolate showed growth in the presence of different concentration pineapple peel (PP) up to 10%. The selected isolate tolerated pH 2.0 better in presence of PP. Pineapple peel have dietary fibre content which makes its suitable for prebiotic source. The stability of the synbiotic chocolate was studied for 7 days in which probiotic chocolate (without prebiotic) was used as a control. Viability of culture in synbiotic as well as probiotic chocolate found to be 6 log cfu/g and it was stable for 7 days. The future aspect is to study the stability of synbiotic chocolate for 60 days, cytotoxicity study of chocolate on human cell line and in vitro digestibility of chocolate. Development of synbiotic chocolate using natural prebiotic and probiotics can facilitate a paradigm shift from illness to wellness by improving gut microbiota.

OP 68

Lichen Planus: A disease with abstruse pathology
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Abstract: Lichen (Greek) means “treemass” which is a type of plant growing on trees formed by mutual combination of algae and fungus. Planus (Latin) means “smooth level or even”. Erasmus Wilson (1869), an English physician described a dermatological condition that featured “an eruption of pimples remarkable of their colour”. Lichen Planus is a distinct mucocutaneous inflammatory condition involving skin and primarily the oral mucous membrane. It constitutes about 9% of all the white lesions of the oral cavity. Oral lesions of Lichen Planus frequently accompany skin and genital mucosal lesions. These lesions present diagnostic problems since their clinical and histological features overlap with each other. Lichen planus antigen is expressed in association with MHC class I molecules on keratinocytes at the OLP lesion site. Antigen specific CD8 cytotoxic T-lymphocytes are activated possibly with the help from CD4 T-cells and trigger keratinocyte apoptosis via secreted TNF- α . TNF- α is secreted and released from cytotoxic T-lymphocytes by MMPs. Basement membrane disruption facilitates the passage of lymphocytes into the OLP epithelium. It denies keratinocyte of cell survival signal. All these events result in keratinocyte apoptosis.

OP 69

Heavy cluster emission in the decay of Z=112-116 superheavy nuclei**Kirandeep Sandhu¹, Rajni² and Gurjit Kaur³**¹P.G Department of Physics, G.S.S.D.G.S Khalsa College Patiala²Sardar Vallabhbhai National Institute of Technology Surat, Gujarat³Department of Physics, Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, 160036, Chandigarh

Abstract: Alpha decay and the spontaneous fission are prominent decay modes of the superheavy mass region. Apart from these, the wide analysis is also being made on the heavy particle emission $Z_c > 28$ from the parent nucleus with $Z > 110$ [1-2]. It is relevant to mention that in heavy particle radioactivity, emission of cluster is always accompanied by doubly magic Pb as daughter or its neighboring isotope. Broadly speaking, the heavy cluster is emitted corresponding to the daughter nucleus ^{208}Pb [1-2]. Various methodologies were developed (such as analytical super asymmetric unified fission model, the unified description formula, the universal decay law etc.) to understand this peculiar decay mode, among which the Preformed cluster model [3-4], based on the collective clusterization technique is applied here to observe the various clusters emitted from Z=112, 114 and 116 nuclei. The quantum mechanical fragmentation theory (QMFT) [5-6] is used to investigate the cluster emission. The half-lives of heavy clusters are estimated by using the only parameter of the model called the neck-length parameter used for the penetration of the cluster from the barrier. In addition to this, the barrier characteristics are also discussed. The preformation and the penetration probabilities are calculated for the cluster emission in the decay of Z=112,114 and 116 nuclei. It is important to mention that the methodology is already applied for the odd mass systems such as Z=113,115 and 117 [7]. Owing to this, this work mainly concentrates on the even- mass nuclei whose decay is quite different from the odd mass nuclear systems.

Keywords: Cluster radioactivity, Half-lives, Superheavy nuclei.

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OP 70

One pot Three Component Mannich Reaction for the Synthesis of 2-substituted Piperidine and Pyrrolidine Natural Products

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Abstract: Proline catalysed one pot three component Mannich reactions got more attention during the past decades due to wide applications in the synthesis of various natural products and bioactive molecules. Synthesis of 2-alkylated pyrrolidine and piperidine is very challenging and most of the synthesis is lengthy and costly. Many bioactive molecules having 2-alkylated pyrrolidine and piperidine as a key structural unit. Here we present a detailed study of proline catalysed one pot three component Mannich reaction followed by sequential cyclisation directed towards the synthesis of 2 substituted pyrrolidine and piperidine class of alkaloids. The methodology is extended toward the synthesis (\pm) Pelletrine, (\pm) Coniine, (\pm) Allosedridine and (\pm) Sedridine.

Keywords: Mannich Reaction, Organocatalysis, Proline, Alkaloids, Natural Products.

Reference:

1. Proline catalyzed, one-pot three component Mannich reaction and sequential cyclization toward the synthesis of 2-substituted piperidine and pyrrolidine alkaloids. **Shibin Chacko**, Ramesh Ramapanicker. *Tetrahedron Letters*, 2015, 15, 2023-2026.

OP 71

Total Synthesis of 4-Hydroxy ornithine Using Proline Catalysed α -hydroxylation Reaction

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Abstract: Hydroxy diamino acids like 5-hydroxylysine, 4-hydroxyornithine and 3-hydroxy-2,4-diamino acids are found in collagen, in antibiotics, like biphenomycin and clavalanine, and as part of the skeleton of marine alkaloid manzacidin B. This chapter deals with the synthesis of hydroxy diamino acids using proline catalyzed asymmetric α -hydroxylation of aldehydes followed reductive amination of the aldehyde functionality as the key reaction. The reaction proceeds with excellent diastereoselectivity and yield. One of the hydroxy diamino acid, (2S,5S)-5-hydroxylysine was converted into the amino caprolactam ring of bengamide A. Bengamide A is known to be highly cytotoxic with antiproliferative property in nanomolar range.

Figure 1: Hydroxy diamino acids

Keywords: Hydroxy diamino acids, Aminoxylation, Proline, Ornithine, Bengamide

OP 72

The study aimed at addressing the professional role transition of new graduate nurses during their initial years of practice.

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Abstract

Methodology: Phenomenological research approach was used among the 10 staff nurses who were working as staff nurses in a tertiary care hospital in Bangalore. An interview technique was used to collect the data in two phases; Focused group interview and Individual interview.

Results: The collected data was categorized into three stages based on Judy Boychuk Duchscher's transition theory. During the initial 3-4 months (Doing stage) the nurses were excited but rapidly perceived that they were not prepared enough to manage the work load and responsibility of their role as staff nurse. The themes emerged were "Being scared and stressed, Reality is different and Need to learn". Subjects felt scared and stressed and realized that the reality is different and need to learn. During the next 9-12 months (Being Stage) their competency, skill and confidence improved. "Gaining confidence and Trustworthy" were the themes emerged during this phase. From 12 months and above (Knowing phase) the subjects experienced less stress, gained confidence and improved their individual capacity to cope and the themes unfolded were "Yes, I know, and To be empowered".

Conclusion: The study revealed the complexity in the transition of student to registered nurse. In the current scenario with an acute shortage of staff nurses, it is vital to address this issue and to plan for necessary reforms to strengthen the profession.

Keywords: Initial years of practice, new graduate nurses, Professional role transition, and Qualitative study

OP 73

A Review on In-Silico Approaches for Drug Designing and Drug Discovery**Prashasti Sinha^{1*}, Dr. Anil Kumar Yadav¹ and Manas Misra²**¹Department of Physics, School for Physical & Decision Sciences, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow-226025 Uttar Pradesh²Department of Physics, IIT Bombay, Mumbai-400076 Maharashtra

Abstract: The cycle of designing and discovery of drugs is exceptionally difficult and there is a need of interdisciplinary knowledge for synthesizing some effective and cheaper drugs. The major aim is to acknowledge a drug that can fit to a particular active site of a protein target both mathematically and experimentally. The data for conventional methods have never been satisfactory as to generate drugs with the same method are expensive and time taking. The issues with this strategy are that it is significantly expensive and time taking. Now the structure-based drug designing along with computational simulation produced an increased number of drug revelation in a proficient way. Improvised techniques involving both hardware and software produce more stable and biologically preferred compounds. These instruments can take advantage of cheminformatics to significantly reduce the time consumption during synthesis and designing of drugs, and in this way make drug discovery savvier. A detailed outline is given about the drug discovery procedure including the conventional and modern methodologies followed for drug designing. The review covers a wide range of in-silico approaches for drug designing including molecular optimization, molecular docking, QM/MM technique, molecular dynamics, force fields like AMBER, CHARMM, GROMOS, OPLS, molecular visualization and ADMET tools along with their descriptions and software.

Keywords: Drug Designing, Computer-Aided Drug Designing, Molecular Docking, QM/MM Technique, Molecular Dynamics

OP 74

Quality of life among Hemophiliacs of Kadapa district based on their Severity**Uday Raj Devaraju Juttuka¹ and Dr. Ajitha Katta²**¹PhD Scholar, Department of Public Health, University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad – 500046²Associate Professor, Department of Public Health, University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad – 500046

Abstract: Assessing quality of life provides information about patient's well-being and the effect of a disease. Hemophilia is an inherited, X-linked bleeding disorder, demonstrating absence or reduced clotting factors in the blood. Males are predominantly the sufferers, while females are usually the carriers. It is a rare blood disorder affecting 1 in 5000 (Factor VIII deficient – Hemophilia A) or 1 in 10,000 (Factor IX deficient – Hemophilia B). Persons with Hemophilia (PwH) suffer from bleeding episodes, particularly in joints and muscles, causing reduced joint mobility and muscle strength. Repeated bleeds lead to chronic hemarthrotic joints causing crippling deformities. In developing countries, like India, with limited treatment resources for Hemophilia, these deformities affect PwH quality of life and functional ability and there is a lack of Indian literature regarding the same. This study aimed to investigate the quality of life of hemophiliacs and their functional ability based on severity. This observational study, conducted in Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh, assessed quality of life of PwH using Haemophilia Adult Quality of Life (Haem-A-QoL) questionnaire and their functional ability using Functional Independence Score for Hemophilia (FISH). A total of 32; 16 (50%) severe and 16 (50%) moderate PwH, who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were recruited. Their mean age was 25.3±3.4 vs 27.6±5.8 (severe vs moderate) years respectively. Among them 24 (75%) had deformities and 27 (84.3%) suffered with target joints. The Haem-A-QoL score showed significant difference by severity; $p = 0.004$, but the mean FISH score did not reveal a significant difference; $p = 0.547$. This study concludes that there is a difference in quality of life between severe and moderate PwH, but no difference was seen in their functional ability.

Keywords: Hemophilia, Severity, Quality of Life, Functional ability

OP 75

Study of some elastic properties of nano TiO₂ from EOSs**Shivam Srivastava¹, Prachi Singh¹, Anjani K. Pandey² and Chandra K. Dixit¹****¹Department of Physics, Dr. ShakuntalaMisra National Rehabilitation University
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh****²Institute of Engineering and Technology,
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Abstract: In the present study, we have made prediction about elastic properties of nano TiO₂ using equation of states. The theoretical predictions have been made using Shanker EOS, Tait EOS, Brennan-Stacey EOS. All the calculations have been done for three ranges of pressures viz. high pressure range, moderate pressure range and at low pressure range. Pressure up to 100 GPa will be recognized as low pressure range, pressure from 100 GPa to 200 GPa will be identified as moderate range of pressure and beyond 200 GPa will be high pressure range. The theoretical calculations was showing that Tait EOS and Brennan-Stacey EOS gives very similar result at low pressure range and as well as at high pressure range but Shanker EOS deviates from moderate range of pressure. Available experimental data will validate our work.

Keywords: EOSs, lattice parameter, Debye frequency, Debye temperature

OP 76

Therapeutic potential of Ayurveda management in Atrial fibrillation with special reference to paroxysmal and Lone AF**Dr Mini V G¹ and Dr Giri P V² (MD (AY), PhD****¹PhD scholar, Department of Kayachikitsa, Vaidyaratnam Ayurveda College, Ollur, Trissur, Kerala, 680306****²Professor and HOD, Department of Kayachikitsa, Vaidyaratnam Ayurveda College, Ollur, Trissur, Kerala, 680306**

Abstract: Atrial fibrillation (AF) is an increasingly prevalent cardiovascular pandemic encountered in clinical practice. Disorders in electrical wavefront propagation mainly caused by structural and molecular abnormalities which can be measured non-invasively by surface electrocardiogram. Management of Atrial fibrillation related electro-pathology to maintain sinus rhythm includes lifestyle changes, pharmaceutical and nutraceutical therapies. Geriatric population with Atrial fibrillation is at increased risk for both stroke and bleeding with AF anticoagulation. Hence anticoagulation must be tightly monitored in these conditions with a goal of maintaining the INR at 2. Proper evaluation and diagnosis describe the management strategies such as anticoagulation, rate control medication, rhythm control medication, interventional cardiac procedures etc. Identifying the complex pathophysiology of Atrial fibrillation in individual cases is difficult and assessment of the efficacy of current therapies is suboptimal. Therefore, unravelling the electro-pathology and underlying molecular mechanism is expected to develop an innovative personalized diagnostic tools and treatment modalities. As per Ayurveda classics "*Hridroga*" i.e., disease pertaining to "*Hridaya*" are very well explained along with management with classical Ayurveda formulations. According to Ayurveda principles all movements including rhythmic atrioventricular contractions are regulated by the functions of *vata* dosha particularly *vyana vayu*. The management of rhythm abnormality can be classified mainly in to two stages i.e., during the episodes of atrial fibrillation with symptoms and asymptomatic phase. In paroxysmal and lone AF management, Ayurveda formulations along with *rasayana* therapy beneficial to prevent the thrombogenic stroke and cardiogenic ischaemia. In the asymptomatic stage regular internal medications indicated in *Hridroga chikitsa* along with external therapies and administration of *rasayana* can be beneficial to prevent recurrence of rhythm abnormalities. This paper is a sincere effort to understand atrial fibrillation in terms of

Ayurveda parlance and explain the inter professional strategies, which will be beneficial for improving the Quality of Life as well as preventive aspects in AF.

Keywords: Atrial fibrillation, *Rasayana therapy*, *Hridroga*, Quality of Life, paroxysmal AF, Lone AF

OP 77

Advanced Applications of Hybrid Nanomaterials: A Review**Roshni Kumari¹ and Dr. Anil Kumar Yadav²****^{1,2}Department of Physics, School of Physical & Decision Science
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Abstract: Hybrid nanomaterials which are the combination of different nanomaterials exhibit properties same as its components and some unique properties. The use of hybrid nanomaterials is basically dependent upon the unique property of the materials which arises by the combination of its components. These nanomaterials are widely used in biomedical, energy, agriculture, and environmental remediation. This review summarizes the basic classification of hybrid nanomaterials based on their morphologies, components and functionality and applications of these nanomaterials in different fields.

Keywords: Hybrid nanomaterials, Organic-inorganic hybrid nanomaterials, Biomedical, Energy, Photocatalytic.

OP 78

Viable disposal of crumb rubber (CR) in bitumen modification to enhance its rheological properties**Aman Chand^a, Arun Kumar^a and Kamal Kumar^b**^aDoon University, Dehradun, 248001, Uttarakhand, India^bCSIR-Indian Institute of Petroleum, Dehradun, 248005, Uttarakhand, India

Abstract: Increased population of automobiles contributes to the generation of used tyres in large quantities. Recently the concept of rigid pavement has also significantly increased the scrap of waste tyre. These used tyres pose serious disposal problems and threaten the environment. Earlier attempts by other researchers showed that crumb rubber from used tyres could be used as a modifier for making flexible pavements. It seems sensible to suggest a way of reusing such waste materials in engineering and industrial construction projects like road pavement to enhance the qualities of asphalt mixture and lessen the detrimental effects of the waste materials on nature and the environment.

Present study used different percentages of CR from 0 to 12 wt% to make modified bitumens that were physico-chemically characterized for penetration, softening point, viscosity, and rheology. Study revealed that base bitumen of penetration more than 100 dmm was found suitable for making a modified bitumen with penetration and softening point 50 dmm and 50°C respectively under certain parameters like rate of stirring, the temperature of the reaction, and reaction time. Thermogravimetric analysis suggested that CR can be safely used in bitumen modification up to 160°C as its decomposition starts beyond this temperature. Rheological studies suggested that the addition of 12 wt% CR increases the fail temperature of the base bitumen from 61.83 to 67.4°C. RTFOT study showed the fail temperature of 12 wt% CRMB was 64.8°C. This study will not only solve the disposal problem of crumb rubber from waste tyres but also improve the mechanical as well as rheological properties of bitumen.

Keywords: Bitumen; crumb rubber; flexible pavement; pavement; rheology.

OP 79

Social Audit: A Powerful tool in the Social Responsibility
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Abstract: Social audits are necessary for several reasons, most notably to combat corruption and improve the accountability of the relevant authorities. As is well known, the government invests significant sums of money and resources in ensuring the welfare of the population through a variety of centrally and state-sponsored programmes and initiatives. Every public entity is responsible in this regard for the funds used to carry out the intended tasks in the public interest. Citizens are now more vocal about their rights, and the government is working to fulfil the rising demand for accountability and social responsibility. The main reason for the push for social audit is the huge disconnect between what the people need, what the government thinks and what is actually done. This is translated in practical terms into a concern for the improvement of “quality of life” through improving standards of living, health and education, earning capacity etc. for the people. The present study deals with the methodology for the social audit of SCSP/TSP works implemented by the irrigation departments. The study guides the researcher/auditors in various aspects to consider in performing the social audit such as record maintenance and transparency, economy efficacy and effectiveness of the works, impact of SCSP/TSP works on the quality of life of beneficiaries especially on farm income to know the economic upliftment and also the key issues found during the field survey to improvise and maintenance of the works.

OP 80

Preformulation studies of Roxatidine acetate: First step towards before the developing stable Floating Drug Delivery System**Vishnu Prasad Yadav* and Vinay Kumar****Veer Bahadur Singh Purvanchal University, Department of pharmacy, Jaunpur-222003, India****Abstract:**

Objective: The primary objective of this research study was to perform a preformulation analysis of Roxatidine acetate to establish a stable, robust and therapeutically effective system.

Methods: Preformulation studies of Roxatidine acetate was determine using Organoleptic properties, Determination of solubility, Melting point, FTIR Spectroscopy, Differential scanning calorimetry studies, Physical compatibility test , UV Spectroscopy (Determination of λ max) and HPLC analytical method. Standard UV curve was developed to aid in further analytical research studies.

Results: The preformulation evaluation studies of Roxatidine acetate yielded positive results, indicating that the drug possessed favorable Organoleptic properties, Determination of solubility, Melting point, FTIR Spectroscopy, Differential scanning calorimetry studies, and Physical compatibility test results. The drug's purity was verified through infrared spectrum analysis, which demonstrated characteristic peaks, and UV Spectroscopy, which revealed a maximum at 254 nm. The standard curve obtained was linear, with a correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.999$) and equation $y = 0.004208x + 0.001416$. No drug excipient interactions were observed, as there were no visual changes in drug samples with respect to discoloration, liquefaction, or odor. Finally, the HPLC data indicated that Roxatidine acetate was suitable for the formulation of an oral dosage form.

Conclusion: Roxatidine acetate, the drug candidate considered in this study, is a pure substance that possesses favorable properties for the development of an in-situ gel formulation. The selected numerous factors indicate that the drug is stable and can be used for further research and development purposes.

Keywords: Preformulation, Roxatidine acetate, Drug characterization, Drug-excipients compatibility studies.

OP 81

ध्यानः आनन्द का मुख्य द्वार

Kuwar Singh

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□ □ □(Abstract):

परमहंस योगानन्द पुस्तक "दिव्य प्रेम - लीला" में लिखते हैं कि चाहे जीवन आपको एक ही साथ वह सब कुछ दे भी दे जिसकी आपको इच्छा थी- धन, शक्ति, मित्र- तो कुछ समय पश्चात् आप पुनः असन्तुष्ट हो जायेंगे तथा कुछ और अधिक चाहेंगे। परन्तु एक ऐसी है वस्तु जो आपके लिये कभी नीरस नहीं हो सकती अर्थात् आनन्द स्वयं।

विभिन्न वस्तुओं की सम्पूर्ण खोज में, स्पष्ट या अस्पष्ट रूप से, वास्तव में आप अपनी इच्छाओं की पूर्ति द्वारा प्रसन्नता को खोज रहे हैं। आप उन वस्तुओं को नहीं चाहते जो दुःख लाती हैं। न ही उन वस्तुओं को जो प्रारम्भ में थोड़ी प्रसन्नता प्रदान करें, परन्तु अन्त में, दुर्गति एवं शोक के गहरे गड्ढे में डुबो दें। आपका लक्ष्य चाहे कुछ भी क्यों न हो, आप उसे पाकर सन्तुष्ट होने की आशा में, उत्सुकतापूर्वक उसे खोजते हैं, और जब आप इसे वास्तव में पा लेते हैं तो आपको आनन्द एवं प्रसन्नता का अनुभव करना ही चाहिये। तब सीधे ही आनन्द को क्यों न खोजें? इसे भौतिक सुखों एवं वस्तुओं के माध्यम से क्यों खोजें?

वह आनन्द जो प्रत्येक समय लयबद्ध रूप से परिवर्तित होता रहे, तथा तब भी स्वयं में अपरिवर्तनशील रहे। एक अभिनेता की भाँति, जो विभिन्न भूमिकाओं एवं भाव भंगिमाओं द्वारा मनोरंजन करता है, उसी सुख को हम खोज रहे हैं। ऐसा आनन्द केवल गहन एवं नियमित ध्यान द्वारा ही पाया जा सकता है।

इसलिये प्रसन्नता को भौतिक माध्यम से न खोजें, अथवा ऐसे सम्पर्कों पैदा हुई इच्छाओं में न खोजें। अपने भीतर में अक्षय अप्रतिबन्धित शुद्ध परमानन्द को खोजें, और आपके पास होगा नित्य-विद्यमान, नित्य-चेतन, नित्य-नवीन- आनन्द-ईश्वर। भौतिक सुखों की भाँति यह आनन्द मन का एक निराकार गुण नहीं है। यह ब्रह्म का सचेतन, स्वयंभू, आत्म-अभिव्यक्त गुण है। इसे खोजें और सदैव के लिये सुखी हो जायें।

OP 82

On Odd Graceful and Cordial Labeling of Super Subdivision of certain classes of Path and Star graphs**Devakirubanithi D¹ and Jeba Jesintha J²**¹**Dept of Mathematics, St. Thomas College of Arts and Science, University of Madras****Research Scholar, PG Department of Mathematics, Women's Christian College, Chennai**²**PG Department of Mathematics, Women's Christian College, University of Madras, Chennai**

Abstract: Odd graceful labeling is to inject $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0,1,2, \dots, (2q - 1)\}$ whenever the edge ab is identified the label $|f(a) - f(b)|$, so that the resulting edge labels are $\{1,3,5, \dots, (2q - 1)\}$ distinct. Cordial labeling is defined as a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ in which each edge ab is assigned the label $|f(a) - f(b)|$ with the conditions $|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$ where $v_f(0)$ and $v_f(1)$ denote the number of vertices with 0's and 1's, similarly $e_f(0)$ and $e_f(1)$ denote the number of edges with 0's and 1's. In this paper, we prove Odd graceful labeling of super subdivision of coconut tree, Octopus graph and Cordial labeling of super subdivision of Comb graph and bistar graph.

Keywords: Odd graceful labeling, Cordial Labeling, Super subdivision, Star graph, Bistar, Path, Coconut tree, Comb graph, Octopus graph.

2010 Mathematics Subject Classification: 05C78

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OP 83

A new multi-steps iteration scheme for approximating fixed points of non-expansive mappings with applications**Manoj Kumar¹ and Hemant Kumar Pathak²**^{1,2}**School of Studies in Mathematics, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur (C.G.) 492010, India**

Abstract: The aim of this paper is to prove some convergence results for generalized nonexpansive mappings endowed with the property (E) in uniformly convex Banach spaces. We also claim that our multi-step iteration is more stable for various parameters and initial values in comparison of iterations existing in literature. To validate our proofs, we provide a numerical example supported by graph and table. Finally, to describe the applicability of our iterative method, we used our iteration to solve the mixed type Volterra-Fredholm integral equation and the data dependence of the solution for the mixed type Volterra-Fredholm integral equation with a deviating argument. Thus, results in this article generalize and improve several well-known results in the existing literature.

Keywords: Generalized nonexpansive mappings, data dependence, fixed points, iterative algorithm, weak and strong convergence, mixed Volterra-Fredholm integral equation.

MSC (2010): 47H09, 47H10, 54H25.

OP 84

Effect of different carbon sources on lipid production of *Bacillus velezensis* DAA1**Sugandha Asthana¹ and Deepshikha Pande Katare^{1*}****¹Molecular Genetics Research Laboratory, Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity University, Uttar Pradesh, Sector-125, Noida, India**

Abstract: In recent years, the industrial expansion has boosted energy demand at an unprecedented rate. In the preceding year (April-March 2021), India purchased crude oil for a total of 119.2 billion USD of which 4,398 million USD was spent on fuel oils. Alternatives to fossil fuels that are non-renewable are being researched as a means of reducing pollution and the greenhouse effect in order to lessen India's reliance on fossil fuels and enhance its output of fuel oil. In the near future, biofuels, an alternative renewable source, can be an ideal option for replacing fossil fuel. They are created primarily from biomass, are sustainable, do not contribute to the greenhouse impact, and emit less carbon. One alternative is the use of oleaginous microorganisms to produce biofuels. Oleaginous microorganisms are those that are able to accumulate over 20% lipids of their dry cell biomass. Our previously isolated strain, *Bacillus velezensis* DAA1 showed the ability to accumulate lipid and the C:N ratio was optimized at 25:1. In this study, we grew the strain in four different carbon sources and lipid production was calculated. The strain showed the best growth in glucose (75%) and sucrose (41%). The lipids were characterized using GC-MS and 12-methyltetradecanoic acid (41%) and palmitic acid (21%) were observed in highest concentrations. Thus, this strain can potentially be used as an alternative for biodiesel production.

OP 85

THE RISING EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON YOUTH**Neha Dubey¹ and Dr. Satish Bodla²**¹Assistant Professor, Parul University²Kurukshetra University, Haryana

Abstract: The research aims to understand the effects and impact of social media on the young people in India. The study's objective is to learn how the youth in India use social media daily and how social media affects their behaviour. The research seeks to understand the dangers of social media use faced by the youth in India. The study used a qualitative research design. The findings of the study indicated that young people spend most of their time online and on social media. It also showed that the youth in India use the internet for at least 2-5 hours a day.

According to the findings, internet browsing is the most frequent activity young people engage in and their most used platforms are Instagram, Snap Chat, and Whatsapp. The study recommended that it is necessary to teach youngsters how to effectively use social media to cut down time wasted on chatting and browsing the internet, the Ministry of Electronic and Information Technology should also filter materials that get to young people or that young people have access to. Moreover, the study also recommended that parents should keep an eye on their children's social media platforms to protect them from sex predators and pedophiles. The study further recommends schools and government organizations use social media as one of the effective channels of communication for young people if they want to do so effectively.

Keywords: Social Media Platforms, Youth, Internet Browsing.

OP 86

Hepatoprotective and Nephroprotective Potential of *Saraca indica* Methanolic Extract against Lead Acetate induced Toxicity in Rats**Brijesh Shivhare^{1*}, Maneesha Pandey¹ and Ramesh Kumar²**¹Discipline of Biochemistry, School of Sciences, IGNOU, New Delhi, India -110059²Department of Biochemistry, Bundelkhand University, Jhansi, Uttar Pradesh, India - 284128

Abstract: *Saraca indica* has been used medicinally for several diseases and ailments and exhibits many pharmacological effects. The current study aims to evaluate the protective effect of *Saraca indica* methanolic extract (SIME) on lead acetate (PbAc₂) induced hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity in adult Wistar rats. Methanolic extract from *S. indica* was tested for its hepatorenoprotective effects against rat liver and kidney damage induced by lead acetate at 60 mg/kg. The renoprotective property of the ethanol extract (500 -2000 mg/kg) was assessed by the assessment of liver and kidney function parameters, antioxidant enzymes, and histopathology. N-Acetylcysteine (NAC) was utilized as a positive control at 100 mg/kg. PbAc injection caused a significant elevation in the liver and kidney function parameters as compared with normal rats. The concomitant decline in the glutathione content, catalase and SOD was observed as compared with the control. The SIME-treated rats showed a protective effect against lead-induced toxicity. The findings of this study show that SIME can protect liver and kidney damage induced by PbAc₂, possibly as a result of the antioxidant activity of its ingredients. Thus, it may be used to explore the active lead molecule for the management of liver and kidney diseases.

Keywords: *Saraca indica*, Lead acetate, Antioxidant, Hepatoprotective, Nephroprotective

OP 87

Identification of a sub network as a predictive dynamic biomarker for Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer**Anita Chauhan¹ and Seema Kalra²**^{1,2}School of Sciences, Indira Gandhi National Open University, Maidan Garhi Road, Maidan Garhi, New Delhi, Delhi 110068**Abstract**

Background: Developing predictive biomarkers to detect the tipping point before metastasis of NSCLC, is critical to prevent the irreversible deterioration. To discover such early-warning signals or biomarkers of pulmonary metastasis in NSCLC, we analyzed stage-wise gene expression data from lung cancer database with dynamic network method. Dynamical network biomarkers (DNB) showed time-dependent alterations of network biomarkers monitored and evaluated at different stages and time points during the development of diseases.

Methods: We identified the DNB containing 7 genes that can serve as a prognosis biomarker for NSCLC patients. We also show that DNB-related interaction network plays important roles in driving the state transition during NSCLC progression, by analyzing the dynamical changes of DNB molecules in gene expression levels.

Results: Our analysis revealed the sub network of 7 genes dynamically interacting in different stages of NSCLC and involved in the purine metabolic pathways. To our knowledge, our analysis first time revealed the dynamic interaction of Deoxynucleotidyltransferase Terminal Interacting Protein 1 with AZIN1 in various stages of NSCLC. Our literature analysis supported that identified sub network strongly involve in metastasis of NSCLC for primary tumor cells.

Conclusion: Our study suggested a new way to identify the tipping point of NSCLC pulmonary metastasis with its DNBs and provided biological insights into the molecular pathology of this progression from the perspectives of dynamics and networks.

Impact: Our analysis revealed a predictive biomarker as an early warning indicator of the initiation of metastasis for clinical application.

Keywords: Non-small cell lung carcinoma, Dynamic Network Biomarker, text mining, function enrichment.

OP 88

Removal of Organic Dyes by Activated Carbon Adsorption: A Review**Twinkle¹, Pankaj Chamoli^{1*} and Shreya Kotnala²**¹School of Basic & Applied Sciences, Department of Physics, Shri Guru Ram Rai University,
Dehradun-248001, Uttarakhand, India²School of Basic & Applied Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Shri Guru Ram Rai University,
Dehradun-248001, Uttarakhand, India

Abstract: Technological development not only improves the quality of life generally but also has a negative impact on the environment. Water contamination is now considered to be the most serious issue on the planet, and its remediation is the need of the day. Industrial wastewater frequently contains a number of hazardous organic substances that can harm both aquatic life and humans. The first pollutant discovered in industrial wastewater is dyes. A significant volume of wastewater containing toxic dyes is released into the environment by a number of industries, including, printing, pharmaceuticals, textiles, food processing, cosmetics, and paper. It is estimated that 50,000 tonnes of organic dyes are discarded annually around the world. The most effective method for removing organic dyes from wastewater is the adsorption technique by using activated carbon prepared from bio-waste due to its low cost of manufacturing, high porosity, high surface area, ease of handling, high degree of surface reactivity, etc. This review summarizes the recent studies on the use of activated carbon adsorption techniques for the removal of organic dyes from wastewater.

Keywords: Activated Carbon, Dyes, Wastewater, Adsorption.

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OP 89

Antimagic Labeling of Certain Families of tree Graphs**N K Vinodhini¹ and J Jeba Jesintha²****¹Department of Mathematics, Anna Adarsh College for Women,
University of Madras, Chennai****Research Scholar, PG Department of Mathematics, Women's Christian College, University of
Madras, Chennai****² PG Department of Mathematics, Women's Christian College, University of Madras, Chennai**

Abstract: A labeling of graph is assigning to its vertices or edges with integers such that no two adjacent vertices or no two adjacent edges have the same labeling subject to some conditions. Antimagic labeling is an edge labeling which has many variants and due to its relevance in many fields, lot of research developments in antimagic labeling is seen in recent times. Various types of labeling of many families of trees have been studied extensively in graph theory. In this paper we study antimagic labeling for certain tree families such as slim tree, Christmas tree and hypertree.

AMS Subject Classification: 05C78

Keywords: Antimagic labeling, slim tree, christmas tree, hypertree.

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OP 90

Development of hybrid model for improvement of forecast Agricultural commodity price**Borsha Neog* and Bipin Gogoi¹*****Assistant Professor, Department of Agril. Statistics, Assam Agricultural University****¹Professor, Department of Statistics, Dibrugarh University**

Abstract: Auto regressive fractional integrated moving average (ARFIMA) is widely applied for time series forecasting in long memory for divergent domain from several decades. The major limitation of this model is presumption of linearity. In real world, most of the long memory time series data are not purely linear; therefore hybrid model is evolved to enhance the prediction ability of ARFIMA models by fusing with other non-linear models. With this reasoning, this present study attempts to predict the price of Onion using ARFIMA-ANN and ARFIMA-SVM models. Results of this experiment justified the results of hybrid model gives better results with comparison to linear and non-linear models.

Keywords: ARFIMA, ANN, Forecasting, Price, Time series.

OP 91

Production of metabolites from mutant strains of *Rhodotorula minuta* upon varied temperature**Gowthami G. A. and Gunashree B.S.*****Department of Studies and Research in Microbiology, Mangalore University, P.G Centre (nominated as Kodagu University), Chikka Aluvara, Kodagu-571232, Karnataka, India**

Abstract: The present investigation focussed on the production of metabolites such as phytase, carotenoid pigment, lipids, and exopolysaccharide content by a hyper producing putative mutant strain of *Rhodotorula minuta*. Several putative mutants namely MR5, MR7, MR9, MR13, CMR1, and CMR2 were isolated after a series of UV and chemical Ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS) mutagenesis of an orange yeast strain, *Rhodotorula minuta*. The effect of different temperatures on the production of metabolites by these mutants was tested. The result showed an highest phytase from MR7 (21.620 U/ml) and CMR1 (26.735 U/ml) at 35°C and 30°C respectively. With respect to exopolysaccharide production, highest yield of 1000 and 1300 mg/l was obtained at 40°C with MR9 and CMR2, respectively, while lipid production from MR5 (34 g/kg) and CMR1 (11 g/kg) was at 25°C. Total carotenoid content in MR13 was 445 µg/kg at 35°C and in CMR1 it was found to be 454 µg/kg dry cell weight at 25°C. All the putative mutant strains of *Rhodotorula minuta* produced highest amount of one or the other tested metabolites. The CMR1 strain produced highest amount of both carotenoid and phytase, CMR2 strain produced good amount of exopolysaccharide while MR5 strain showed maximum accumulation of lipid content in the cells.

Keywords: *Rhodotorula minuta*, putative mutants, mutagenesis, lipids, exopolysaccharide, carotenoids, phytase.

OP 92

Impact of COVID-19 on Small and Marginal farmers in India**Ms. Supriya Gautam****PhD Research Scholar, Department of Economics, BBAU, Lucknow**

Abstract: This paper tries to understand the connection between the pandemic and migration holds tremendous academic significance. Particularly in countries with an agrarian economy, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought hardships faced by farmers into sharp focus. One of the most badly hit countries was India. *Coronavirus disease (COVID-19)* is an infectious *disease* caused by the *coronavirus*. *It affects the people and economy*. **Forced return** is a migratory movement. Migration is voluntary but the forced return is not voluntary. During the Pandemic, the Indian government imposed a lockdown in all countries on 25th March 2020. In a lockdown, returning people home is also a type of forced return. The return of people back home affects the small and marginal farmers' lifestyle and income. This study aims to bring to light the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the farmer's income in the Northern Indian state of Uttar Pradesh. The main objective of this paper is to examine the interlinked relationship between the pandemic and migration by correlating covid-19 with other similar incidents that happened in the past and exploring emerging scenarios on the current pandemic to draw a picture of international migration in the post-covid world order. It is a normative historical analytical and descriptive article that attempted a comprehensive study by using both primary and secondary sources of data. With the onset of globalization, there have been changes in the structure of the labor market. This study is based on Primary and Secondary data. Primary data was collected from the Auraiya District of Uttar Pradesh and the Sample size is 40. We collected the data through interviews and studied the impacts of the pandemic on the farmer's income. Secondary data was collected from books, journals, and other sources. Measures of central tendency and others tools used for data analysis. While the government has exempted the operation of agricultural markets and mandis from the lockdown, it will be difficult for farmers to harvest agricultural produce in the surplus States in the absence of migrant laborers. Some of the short-term impacts may affect price realization by farmers but the real worry for farmers is the decline in prices for agricultural produce. The decline in prices is likely to hurt the income of farmers, in the long run, more than the short-run supply disruptions and labor shortages. This study finds that farmers get 12 percent

less income than the last Ravi crop season. In other words, agriculture productivity was the decline in terms of money. We found negative impacts on the farmer's income due to COVID-19. As the impacts, responses, and ability to secure livelihoods varied across the different farming systems, we concluded that there is not a single solution that could be prescribed for all farming systems and that each land use system must be treated individually.

Keyword

Forced Return is a migratory movement which, although the drivers can be diverse, involves force or compulsion.

Migration is the movement of people in a country or between countries purposively.

Agricultural Productivity is the total crop production value in terms of Money.

OP 93

Detection of pathogen *Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus* (CLas) causing Citrus Greening Disease by gene primer method**Ishu Priya¹, Mohammad I. Ali² and Rashmi Saini^{3*}**¹Research Scholar, Department of Life Sciences, Mandsaur University, Mandsaur (M.P.), India²Associate Professor, Faculty of Life Sciences, Mandsaur University, Mandsaur (M.P.), India³Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, Gargi College, University of Delhi, Delhi, India

Abstract: Citrus is a major horticultural crop and is commercially grown worldwide. *Candidatus liberibacter asiaticus* (CLAs) is most widely found phloem-restricted gram-negative bacterium found in citrus crops causing citrus greening disease in India. In this study, a set of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) primer pairs were screened to diagnose CLAs, and this method enhanced the sensitivity to detect CLAs up to 10 times and 100 times compared to conventional PCR primers. In total, 120 samples from 25 different citrus cultivars in 4 different cities were assayed. The results showed that 25 samples were HLB-infected; the highest positive detection rate was 70% from the Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI, Delhi), and the lowest positive detection rate was 10% from Haryana. The results indicated that the designed PCR primer pairs can detect CLAs from different citrus cultivars and different geographic regions. The primers designed in the present study provide a very useful supplement to the current approaches for CLAs detection. The nrdbL2F1/R1 primer sequences correspond for detection of the multicopy nrdb gene, which encodes the β -subunit of ribonucleotide reductase (RNR), a critical enzyme involving bacterial proliferation. Three nrdb copies were in long form (nrdbL, 1,059 bp), and two were in short form (nrdbS, 378 bp). Detection of CLAs is very challenging because of its low concentration and irregular distribution in its citrus host. A lot of researchers tried to develop assays based on PCR, but the nrdb gene detection would provide a significant, rapid, and sensitive method to detect the pathogen early in the vector or the citrus plants. This will help in controlling the spread of the disease in non-infected plants, and thus prevent citrus crop loss. The present study provides means to detect pathogen in early stages and subsequently stop further dissemination of pathogen thereby helping in the management of Citrus Greening Disease.

Keywords: Citrus greening disease, *Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus*, primer, *Diaphorina citri* (Asian citrus psyllid), Huanglongbing (HLB)

OP 94

Tribal Health Problems and Reasons in Telangana State: A Review Study**Bhukya Anil¹ and Prof. Channaveer R.M²**¹Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Social Work, Central University of Karnataka, Kalaburagi²Dean, School of Social and Behavioural Science, Central University of Karnataka, Kalaburagi

Abstract: The government's primary goal is to provide high-quality healthcare services to tribes in the wake of the state reorganization of Telangana from Andhra Pradesh to improve their quality of life and development. But the health of Aboriginal peoples continues to deteriorate, and they face health issues. This researcher aims to find out the current state of tribal health problems and the reasons for tribal health problems in Telangana. According to the aim of this study, 20 papers were chosen as part of the methodology from databases. According to studies, there are important reasons for tribal health problems; the majority of those battling undernutrition and malnutrition are women, children, and teenage females. Typhoid and malaria, anemia, jaundice, and poor dental hygiene are also concerns in tribal households, along with infectious diseases. All of the issues mentioned above with tribal health problems are caused by factors like inadequate nutrition, alcohol use, smoking, and chewing tobacco, changing lifestyles, illiteracy, remote locations, economic conditions, and a lack of basic needs, and also tribal women's participation lower than that of rural women due to a lack of health awareness and knowledge, and knowledge gap among female health workers. The study recommends that improve tribal good health, all health professionals involved in the health system will overcome numerous obstacles and also prepare for future policy-making for health conditions, and also suggesting that the tribal people must realize that they must move forward with their full participation in the utilization of health care services for their well-being.

Keywords: Tribal, Tribal health problem, Telangana state.

OP 95

A review on activated carbon-based nanomaterials derived from bio-wastes for high performance supercapacitor application**Vanshika Gairola[#] and Pankaj Chamoli****Department of Physics, Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Dehradun-248001, Uttarakhand, India**

Abstract: The demand for renewable energy sources globally has gained huge research attention over the past decades. Technologies such as solar and wind have been commonly researched. However, economical use of these technologies is not extensive due to cost and the lack in service during source periods. To make these technologies fiercer, research into energy storage systems has increased over the last few decades. The idea is to design an energy storage system that allows for storage of electricity during lean hours at a relatively low cost. Energy storage such as Supercapacitors is receiving huge attention worldwide due to their fast charge/discharge rate, excellent working lifetime and high-power density. In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in bio-waste derived activated carbons as an electrode material for supercapacitor applications. Specially, ACs have been used in the EDLCs because of its immense specific surface area (SSA), different pore size and high conductivity. The main purpose for this is to convert waste materials bio-wastes into useful purpose and manifest the suitability of prepared activated carbon as a promising electrode material for SCs applications.

Keywords: Activated carbon, electrodes, supercapacitor, bio-waste

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OP 96

Artificial Intelligence as a Diagnostic tool for Prolapsed Intervertebral Disc: A Literature Review**Sandeep Pattnaik¹ and Manu Goyal²**¹Research Scholar, M.M *Institute of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Maharishi Markandeshwar (Deemed to be University)*, Mullana, Ambala²Professor, M. M *Institute of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Maharishi Markandeshwar (Deemed to be University)*, Mullana, Ambala**Abstract**

Background: Prolapsed intervertebral disc (PIVD) is a concentrated displacement of the content within the intervertebral disc beyond its natural limits as sequelae to the degenerative disc disease. It is commonly diagnosed with physical examination, X-ray, computed tomography scan, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) out of which MRI is considered to be the gold standard. In recent decades with the development of the sub-fields of artificial intelligence (AI) such as computer vision, computer-aided diagnosis, and deep learning, clinicians have turned towards its use as an alternative to the conventional method of diagnosis for PIVD.

Objective: The objective of this review is to appraise the role and utility of AI in the efficient diagnosis of PIVD.

Methods: Different search media were searched to gather published literature stating and examining the use of AI as a diagnostic tool for the diagnosis of PIVD.

Discussion: All of the included studies showed relatively moderate to high accuracy in the diagnosis of PIVD. Most of these studies used MRI images as the main source of input. They not only demonstrated higher test accuracy but also demonstrated good training accuracy. Most of those AI are based on the classification model of the computer-aided diagnosis design. AI in almost all the used models has arrived at the diagnosis based on the data extracted from the radiological findings, especially MRI without considering the physical examination findings and analysis of symptoms. This ignores the fact that there is a moderate relationship between radiological findings and symptoms in patients with PIVD. So future research in developing AI for the diagnosis of PIVD based on the physical findings along with the radiological findings can be considered.

Conclusion: From this viewpoint, the study concludes that the use of AI may effectively improve the diagnosis process in patients affected by PIVD.

Keywords: Prolapsed intervertebral disc; Disc herniation; Disc bulge; Artificial intelligence, Computer-aided diagnosis; Diagnosis

OP 97

Perspectives of patients having Diabetes Peripheral Neuropathy about Physiotherapy intervention: A Literature Review**Rittu Sharma¹ and Prof. (Dr.) Manu Goyal²****¹Ph.D. Scholar, Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Maharishi Markandeshwar (Deemed to be University), Mullana, Ambala, Haryana****²Professor, Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Maharishi Markandeshwar (Deemed to be University), Mullana, Ambala, Haryana****Abstract**

Background: 70% of diabetic population experience mild to severe damage to nervous system leading to Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy (DPN), defined as the presence of symptoms or signs of peripheral nerve dysfunction after exclusion of other causes.

Objectives: To review patient perspectives about Physiotherapy interventions for the management of DPN.

Methods: PubMed/Medline, Scopus, Google Scholar were searched to gather recent published qualitative literature stating patient perspectives of Physiotherapy interventions for the management of DPN.

Discussion & Conclusion: Physiotherapy interventions can be the more potentiate intervention for the management of DPN. Facilitators and barriers were identified: Facilitators are Family support, Emphasis by nurses and patient's knowledge about reduction in weight & blood sugar, and awareness of complications, and Barriers like social issues, lack of perception of obesity as a health issue, inability to link exercise with blood sugar control and lack of infrastructure. By knowing patients perspectives about facilitators and barriers in the management of DPN help in the treatment of DPN individuals to get more beneficial results and help in future implementation in clinical practice for better and fast recovery by focusing on barriers of the DPN.

Keywords: Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Physiotherapy, Intervention.

OP 98

**Synthesis, Thermal, Spectral Characterization and biological study of Mixed Ligand Nickel
(II) Complexes****Jitendra M. Pawara* and Sunil S. Patil****Department of Chemistry, Changu Kana Thakur Arts, Commerce and Science College
(Autonomous), New Panvel, Maharashtra, India**

Abstract: A series of new mixed ligand Ni(II) complexes of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{P})(\text{L})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ have been synthesized by using 2-amino-6-methyl pyrimidine-4-ol (HP), a primary ligand and N- and O- donor amino acids (HL) secondary ligands. Synthesis of Ni(II) complexes has been carried out by thermal and microwave methods. Results show that complexes synthesized by the microwave method were more efficient than the thermal method. Preparation time in the microwave method was short (4-7 min.) as compared to the thermal method (45 min.). Moreover, the microwave technique gave a very high yield (90%) of the complexes. The prepared complexes were characterized by Gouy experiment, FTIR, elemental analysis, TGA, and DTA at room temperature. The complexes have shown significant antimicrobial activities such as antifungal and antibacterial activity.

Keywords: Ni(II) complexes, 2-amino-6-methyl pyridine-4-ol, amino acids, microwave, antimicrobial activity

OP 99

 $f(T)$ gravity and Domain wall in Bianchi V space - time**Lovely Gupta¹ and Lallan Yadav²****^{1,2}Department of Physics, D. D. U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur 273009, India**

Abstract: In this paper, the investigation of some features of Bianchi type-V cosmological model in the presence of domain walls with volumetric power and exponential expansion laws towards the gravitational field equations for the linear form of $f(T)$ gravity is presented. The aspects of derived model are discussed with the help of solution and make out that both models at late times turn out to be flat Universe. We observed that the power law model has initially singular and becomes time-like and stable for whole expansion while exponential model is free from any type of singularity and stable throughout the expansion. Also the physical and geometrical properties of the observed universe have been described in detail.

OP 100

From Screen to Streets: How Bollywood Fashion Influences the Masses

Prof. Vasundhara Saluja & A.B.M Tanvirul Islam

Sharda University, Uttar Pradesh

Abstract: Fashion since ages has always affected life, it is a dynamic trend which is the spirit of time, and hence there have been theories of fashion adoption through different classes. Film industry Bollywood in India has always been the source of inspiration for masses. It has influenced the fashion choices and has played a crucial role in shaping the trends across. This paper will review almost a century of Bollywood costume and the trends which have affected fashion in India.

OP 101

Handcrafted Crochet Garments: Design Challenges**Isha Kumari****Student, Department of art & design, Sharda University**

Abstract: Clothing created entirely by hand with crocheting techniques is known as "handcrafted crochet." Creating patterns that are both practical and aesthetically pleasing, as well as choosing the right yarn and crochet hook, can be difficult when designing these clothes. One of the biggest design challenges when creating handcrafted crochet clothing is striking a balance between form and function. The clothing needs to be able to convey the desired style, look good, and feel good on the wearer. Choosing the right yarn and crochet hook for the desired design presents another difficulty. To achieve the desired texture and drape, the proper yarn type and hook size must be selected based on the intended use of the garment. Complex crochet patterns also call for a high level of expertise and attention to detail. To make a pattern that is cohesive and appealing to the eye, designers must carefully plan each stitch and take into account how it will interact with nearby stitches. Achieving a proper fit is one of the main difficulties in designing and creating handcrafted crochet clothing. Contrary to commercially produced clothing, which is frequently made in standard sizes, crocheted clothing is typically made to the wearer's precise measurements. This call for exact measurement attention in addition to knowledge of how various crochet stitches and patterns will affect the fit and drape of the garment. Making patterns that are both useful and aesthetically pleasing is another challenge. Designers must take into account the pattern's appearance as well as how it will interact with the garment's shape and intended use. A lacy pattern, for instance, might be lovely on a shawl or scarf but might not offer enough warmth or coverage for a sweater or cardigan. Other difficulties in designing handcrafted crochet clothing may include choosing the right yarn and hook size for the desired drape and texture, making seamless joins between various parts of the garment, and incorporating shaping techniques to make a flattering silhouette, in addition, to fit and pattern.

Overall, designing handcrafted crochet clothing requires a blend of technical proficiency and artistic vision, as well as close consideration of the wearer's unique needs and preferences.

OP 102

Biogenic amphoteric transition metal-based nanomaterial for pharmaceutical pollution reduction**B. Ramya¹, R. Dhanabal¹ and P. Gomathi Priya*****¹* Department of Chemical Engineering, Alagappa College of Technology, Anna University, Chennai-600025, TamilNadu, India**

Abstract: One of the most widely used alternative wastewater treatment processes is heterogeneous photocatalysis. It uses a semiconductor substance as a catalyst, with metal oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) being the most often utilized catalyst. A series of biogenic ZnO NPs were made using a precipitation approach using *Piper nigrum* (*P. nigrum*) as the biomaterial in this investigation. Crude black pepper (*Piper nigrum*) seed extract was used as a stabilizing, capping, and bio-reducing agent. Various zinc precursors such as zinc nitrate, zinc sulphate, and zinc chloride were employed to control the synthesis of zinc oxide (ZnO) nanostructures. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) and Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) were used to analyze the synthesized ZnO NPs using three zinc salt precursors for crystallinity, structure, size, shape, functionality, and external morphology. Based on XRD and FE-SEM, the ZnO NPs generated with zinc nitrate hexahydrate appeared more crystalline, with a sphere-shaped morphology and estimated crystallite size of 29.89 nm. FT-IR analyses confirmed chemical bond formations of Zinc oxide. Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) was used to verify the visible light response and band gap. Under ultraviolet (UV) irradiation, the photocatalytic activity of ZnO nanostructures for pharmaceutical waste was investigated. For all of the ZnO nanostructures tested, those produced using zinc nitrate precursor appeared sphere-like shape morphology had the best photocatalytic performance due to the crystallinity, crystallite size, and external topography of ZnO nanospheres is particularly appropriate for adsorption, were ascribed to their improved photocatalytic activity.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Green synthesis, Photocatalytic degradation, Pharmaceutical wastewater.

OP 103

**Phytochemical Analysis and Antioxidant Properties of Weedy Plants *Amaranthus viridis*
And *Portulaca oleracea*: A Review****Rohit Rangnath Paithane^{1*} and Satish S. Tambe²
LVH College, Nashik- 422003**

Abstract: Weeds are widely distributed all over the India, growing under a wide range of climatic conditions and has been utilized as a medicinal herb in traditional Ayurvedic medicine. Weeds are eaten extensively in various region of India. Weedy plants are very helpful in people's diet to maintain their health and boost the immunity system to protect from various diseases. The aim of the study was designed to evaluate the chemical composition, antioxidant and biological properties of different fractions obtained from these weeds *Amaranthus viridis* and *Portulaca oleracea*. Weeds could be used as an antioxidant profile enriched cultivar with high nutritional and antioxidant activity. Pigments, β -carotene, vitamin C, phenolics, and flavonoids had strong antioxidant activity and played a vital role in the antioxidant activity of selected weeds. This review provides a summary of phytochemical profile of these weeds. It gives an account of all the data and reports which have been appeared to prove its medicinal and nutritional importance.

Keywords: Weeds, phytochemicals, antioxidant, *Amaranthus viridis* and *Portulaca oleracea*

OP 104**Creating a better alternative - Use of Zero waste pattern making techniques for sustainable denim production****Prof. Ankita S. Pandey & Km. Nishi
Sharda University**

Abstract: Inefficiencies of design, pattern making & fabric management in the garment manufacturing processes lead to 10-25% fabric waste at the Pre-consumer stage itself. Keeping this in perspective an estimated 588-1471 million meters of denim fabric at least would have been wasted out of the 5,885 million meters of denim fabric that was expected to be consumed by 2020 in the Asia Pacific region alone. This is a great fashion management sustainability concern from environmental, ethical & economic perspectives which existing business management practices often ignore and this masked inefficiency. This study explores the Zero waste pattern development technique as a solution to the problem. It attempts to firstly, examine the tools that will be required by fashion businesses; secondly suggests how existing processes & hierarchies can be reshaped to fit in zero waste pattern development techniques to develop a sustainable relationship between design & manufacturing.

Keywords: Zero Waste, Zero Waste Pattern, Zero Waste Denim.

OP 105

Nanoparticle infused hydrogel as a sustainable approach in wastewater remediation: A mechanistic and comprehensive review**Jyoti Chaprana¹, Jaya Maitra² Bhaswati Banerjee^{2, 1,3*}**¹Dept. of Environmental Science, SoVSAS, Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, U.P.-201312²Dept. of Applied Chemistry, SoVSAS, Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, U.P.-201312³School of Biotechnology, Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, U.P.-201312

Abstract: In the present era of massive urbanization, industrialization and infrastructural development, the ever-increasing demand for water is one of the leading causes of water pollution that is largely responsible for deteriorating the condition this finite precious natural resource. Numerous methods have been developed and employed for wastewater remediation; nevertheless, a universal, optimal, sustainable method is yet to be achieved. Sustainable wastewater remediation involves the use of environment-friendly methods and technologies that minimize harm to the environment and conserve natural resources while decontaminating polluted water to render it is safe for discharge into rivers, lakes, or oceans, or to recycle and reuse for other purposes such as irrigation or industrial processes. It includes practices such as reducing water usage, utilizing renewable energy sources, and implementing green infrastructure to treat and manage wastewater. The need of a more rapid, efficient, widely applicable wastewater treatment method encouraged the researchers to explore the applicability of nano-hydrogel composites to remove pollutants. Hydrogel, a unique polymer that can absorb and retain large volumes of water have been used in a variety of clinical and non-clinical applications including wound dressings, contact lenses, drug delivery systems, and tissue engineering and also in agriculture to improve soil water retention and plant growth, and in environmental remediation to absorb and remove pollutants from water and soil.

In this comprehensive mechanistic review, we attempt to meticulously explore and analyze the application of nano-hydrogel composites in waste water treatment as it is a safe, sustainable, cost-effective, accessible and predominantly environment friendly in nature.

Key words: Wastewater remediation, Nanoparticles, Hydrogel, Nanohydrogel

OP 106**An Analytical Study of Development in UT Ladakh after the abrogation of Article 370,
especially in Tourism sector****Mohd Sadiq,****Ph. D Research Scholar, Department of Economic
Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow-226025, UP, India**

Abstract: This study shows an inclusive development in UT Ladakh after the abrogation of 370. In this paper we will touch all aspects of development in the regions. This study will also show the direct and indirect employment opportunities for local youths. The role of the centre and state government is to improve the trust of local people through various welfare schemes. We will discuss the tourism sector that is the backbone of the state economy, the role of employment opportunities given by the government to youths of the state and the review of the new reservation policy for weaker sections of the state after the abrogation of Article 370. The status of a special state, which was abolished by the central government, has also changed the statehood of Jammu and Kashmir and divided it into two union territories (UTs), the UT of Ladakh and UT of Jammu and Kashmir both come into existence on 31 October 2019.

Keywords: UT Ladakh, Employment, Reservation, Grassroots, Abrogation, tourism.

OP 107

Poetic Analysis of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Religion and Spirituality in Odisha**Ms. Rituparna Priyadarshini¹ and Dr. Pallavi Kiran²****Research Scholar, School of Humanities, Kalinga Institute of Industrial Technology**

Abstract: The tribal Kondh, Kui, Oraon, and Munda groups in Odisha are greatly impacted by religion. Their feeling of spiritualism and spirituality is not only accurately portrayed in folk tales, but also in the creative works of several poets, including Purnamaasi Jani, Bhima Bhoi, Sitakant Mahapatra, and Haldar Nag. The study illuminates how tribal societies uphold their traditional means of worship, cling to their ingrained religious beliefs, and dislike anything that feels imposed when viewed from a cultural perspective. The poetry works of Bhima Bhoi and Purnamasi Jani are examined for reference. In the works of Bhoi, it can be seen how social, spiritual, and religious sentiments and practises gave rise to the Mahima Dharma, which served as a vehicle to rebel against the elitist religious hierarchy's imposed traditions. In contrast, Jani's intense devotion to the tribal deity Lord Jagannath is an internalised core value that has made serving the Lord her main goal in life. The study seeks to analyse the intrinsic and extrinsic religiosity and spirituality in the chosen poems of the two poets and demonstrate the differences in their belief systems, with a focus on the deep beliefs and experiences of the communities of Kondh and Kui. Close cultural analysis also reveals that Bhoi's dedication to the Mahima Dharma is largely an effort to liberate the oppressed while spreading the same. On the other side, Jani's poems are about walking in the way of the Lord and doing all that draws one nearer to Him. Bhoi's poetry is additionally viewed as a revolt against the status order and in many respects contrasted the religion of Jagannath. Jani's poems, however, have the exclusive purpose of exalting the Lord and encouraging people to walk in righteousness. The study aims to revitalise the tribal poetic genre and offer insight on the various religious and spiritual practises that are prevalent in Odisha.

Keywords: Odia Tribal Poetry, Cultural Analysis, Bhima Bhoi, Purnamasi Jani, Intrinsic & Extrinsic Religiosity & Spirituality, Mahima Dharma, Lord Jagannath.

OP 108

Medicinal Uses of Bioactive Compounds in Medicinal Plants of Family Lamiaceae**Uma Sharma & Dr. Seema Bhadauria****Department of Botany, RBS College, Agra -282001**

Abstract: The Lamiaceae family, one of the most important herbal families, incorporates a wide variety of plants with biological and medical applications. Lamiaceae is one of the most important family comprising 236 genera and about 7200 species. Most of the plant species of family Lamiaceae produce large amounts of secondary metabolites like alkaloids, aurones, chalcones, flavones, anthraquinones, tannins, saponins, sterols and cardiac glycosides & also the compounds present in essential oils in plants with biological activities and therapeutic potential. Some examples include *Lavandula*, *Lamium*, *Mentha officinalis*, *Mentha vulgare*, *Origanum*, *Ocimum* spp., *Salvia hortensis*, *S. lavandulifolia*, *S. lateriflora*, *Thyme vulgaris* etc. The bioactive compounds present in plants have natural antibacterial, antioxidant, antifungal and antitumor effects which suggests that they may be viable alternatives to synthetic products in the therapy of various diseases. The family is also famous for the presence of essential oils like volatile oil of cineole presenting basil, menthol and limonene having peppermint, oleanolic acid, ursolic acid having the *Leucasaspera*, carvone, limonene, cineole presenting spearmint and thymol, carvacrol, having the thyme. This study will help to develop new drugs. Thus, the proven benefits on human health represent the main reason why various medicinal plant species belonging to the *Lamiaceae* family are increasingly exploited nowadays, in various formulations. These approaches have revealed not only therapeutic effects similar to those exhibited by synthetic chemical molecules, but have not produced any side effects and may thus be used over longer periods of time.

Keywords: Medicinal plants, Lamiaceae, Bioactive compounds

OP 109

Antibiogram and phenotypic detection of virulence genes among clinical isolates of *Klebsiella* species from CKD-UTI patients**Miss. Nithya K****PhD. Scholar, Microbiology****Yenepoya (Deemed to be University)****Mangalore, Karnataka**

Background: *Klebsiella* species has become relevant to study because of its emergence as second most uropathogen. Due to the recurrent failure of antibiotics in treating common infection like UTI, morbidity and mortality in immune-compromised patients has increased. Various studies have reported that *Klebsiella* spp. shows high virulence gene expression have Multi drug resistant (MDR) profile. This study was designed to evaluate antibiogram pattern and phenotypic detection of virulence genes in *Klebsiella* spp. from urine culture of CKD- UTI patients.

Method: Urine samples from CKD-UTI patients were collected and culture & sensitivity was done. The antibiogram of *Klebsiella* spp from automated AST (BD, Phoenix) was evaluated. Phenotypic detection of ESBL, Carbapenemase production & MBL were done as per CLSI guidelines. Hypermucoviscosity (HMV) and biofilm formation was determined by phenotypic method. The association of virulence gene expression with MDR pattern was analyzed.

Results: Among 65 isolates 61.53% (n=40) of *Klebsiella* sp were MDR. CKDG1 patients with 26.15% (n=17) were found to have higher chance of getting UTI rates of 23.07 % (n=15), 12.30% (n=8) & 15.38 % (n=10) were noted for CKDG2/CKDG3, CKDG4, and CKDG5 respectively. Resistance to Ceftazidime and Ampicillin was 75.38% (n=49) and 73.84% (n=48) respectively. ESBLs were found in 45% (n=18) and MBL in 5% (n=2). Carbapenemase were found in 65% (n=26) of the isolates. 20% (n=8) isolates were HMV positive. A total of 60% of *Klebsiella* spp. (n=24) were moderate to strong biofilm producers.

Conclusion: MDR *Klebsiella* spp. are common cause of UTI in CKD-population (61.53%). Biofilm formation (60%) & Carbapenemase (65%) were found among MDR strains. ESBL, Hypermucoviscosity, and carbapenemase production probably up regulate the formation of biofilm in *Klebsiella* species and altogether these genes favor the mechanism of antibiotic

resistance. Genotypic studies and strategy for inhibiting the expression of virulence genes need to be studied further.

OP 110

Semantics Cohesive Devices in Compositions: The case of Arab EFL learners**Samer J H Abuowda¹ and Dr. S. A. Shanvas²**¹Ph.D. Scholar Department of Linguistics, Karyavattom Campus, Trivandrum, Kerala University²Associated Professor Department of Linguistics, Karyavattom Campus, Trivandrum, Kerala University

Abstract: The aim of this study is to identify the most significant semantics cohesive devices like reference, substitutions, ellipsis, conjunction, and lexical cohesion in both Arabic and English. It adopts Halliday and Hasan's (1976) model for analysis. It explains how the four types of cohesion function in Arabic and English and how they contribute to the overall cohesiveness and textuality of texts. The study provides some insights into the nature of cohesion in the two languages, especially in Arabic. This study is theoretical, and the researcher relies on books, articles, and the internet. The procedure to be followed in achieving the aims of the present study consists of defining with elaboration the notion of semantic cohesion in both English and Arabic languages under study and classifying the types of cohesive devices in composition. In analyzing cohesive devices in Arabic, the researcher has depended on the available literature, especially major sources in Arabic, and has counted on his intuition checked upon by native speakers of Arabic. In terms of the communicative nature of writing, cohesion is regarded as an essential textual component for both creating organized texts and making the content understandable to the reader.

Keywords: Semantic, Cohesive, Composition, EFL Learner

OP 111

Cyber Crimes Related to Online Fraud: Laws and Challenges**Awadhesh Kumar****Research Scholar, Department of Law****Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, UP**

Abstract: At present technologies have changed the whole world. Most people have involved and access internet through the mobile and computer. Technology has transformed the society and has a big impact on business. Computer and mobile devices are using for every work like shopping, online banking transaction, ticket booking etc. With the use of computer and mobile, there has been increased cybercrime. Cybercrime is a crime where a computer or mobile device is used as a tool or target with the connection of internet. Committing online fraud is a type of cybercrime. There has been a steady spike in cases of cybercrime in the last five years. According to NCRB report 2021 total 52974 cases in 2021 were registered under cybercrimes, showing an increase of 5.87% in registration over 2020 (50035 cases). Cybercrime motive 2021 fraud cases are 32230 whereas in 2020 such cases were 30142. Thus, the cyber fraud motive cases have been increased by 6.92% from last year. The investigation and containment of this crime present a significant problem for enforcement organisations around the world. While, considering the concept of the online cyber fraud, it has been considered that financial and cybercrime are part of the bigger concept of the crime. Online fraud crimes are those crimes, which are perpetrated using cyber technology, but basically for financial gains. Major online fraud crimes which are most prevalent are Credit Card/ Debit Card frauds, ATM fraud, O.T.P. fraud, Virtual Crypto Currency Frauds/Scams, Virtual Money Laundering, Ransomware or Cyber Extortion, Phishing and Vishing Scams, Dark Web Markets, Social Media fraud, Online game fraud and Identity Theft. To deal such type of crime we have Information Technology Act 2000.

OP 112

Knowledge regarding warning signs of cancer among home-maker women**Mrs. Vinita Jamdade¹, J Sonali², J Suchita³, M Akib⁴ and S Ravi⁵**¹Assistant Professor, Bharati Vidyapeeth College of Nursing Pune²⁻⁵T Y G N M Students Bharati Vidyapeeth College of Nursing Pune

Introduction: When aberrant cells proliferate uncontrolled, cross their normal borders to infiltrate other body parts and/or move to other organs, the result is cancer, a broad category of disorders that may begin in almost any function or muscle. The latter phase, known as metastasizing, is a significant contributor to cancer-related mortality. Other synonyms for cancer include neoplasm and malignant tumour. Approximately 9.6 million fatalities, or one in every six deaths, were attributed to cancer in 2018, making it the second largest cause of death worldwide.

Methodology: In the present study Descriptive Survey research design was used. Data collected on 500 samples. Tool was constructed to identify the demographic variables, and a set of self-structured questionnaires on knowledge regarding warning signs of cancer in home- maker women. Result: The main results about the degree of awareness of cancer warning signals among Home-Maker women are that 497 (99.4%) of the women have average knowledge, 3 (0.6%) have poor knowledge, and 0 (0%), have high knowledge. The mean awareness of cancer warning signals amongst Home-Maker women is 9.37, with a standard deviation of 0.74. Conclusion: The research was carried out to see how well Home-Maker women in certain parts of Pune city were informed about cancer warning indicators. The analysis was conducted to evaluate Home-Maker women's awareness of cancer warning indicators. It demonstrates the average knowledge score of most married women. The level of understanding and their demographics did not significantly correlate with one another.

Recommendation: A similar study can be done on urban population.

Keywords: Assess, Knowledge, Warning signs, Cancer, Home- maker.

OP 113

Efficient Removal of Fluoride Ions and Anionic Dyes by Zirconium-2-Imidazolidinethione Functionalized Reduced Graphene Oxide Aerogel**Aminul Islam^{1*} and Sana Fatima¹****¹Analytical Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, UP, India-202002**

Abstract: We synthesized a novel multifunctional aerogel (Zr-IMDT/rGOA) by functionalizing Graphene Oxide with $ZrCl_4$ and 2-imidazolidinethione through one pot hydrothermal reduction and subsequent freeze drying. The aerogel was characterized and employed for the removal of anionic pollutants. Zr-IMDT/rGOA showed excellent removal performance for both fluoride ions (F^-) and anionic dyes (Alizarin Red S (ARS) and Eosin Y (EY)). The removal efficiency of F^- was 97.96% at pH 4.6, stirring time 30 min, initial concentration of 10 mg L^{-1} and adsorbent dosage 0.01 g as optimized by the Box Behnken Design (BBD) in response surface methodology (RSM). Subsequently, removal of >95% was achieved for both dyes, ARS and EY. Brouers Sotolongo isotherm model fits well with the equilibrium sorption data and maximum sorption capacity (Q_{max} , mg g^{-1}) 328.28, 694.00 and 1449.28 was obtained for F^- , ARS and EY, respectively. Fractal like pseudo second order (FLPSO) kinetic model was best suited to the kinetic data and >50% removal was attained for all analytes within 5 min indicating fairly fast kinetics. Zr-IMDT/rGOA showed good selectivity for F^- in the presence of other counter ions (Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- and $H_2PO_4^-$) and could be regenerated upto 5 cycles with >90% removal. The synthesized aerogel was successfully applied for the removal of F^- from tap water, river water and black tea infusion.

Keywords: Graphene oxide, Aerogel, Adsorption, Fluoride, Dye Removal, Box Behnken Design.

OP 114

Efficiency of probiotic in preterm neonates with sepsis: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials**Faiza Iqbal¹, N Siva², Baby S Nayak², Leslie Edward Lewis^{1*} and Vandana K E³**¹Dept of Paediatrics, Kasturba Medical College, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal²Dept of Child Health Nursing, Manipal College of Nursing

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Abstract: Microbial colonization in immune naive preterm neonates may lay the groundwork for life-long disease risk from immune modulation. Probiotics may reduce the risk of sepsis through a variety of mechanisms, including production of short-chain fatty acids to lower intestinal pH and support intestinal epithelial cell function, suppression of pathogenic bacterial growth and by upregulation of host anti-inflammatory genes. A comprehensive search was conducted from global databases like Cochrane CENTRAL, CINAHL Plus via EBSCO host, MEDLINE via PubMed, EMBASE, SCOPUS, ProQuest Medical Library, and Web of Science by using specific keywords and search terms. We assessed the quality of included randomized controlled trials using the Revised Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool (RoB 2.0). And quality of non-randomized controlled trials, using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal Checklist. The primary outcome of the study was to assess the incidence of sepsis, mortality, and length of NICU stay. Secondary outcome included to assess the morbidities associated. A total of 2380 potential studies were identified in the initial literature retrieval from eight databases. The quantity pooling of data revealed that there was increase in incidence of sepsis in control group when compared to probiotic group. (RR = 1.14; 95% CI: 0.98–1.32, p = 0.09, I² = 48%). Heterogeneity was substantial (I² = 48%) for the comparison probiotic group with Placebo. There was no significant difference in mortality and length of NICU stay between the probiotic and control groups. Current evidence indicates that probiotic supplementation in neonates does not have effect in reducing the risk of sepsis in preterm neonates in neonatal intensive care units. Further studies are needed to address the optimal probiotic organism, dosing, timing, and duration. High-quality and adequately powered RCTs regarding the efficacy and safety of the use of probiotics in ELBW infants are still warranted.

Keywords: Probiotics, Preterm, Neonates, Sepsis

OP 115

Identification and Hydrolytic Enzyme Potential of Actinomycetes from the Mangrove Sediments of North Kerala**Kiran Kishore and Sebastian C. D.****Division of Molecular Biology, Department of Zoology, University of Calicut**

Background: Mangroves are woody plant communities that are accustomed to the harsh transitional zone between aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems and have evolved adaptations with the harsh environment. A variety of microbes are found in mangroves, and actinomycetes are one among them. Actinobacteria have been continuously reported as the prolific producers of microbial bioactive secondary metabolites for pharmaceutical aspect and agricultural applications. Mangrove actinomycetes are versatile in terms of its bioactivity, which actually motivates to intrinsically assess its bioactive potentiality.

Method: This work explores the diversity and hydrolytic enzyme potential of actinomycetes along the mangrove sediments of northern Kerala with respect to sediment characteristics. Temperature, pH, salinity, organic matter and sediment texture were analysed. Isolated actinomycetes colonies were screened for the production of various hydrolytic enzymes and selected isolates were identified by molecular methods using the amplification of 16S rRNA gene.

Results: A total of 124 isolates were obtained during the present study. pH of the sediment ranged from 6.5 – 7, temperature from 27-30°C. Kadalundi showed maximum CFU/ml and Chettuva showed lowest population. 90% of isolates exhibited various hydrolytic enzyme activity. The isolates obtained belonged to the genera *Streptomyces*.

Conclusion: The present study is mainly involved in the isolation and determining the hydrolytic potential of actinomycetes obtained from the mangrove sediments of Northern Kerala. 124 isolates were obtained of which 90% of the isolates showed hydrolytic potential. Maximum population of actinomycetes was obtained from Kadalundi station. The population of actinomycetes varied according to sediment characteristics.

Keywords: Mangroves, Actinomycetes, Hydrolytic enzymes, 16S rRNA gene, Sediment

OP 116

**Species diversity and Vectoral Status of Culex mosquitoes in
Mananthavady Taluk, Wayanad, Kerala
Maiby Thankachan,
Department of Zoology, University of Calicut**

Abstract**Background**

Culex is the most prevalent mosquito species across the world. Their highly opportunistic behaviour of feeding on both human and animal blood increases their potential to transmit zoonotic diseases that make them important threat to public health. In addition to nuisance that Culex species cause, they also transmit diseases such as Japanese and Saint Louis encephalitis, Rift valley fever, West Nile Virus and lymphatic filariasis.

Materials and methods

Mosquitoes were collected from different locations of Mananthavady Taluk during the period 2019 – 2022. Larval and adult collections were done using dippers, light traps and aspirators. Collected mosquitoes were identified using the authentic taxonomic keys of Barraud (1934) and was confirmed with the help of experts from ICMR – Vector Control Research Centre, Puducherry, India.

Results and Discussion

A total of 5234 Culex mosquitoes under 24 different species belonging to 5 subgenera namely, *Culex*, *Oculeomyia*, *Culiciomyia*, *Eumelanomyia* and *Lophoceraomyia* were collected. Mosquitoes belonging to Subgenus Culex outnumbered all other mosquitoes with 11 species followed by *Lophoceraomyia* (5 sp), *Eumelanomyia* (3 sp), *Oculeomyia* (3 sp) and *Culiciomyia* (2 sp) respectively. Out of the 24 species, 7 species were new reports to Kerala. viz, *Cx. mimulus*, *Cx. barraudi*, *Cx. hutchinsoni*, *Cx. murrelli*, *Cx. foliatus*, *Cx. wilfredi* and *Cx. minor*. Nine species namely *Cx. gelidus*, *Cx. tritaeniorhyncus*, *Cx. fuscocephala*, *Cx. whitemorei*, *Cx. infula*, *Cx. bitaeniorhyncus*, *Cx. quinquefasciatus*, *Cx. vishnui* and *Cx. pseudovishnui* are major vectors of Japanese Encephalitis and Filariasis.

Conclusion

This study adds valuable information about the systematics of nine public health important mosquito species acting as significant vectors for Japanese encephalitis and Filariasis and their high adaption to the environment. This information is further used for the effective implementation of region-specific vector control strategies.

OP 117

Mechanistic Investigation of Formation of Highly-Dispersed Silver Nanoparticles using Sea Buckthorn Extract**Hardeep Kaur^{1,2}, Meenakshi Verma^{1,3}, and Vishal Mutreja^{1*}**¹**Department of Chemistry, University Institute of Science, Chandigarh University, Mohali, Punjab-140 413 India**²**Department of Biotechnology, University Institute of Biotechnology, Chandigarh University, Mohali, Punjab-140 413 India**³**University Centre for Research and Development, Chandigarh University, Mohali, 140413, Punjab, India**

Abstract: Nowadays, the greener pathways for the synthesis of nanostructures are being explored. The extracts of different parts of plants *viz* leave, stems, and roots have been investigated. However, these extracts have been prepared by simply boiling or microwaving, or sonicating the parts of plants with water. Therefore, to have deeper insight and to investigate the full potential of plant extracts, serial extraction of leaves of Sea buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides L.*) which is a medicinally important plant was attempted using Soxhlet apparatus. The as-obtained polyphenolic-rich extract was employed for the preparation of Ag-NPs. Under optimized reaction conditions *viz* 60°C temperature and 500 µL of extract solution (5mg/mL) highly disperse spherical nanoparticles of the average size of 16 nm were obtained. To further understand the reduction by the extract, kinetic studies were also carried out which suggest the predominant occurrence of pseudo-first-order reaction. Furthermore, the mechanism of formation of silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs) using major components of extract *viz* gallic acid and catechin which were identified by HPLC were also investigated using DFT. The mechanistic investigation was performed for both the keto-enol and radical-mediated preparation of Ag-NPs. Additionally; the prepared silver was also employed for the colorimetric detection of H₂O₂.

Keywords: Greener Nanoparticles, Colorimetric sensor, DFT

Graphical Abstract

OP 118

To detect the post covid syndrome with relation to vaccination status in PCR confirmed covid 19 infected patients prospective study**A. Ramyasree¹ and Dr. Sethumadhavan, MD²**¹Research Scholar²Professor, Department of Microbiology, AVMC, Puducherry

Abstract: Data are available concerning the effect of SARS COV2 vaccination on symptoms associated with covid 19 infection can result in long term physical and mental health consequences lasting for longer than 3 months after infection are called post covid syndrome. This is a prospective study where data will be collected from individuals who are pcr confirmed covid19 infected patients diagnosed from January 2021 till november2022 patients from our tertiary care hospital will be included in this study contact information of patients will be available with us. After enrollment, PCR confirmed COVID 19 infected individuals the participants will have to complete a questionnaire with questions regarding socio-demographic details, contact information, symptoms when diagnosed with SARS CoV2, medical comorbidities and risk factors, current health status and present symptoms. To assess the post COVID syndrome in the general population, questions regarding their recovery after infection, the duration they required to become symptom free, any persistent symptoms and other or new ongoing symptoms will be recorded by personal interview

Results: A total of 381 patients completed the survey 356 satisfied the inclusion criteria male are 234 and females are 147 the initial infection as proven with .Antigen Test (Standard Q kit) and RT-PCR (PROMEA THERAPEUTICS) as done by taking Nasopharyngeal swab Total 172 patients received at least one dose of SARS COV 2vaccine at the time of survey,138 received 2doses of vaccine,71 are unvaccinated , The vaccinated and unvaccinated groups were comparable in terms of gender distribution and socioeconomic characteristics.

Discussion: For modified dyspnea Medical Research Council scale, Grade ≥ 1 dyspnea will be considered significant. For FAS scale, score of 22 or more will be considered as threshold.

For DASS 21 scale, score for depression > 9 , score for anxiety > 7 and score for stress > 14 will be reported as significant.

Conclusion: Double vaccinated participants as associated with reduced risk of reporting most of post acute COVID 19 symptoms.our results suggest that vaccination may have a protective effect against long term covid 19 symptoms

OP 119

Mitochondrial COI-based population genetic structure of *Labeo rohita*
Sonakshi Modeel¹ and Ram Krishan Negi^{1*}
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Delhi-110007, India

Abstract: Assessment of genetic diversity and population genetic structure is important for species that are economically important, threatened, and are at global conservation priority. Analysis of mitochondrial DNA is broadly used in species identification and population genetics studies due to the availability of sufficient reference data and better evolutionary dynamics for phylogeographic investigation. *Labeo rohita* (Rohu) is an economically important species cultured under carp polyculture systems in Asia. The present study explores the genetic diversity, phylogeography, and population structure of *L. rohita* from different countries using cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) gene. A total of 17 *L. rohita* specimens were sampled from River Beas, India. For the genetic study, we amplified and sequenced COI mitochondrial DNA region. The obtained genetic data was combined with 268 COI records available in the NCBI and BOLD databases originating from multiple populations/countries across South and Southeast Asia. As a result, 33 haplotypes were identified that displayed low nucleotide ($\pi = 0.0233$) and moderate haplotype diversity ($Hd = 0.523$). Tajima (D) was found to be negative ($P > 0.05$), whereas Fu's F_s showed a positive value ($P > 0.05$). The overall F_{ST} value between studied populations was 0.481 ($P < 0.05$). AMOVA analysis indicated higher variation within than among the population examined. The neutrality tests suggested the presence of rare haplotypes and stable demography within studied populations of *L. rohita*. The Bayesian skyline plot indicated steady population growth until 1 Mya followed by population decline, whereas F_{ST} values indicated significant genetic differentiation. High heterogeneity was observed in the Pakistan population which could be indicative of long-term isolation and excessive culturing to meet market demands. The present results are the first global comparative analysis of *L. rohita* and pave the way forward for detailed genomic and ecological studies aimed at the development of improved stock and effective conservation plans. The study also makes recommendations to conserve the genetic integrity of wild species from aquaculture-reared fishes.

OP 120

Phenotypic and Genotypic detection of extended spectrum beta lactamase enzyme in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates from the clinical specimens of the patients in a tertiary care hospital

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Abstract

Background

Klebsiella pneumoniae can cause a number of diseases, such as pneumonia, bloodstream infections, meningitis, and urinary tract infections. Depending on the infection site, the symptoms of a *K. pneumoniae* infection vary. The purpose of this study is to determine the prevalence of the ESBL enzyme in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates using phenotypic techniques from various hospital wards and the identification of ESBL resistance genes such as CTX, TEM and SHV.

Method

Different clinical samples from a tertiary care hospital were used to obtain *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates, which were then identified using a conventional disc diffusion technique and Combined double disc method, ESBLs were screened. The CTX, TEM, and SHV genes were genotypically detected using Multiplex PCR in accordance with the recommended procedure.

Result

The pattern of antimicrobial susceptibility testing revealed that the most resistant antibiotics include , CAZ (76.67%), CTX(74.07%), CXM(72.67%), followed by TOB(72%), and PIT (67%). Out of 150 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates, ESBL Combined double disc method positive are ceftazidime+clavulanicacid 115(74.7%) and, cefotaxime+clavulanicacid positive, 112

(74.7%). By using the Multiplex PCR technique, the CTX and SHV and TEM genes were 65.3% 51.3% and 41.3% recorded respectively.

Conclusion

Most *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates that produced ESBLs have the CTX gene.

OP 121

Structural and Optical Characterization of MoS₂ for its Potential Applications in Biosensing**Anju^{1,2}, and Amit Garg²**¹Department of Electronic Science,
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Abstract: Molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) belongs to the category of transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) where one atom of Molybdenum is bonded with two atoms of Sulfur. Its physical, chemical, and electronic properties have motivated researchers for their potential use in miniaturization, as well as wearable devices. It has challenged the dominance of semiconductors and graphene based devices at the nanoscale level. Its promising properties in 2D form make it a front runner where Si based semiconductors devices suffers from quantum and tunneling effects during miniaturization. It has wide range of applications in electronics especially sensors like optical sensors, biosensors, electrochemical biosensors, energy applications in batteries, solar cells, as well as in spintronics and magnetoresistance. In our initial work, we have started with the characterization of CVD grown MoS₂. The structural characterization has been carried out using XRD and Raman measurements whereas optical characterization has been done using FTIR, UVVis spectroscopy as well as PL measurements. Results are analyzed to understand their future potential application as biosensors.

Keywords: Molybdenum disulfide, 2D materials, Biosensors, characterization.

OP 122

**Spatiotemporal Analysis of Faridabad district, India Using Remote Sensing and GIS
Approach****Bhavna Singh¹ and V. Venkatramanan²**¹Research Scholar, SOITS, IGNOU, Delhi, India²Assistant Professor, SOITS, IGNOU, Delhi, India

Abstract: With the creation of NCR Plan (1985) for decongesting Delhi, development of adjacent towns takes place and low land cost are the main factors responsible for shifting economic activities that attract people and infrastructure development. The development of Faridabad district is primarily as industrial and commercial zone; a railway line and national highway 19 pass through its middle to provide services. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor the land use land cover (LULC) changes caused by human activities spatio-temporally using remote sensing and GIS. The study used Landsat satellite data for the years 1989, 2000, 2010 and 2020 to delineate the changing pattern of LULC using supervised classification. The result indicates that build-up area and barren land increased by 11.14% and 8.87%, respectively, with a substantial reduction in agricultural area (-13.86%) and green cover (-4.59%). It is observed that urban growth is in a longitudinal pattern. The mining activity was there till 2004 that has drastically affected the environment of the region. Thus, the spatiotemporal information provided from remote sensing and GIS is helpful to the decision makers and planners for effective sustainable urban development with economic growth.

Keywords: Land use land cover, Urban growth, Remote sensing, Sustainable, Faridabad

OP 123

Position and Rights of the unborn child
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“Unborn” Simple means “that is not born” which is an dim- witted a description of this intelligence as anyone could have given it, This word has never had any significance in the cosmos. This can be as a result of the protection offered to them by local, national law. This expression alludes to the legal proverb “en venter as mere,” which alluded to the mother’s womb. This issue at hand is whether or not an unborn person can be considered a person in the eyes of the law and exercises the same rights as other live individuals. Several pieces of legislation also outline the standing and rights of the unborn, each of which confers a different set of rights.

This essay will focus primarily on the legal rights of unborn children under various statutes, including the Hindu succession Act, The Transfer of Property Act and the Indian Constitution. The Indian Penal Code, among other laws, makes reference to international convention and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International convention on the Political Rights of the child all protect children’s rights both before and after birth. These treaties also Place emphasis on important international court decisions. And this study explains the ambiguous legislation and the Declaration of Human Rights, which states that all life should be protected, beginning with conception.

The essay will compare the laws governing unborn people’s rights and status in India, the United Kingdom and United Status. As a result we can state that the research completely depends on the facts that are currently in existence. The research is based on the doctrinal method of research in which we positively depended on the existing facts and conceptions of various intellectuals.

OP 124

Exploring the scope of embryo-toxicology in post-mortem examination: A promising future tool

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Forensic entomology, the application of entomology in forensic science, is the science of insects and related arthropods which is applied to help solve litigation in civil and criminal cases (Byrd & Castner, 2001). In the absence of any other required evidences, the Time of death/ Post-mortem Interval (PMI) is calculated by determining the developmental stage of insects found on the corpse. The two groups of insects of most important to a forensic investigation are species in the Order of true flies (Diptera) and the beetles (Coleoptera). The standard method of entomological estimation of Post-mortem Interval (PMI) is identifying larval and pupal stages and estimating their age by considering temporal, climatic, and toxicological aspects involved. In addition to this, especially in cooler climates, when the eggs are the only entomological evidence available, the age of eggs can also be a critical aid for the same. However, in such cases, due to the lack of a proper method for embryo visualization, the time taken for the egg's hatching is the commonly used index to calculate the age of the egg to determine the PMI. The major limitation of this method is (1) the eggs may take days to hatch, (2) entomotoxicological effects on development within the egg are unable to detect.

This paper deals with the light microscope visualization of major stages of embryonic development in *Chrysomya megacephala* egg and its timing in two slightly different average temperatures of 26°C & 21°C. *Chrysomya megacephala*, commonly called the Oriental Latrine fly, belongs to the family Calliphoridae under the Order Diptera. The visualization method using sodium hypochlorite treatment shows definite stages and landmarks of development in the embryo. Furthermore, our findings prove that even a slight change of 5°C in average temperature shows significant differences in embryo development timings.

OP 125

**Biochemical Characterization of Different Mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) R. Wilczek)
Accessions****Krishna Desai¹ and Nainesh R. Modi^{1*}****¹Department of Botany, Bioinformatics and Climate Change Impacts Management,
Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-380009**

Abstract: Mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) R. Wilczek) is a valuable annual crop that belongs to the Fabaceae family and is a good source of nutrients such as proteins, carbohydrates, and other secondary metabolites that contribute to its functional properties. However, the crop's productivity is low in India due to a lack of genetic diversity. The purpose of this study was to investigate the biochemical diversity of 26 mungbean genotypes by conducting quantitative phytochemical tests including total phenol, flavonoid, tannin, cardiac glycosides, and alkaloid along with antioxidant activity. The study found significant differences in biochemical composition among the genotypes, with some genotypes containing high levels of bioactive compounds. The study also identified a positive correlation of phenol content with antioxidant potential and tannin content. The study employed multivariate approaches, such as PCA and HCA, to characterize, evaluate and categorize the mungbean genotypes based on their similarities and dissimilarities. The cluster analysis identified several highly variable genotypes that are rich in bioactive constitution such as D-1, D-11, and D-13, and could be used as parents in future breeding programs or selected for functional mungbean landraces for daily consumption.

Keywords: *Vigna radiata* (L.) R. Wilczek, Biochemical Characterization, Antioxidant Activity, Principal Component Analysis, Hierarchical Cluster Analysis

OP 126

Digitization of India's Upcoming census**Ms. Cooshalle Wilson****PhD Research Scholar, Department of Political Science****Desh Bhagat University, Mandi Gobindgarh,****Punjab- 147301, India**

Abstract: In the current post-pandemic triggered health crisis, timely and reliable disaggregated data and statistics are critical to understanding, managing, and mitigating the human, social, and economic losses affecting billions of people. However, the disruptions to such regular and reliable data production operations such as national-level censuses caused by the lockdown of coronavirus disease (COVID-19), combined with an unprecedented surge in demand for information to monitor the spread of the virus and mitigate its impact, have presented unprecedented challenges to the data and the statistical community at the global, regional, and worldwide levels.

In addition, the pandemic struck at a time when many countries, India included, were already struggling with severe resource constraints and facing urgent calls from all sectors of society to fill the serious data gaps needed to usher in a decade of action with effective, targeted measures to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Building on the available qualitative data the current research aims to explore and analyze the problems standing in the way of accurate, safe, and prompt data collection in light of the Covid-19 pandemic, by conducting an in-depth study of the now postponed Indian census 2021.

Keywords: Census, India, data, Sustainable Development Goals, SDGs

OP 127

Microaggressions in the Workplace: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis**Hasiba Salihi and Dr. Sandeep Singh****Research Scholar, Department of Management, Shoolini University**

Background: The mission statements of many of organizations include declarations promoting diversity and inclusiveness. To make the transition from ideology to practice, we must consciously create a space to empower underrepresented communities (Avant & Davis, 2018) It is crucial to understand these negative behaviours and effectively manage them. Microaggressions are subtle insults, invalidations, or slights against marginalized persons. Microaggressions degrade quality of life and reinforce negative preconceptions about people with disabilities, people of colour, sexual minorities, gender, religion, and other oppressed groups. The purpose of the present study is to provide a comprehensive summary of micro-aggressive behaviours experienced at workplace.

Method: The author searched PubMed Collection databases for "microaggression at workplace," which yielded 84 results. Filtering Full text, Free Full text from 2009 to 2023 produced 33 results. After reading complete text, only 31 papers were left for final review. The most used methodologies in the papers include systematic reviews, literature reviews, descriptive studies, and research articles.

Result: The literature study examined 31 articles that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this review. These articles focused on healthcare workplaces. Most studies were conducted in the United States, with the remainder conducted in the United Kingdom, Canada, and Germany. Result showed that microaggressions experienced by healthcare providers at workplace. The papers included a range of healthcare professionals ranging from nurses, physicians, onycholysis, Orthopaedics, Women Coaches, etc.

Discussion: The findings show that individuals can be targeted by microaggressions based on a variety of differences. These differences can include a person's sexual orientation, race or ethnicity, gender, religion, or personal characteristics. Microaggressions frequently occur in the

context of healthcare settings. Discrimination in the workplace is still an obstacle to workforce diversity and inclusion and it has negative health and organizational impact.

OP 128

Taxonomic studies of some genera of subfamily Entedoninae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Eulophidae)**Neha Parveen^{1*} and Shahid Bin Zeya²****Department of Zoology Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202002, India**

Abstract: Members of the family Eulophidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) are cosmopolitan in distribution and occur in almost all terrestrial ecosystems. Most of the species of eulophids are entomophagous in nature and a few species are phytophagous, including gall inducers. The entomophagous species may be endoparasitic or ectoparasitic in behavior. Most species of the family are primary parasitoids of concealed larvae particularly leaf-mining Lepidoptera, Diptera, Hymenoptera, and Coleoptera. Many of the genera seem to have quite well-defined host ranges. Most Entedon species attack phytophagous beetles; *Chrysocharis* species parasitize lepidopterous, dipterous and hymenopterous leaf miners; *Omphale* species attack cecidomyiid larvae (Diptera). Entedoninae is currently represented by 33 genera with more than 1200 species from the world. And, the Indian fauna of the subfamily Entedoninae contains 21 genera and 86 species. It is to note that success of any biological control programme is primarily based on the correct identification of parasitoids and their hosts both at generic and species level prior to use them for any biological control programme.

Keywords: Hymenoptera, Chalcidoidea, Eulophidae, Entedoninae,

OP 129

Online Education: Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Teachers with Visual Disability**Meenakshi Verma****Research Scholar, University of Delhi**

Abstract: Education is a pre-condition to impart knowledge and to develop character traits and skills. In the wake of Covid-19 pandemic, to curb the spread of illness, schools and other educational institutes were closed temporarily. To minimize the loss of education, Government of India in March 2020 announced the shift of physical mode of education to online alternate mode of education. The alternative mode i.e. online education is a form of education which is delivered through digital platforms like Zoom, MStears, Google Classrooms, WhatsApp etc. It also requires the help of good electronic devices like computers, laptops, mobile phones and the uninterrupted services of internet. Online Education, which was far from imagination before the pandemic, has now gained importance and impetus. It comes with its own advantages and disadvantages. The various advantages of online mode include the creativity of learning through videos and illustrations, easy access and swift transfer of e-learning material, and learning at individual pace outside the institutional boundaries. These advantages can be availed only when the person has technological resources and computer skills. This is particularly relevant for persons with visual disability. Before the pandemic, majority of them were neither trained in computer skills nor were equipped with electronic devices. Under such circumstances, they faced immense challenges. This paper seeks to explore the efficacy of teaching and learning through online modes with special reference to persons with visual disability.

Keywords: Online Education, Covid-19, Visual Disability, Technology

OP 130

Post-Decisional Dissonance among Young Adults**Poonam Patel****Research Scholar, Sardar Patel University, Anand**

Abstract: The purpose of the experiment was to study post decision dissonance amongst people regarding their desirability and undesirability towards home appliances. A total of 31 students, male and female, between the ages of 20 and 30, were chosen as the sample for the experiment. For the experiment's execution, paper and a pencil or pen were utilized along with a within-group design. The paired sample t-test was employed for statistical analysis. The outcome demonstrates that consumers experience post-decisional dissonance more frequently for undesired home appliances than for desirable home equipment. One of the drawbacks of investigating cognitive dissonance is that, due to the complexity of the experimental adjustments and the ambiguity of the major variables, it is sometimes impossible to draw any definitive conclusions from the data. The findings can help marketers embrace effective historical techniques that have reduced cognitive dissonance. Keywords: Cognitive Dissonance, Decision Making, Post Decisional Dissonance.

OP 131

Design and Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Derivatives having Pyrrole moiety**Prakash, R. N. Singh* and Poonam Rawat****Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow – 226007**

Abstract: The worldwide development of antimicrobial resistance forces scientists to search for new compounds to which microbes would be sensitive. Many new structures contain the 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring, which have shown various antimicrobial activity have been reported in the literature, The presence of the 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring affects the physicochemical and pharmacokinetic properties of the entire compound. The 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring has aroused interest in medicinal chemistry as a bioisostere and oxadiazole ring is used also as a significant part of the pharmacophore which is capable of binding to a ligand. These features of the 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring have resulted in a wide variety of pharmaceutical applications of these molecule. As part of the study of pyrrole containing biheterocyclic derivatives we have synthesized different 1,3,4 oxadiazole derivatives have been synthesized using cyclization of pyrrolyl hydrazide-hydrazone intermediates in the presence of selected reagents. This work deals with structural clarification, NLO analysis and antimicrobial evaluation of synthesized compounds. The structures of the pyrrole-azole derivatives were confirmed by modern spectroscopic methods. All quantum chemical calculations have been performed by density functional theory (DFT), using B3LYP functional and 6-311++G(d, p) as basis set. The calculated data corroborate well with the experimental data. The binding energies of dimer are found 12.75 , 12.57 kcal/mol after basis set superposition error. All compounds have been screened against microbes and exhibited good antimicrobial activity.

Keywords: Pyrrole, 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring , Spectroscopy, NLO

OP 132

Photophysical Properties, Effect of Substituents and Solvent on the Nature of the Transition of Benzimidazole Derivatives**Anant Ram, R.N. Singh* and Poonam Rawat****Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow 226 007, India**

Abstract: Stimuli-sensitive materials have wide applications in biosensing and biomedical diagnostics. Nitrogen-containing heterocycles are fundamental targets in the pharmaceutical industry as well as in materials science. Benzimidazoles and their derivatives have attracted much interest due to their outstanding physiological and biological properties. An efficient one-pot, two-step procedure has been successfully applied for the synthesis of a series of benzimidazole derivatives. The benzimidazoles contain a phenyl ring fused to an imidazole ring. Benzimidazole and their derivatives have diverse applications in coordination chemistry, photophysics, photochemistry and bioinorganic chemistry. A lot of physiologically active natural and synthetic compounds containing benzimidazole moieties possess wide spectrum of biological activity. These properties of benzimidazoles are due to their propensity to form coordination compounds when interacting with metal ions. In this study, novel benzimidazole derivatives synthesized and characterized by FT-IR, UV-Vis, $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ Mass spectrometry and elemental analysis. The photoluminescent properties benzimidazole derivatives were investigated. In this regard studies in the field of synthesis, structure and investigation of properties of benzimidazole derivatives. The photophysical characteristics of benzimidazole and their derivatives are evaluated to determine the nature of the transitions occurring and how the excited states interact. On the basis of the fluorescence and phosphorescence energies, quantum yields, and lifetimes, these benzimidazole derivatives appear to be excited to a manifold of singlet states. Which excited state predominates, either $\pi - \pi^*$ or charge transfer, depends on the side-chain substituent, solvent system, pH, and temperature. The relationship between the synthesized compounds' absorption, and fluorescence spectra with molecular structures has been investigated with experimental data and theoretical calculations.

Keywords: Biosensing, Biomedical, Benzimidazole, photoluminescent

OP 133

Transcriptome-Based Identification of Genes Responding to the Organophosphate Pesticide Acephate in *Drosophila melanogaster* (Miegen, 1830)**Rahila, K* and Y. Shibu Vardhanan******Biochemistry & Toxicology Division, Department of Zoology, University of Calicut – 673 635**

Abstract: Since many years ago, acephate, an organophosphate pesticide, has been used extensively to manage insect pests in agricultural areas. Acephate inhibits acetylcholine esterase to produce its deleterious effects (AChE). We used the *Drosophila melanogaster* model to comprehend the general molecular processes underlying acephate toxicity. *D. melanogaster* eggs were exposed to acephate, and third-instar larvae were examined for developmental anomalies and subjected to whole transcriptome sequencing. 13281 differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were discovered by whole transcriptome analysis, with 2031 and 1812 genes substantially undergoing up- and down-regulation, respectively. We found that 1030 genes expressed differently in exposed animals compared to controls. Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway analysis revealed significant enrichment of metabolic pathways, Toll and imd signaling pathway, purine metabolism, lipid metabolism, drug metabolism—other enzymes, and insect hormone biosynthesis. Together, these studies not only describe the harmful effects acephate has on the organism but also shed light on any potential genetic changes that may be causing these effects, which may have for higher species.

Keywords: pesticide toxicity, acephate, transcriptomics analysis, genes, *Drosophila melanogaster*.

OP 134

Exploring Banking Efficiency of Public and Private Sector Banks in India using DEA**Dr. Bhuvana Venkatraman¹ and Vidya Raisagar²**¹Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, 495001²Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, 495001

Abstract: Several reforms have been made over a period to ensure a strong, healthy, and resilient banking structure in India. At present, both public and private sector banks are vital components in the financial architecture of India. It becomes necessary to measure the efficiency of these banks and compare the significant results. The study aims to measure the efficiency of Public and Private Sector banks in India. This paper is unique in the sense that it is based on a non-parametric approach, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) which measures the relative efficiency of banks. The present study covers a period of six years i. e. from 2016-17 to 2021-22. The top five banks from both sectors i. e. Public and Private, have been selected on the basis of market capitalization. The results indicate that the State Bank of India, Punjab National Bank, and Bank of Baroda from Public sector Banks have been found efficient under both CCR and BCC Models. In the case of Private Sector Banks, ICICI Bank, and Kotak Mahindra Bank have been discovered efficient under CCR and BCC Models.

Keywords: Public sector Banks, Private sector Banks, Efficiency, CCR, BCC model.

OP 135

A cross sectional study on effect of glycaemic status and duration of type II diabetes mellitus on the pulmonary function.**M. Praveena¹ and K. ThamaraiSelvi^{2*}**¹Department of Physiology, Trichy SRMMCH&RC, Irungalur, Trichy – 621105²Department of Physiology, SRMMCH&RC, SRM Institute of Science & Technology, Kattankulathur – 603203

Background: Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder with multifactorial etiology. Type 2 diabetes (T2DM) occurs due to inadequate insulin secretion and resistance to insulin action. In India, the burden of diabetes expected to rise to over 134 million by 2045 in India. Pulmonary complications of diabetes mellitus have been poorly categorized. The duration of diabetes and glycaemic status has shown marked emphasis on functions of the lungs. The aim of our study was to enlighten the spirometric pulmonary function changes in relation to glycaemic status and duration in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients.

Materials and Methods: This is a cross-sectional study involving 140 type 2 diabetes mellitus patients. The study participants were subjected to cosmed computerized spirometer to assess pulmonary function tests. The data obtained was analysed using unpaired student's 't' test and to find the association, Pearson's correlation test was used. The pulmonary function tests were compared with duration of diabetes by ANOVA test. The p value < 0.05 was taken as level of statistical significance.

Results: The findings of our study revealed that there was a statistically significant reduction in mean values of FVC, FEV1, PEF, MIP, MEP and raised FEV1% among type 2 diabetic patients with poor glycaemic control and long duration of diabetes in comparison to subjects with good glycaemic control and relatively short duration of diabetes. Also, there was a statistically significant negative linear correlation between FVC, FEV1, PEF, MIP and glycaemic status (p<0.05). The study findings suggest that there is restrictive pattern of pulmonary impairment among the type 2 diabetes mellitus patients.

Conclusion: The development of pulmonary impairment among the type 2 diabetes mellitus patients is strongly associated with poor glycaemic control and long duration of diabetes. Therefore, periodic assessment of lung function by spirometry tests and intensive glycaemic

control can avert or delay the hyperglycaemia induced progressive lung damage in diabetic individuals.

Keywords: T2DM, PFT, Glycaemic status, FVC, FEV1, FEV1%, PEF.

OP 136

Studying the impact of the capping agents on the surface modifications of ZnO Nanoparticles by Chemical Method**Kaneez Fatima, Atika Farhi and Farha Firdaus****Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh**

Abstract: In the present study, we have undertaken the examinations of ZnO nanoparticles to study their optical properties and nanostructure determination by using different capping agent. Nanoscale materials find use in different areas such as electronic, magnetic and optoelectronic, biomedical, cosmetic, pharmaceutical, energy, environmental, catalytic and materials applications. ZnO is an environmental friendly material which is highly desirable especially for renewable energy and biological applications and extensively used in a wide variety of commercial products such as sunscreens, textiles and paints. ZnO nanoparticles are not stable when dispersed in water therefore several modifying agents i.e. capping agent are used to increase the stability of ZnO nanoparticles. Capping agents are used as stabilisers that inhibit the over-growth of nanoparticles and prevent their aggregation in colloidal synthesis. The uncapped and capped ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized by chemical method i.e. sol-gel process by reacting Zinc Nitrate with KOH in deionized water at 50°C-70°C. The capping agents such as Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA), Triethanolamine (TEA) and Tetraethylammonium Bromide (TEABr) are used as capping agents to control the size and morphology of the ZnO Nanoparticles and it will be characterized by various techniques like Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), UV-VIS spectroscopy which tells about the size and morphological changes of ZnO nanoparticles. The wurtzite structure of synthesized ZnO nanoparticles was confirmed by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) spectra. FTIR (Fourier transform infrared) spectra tells about the presence of capping agent. The morphology of the synthesized nanoparticles was changed with capping agents according to their different functional group.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Capping Agents, Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA), Triethanolamine (TEA), Tetraethylammonium Bromide (TEABr).

OP 137

**Cardio-Pulmonary Dysfunction in Coal Miners with Advanced Fibrotic Lung Impairment-
A Retrospective Study****¹Julekha Sultana, ²Alak K Syamal and ³Suwendu Ghosh****^{1,2,3}Department of Physiology, Hooghly Mohsin College, University of Burdwan****Email: sultanajulekha@gmail.com****ABSTRACT**

One of the prevalent occupational health hazards in opencast and underground coal miners are lung diseases caused by dust called coal miner's dust lung diseases. Various respiratory afflicts associated with disease are cough, fever, bronchitis, wheezing, and phlegm as reported.

A cross sectional study was carried out on 146 opencast coal miners and 123 non exposed office staffs in coal mine of west Bengal. The consent of subjects was taken before conducting the work. Stratified random sampling including every fifth individual was considered. Computerized spirometry was used to conduct the Pulmonary function test. Data analysis was done by SPSS statistical software. The level of significance was determined by performing Students t test.

The results showed pulmonary alterations related with increased period of exposure. Obstructive form was found in 33% individuals, restrictive impairment was seen in 56% and Remaining 11% showed mixed type of alterations. Radiological studies revealed nodular lung disease with 26% of individuals having small opacities and 28% having large opacities in their lungs especially in people who were exposed to coal dust for more than 15 years maximally within the age group of 45-55 years. These people also had altered cardio-thoracic ratio.

Pulmonary fibrosis is also predominant in open cast coal miners which may be related to the augmented cardio-thoracic ratio. These findings not only showed respiratory morbidity but also cardiac stress due to hypertrophy of the heart. Thus, fibrotic lung disease along with cardiac morbidity may be interpreted as an outcome of long-term coal dust exposure in open cast miners.

Keywords: Open Cast Coal Miners, Nodular Lung, Cardio-Thoracic Ratio.

OP 138

Investigation of anticancer and antioxidant efficacy of *Calocybe indica* P&C along with quantitative profiling of bioactive compounds**Hiral Chaudhary¹, Nainesh R. Modi¹ and Rakesh Raval²**¹Department of Botany, Bioinformatics and Climate Change Impacts Management, School of Science, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India, 380009²Department of Life sciences, School of Science, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India, 380009

Abstract: Edible mushrooms have been used through the ages, as a natural source of medicaments for various cancers. Lung cancer is one of the most common cancers that responsible for high death rate worldwide. Hence, this study aimed to identify and explore anticancer potency of an edible mushroom *Calocybe indica* P&C using the human adenocarcinoma cell line A549. The anticancer effect of methanolic and chloroform extracts was evaluated by MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay. Additionally, free radical scavenging activity was measured by 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) methods. Furthermore, preliminary screening, total phenol, flavonoid, tannin and glycoside content of extracts were estimated to explore the bioactive constituents present in fruiting body. Total alkaloid content was also evaluated from the powder of fruiting body. The results indicated that methanolic extract revealed higher phenolic content with strong antioxidant and anticancer activities than chloroform. However, chloroform extract exhibited higher content of flavonoids, tannins and glycosides than methanol. The powder of fruiting body possesses a significant amount of alkaloid content. The data revealed that *Calocybe indica* P&C can act as a potential drug candidate in the treatment of lung cancer for future aspects in pharmaceuticals.

Keywords: *Calocybe Indica* P&C, antioxidant activity, anticancer activity, qualitative and quantitative analysis

OP 139

**State-building Process in Afghanistan: Issues and Challenges with Special Reference to
2005-2015****Basir Ahmad Sharifi¹ and Dr. C.M. Raj Praveen²****¹Ph.D. Scholar at the Department of Political Science,
Mangalore University, India****²Associate Professor, Department of Political Science,
Mangalore University, India**

Abstract: State-building is the process of establishing and strengthening the institutions essential for the smooth functioning of government and necessary for economic, social, and political development. The state-building process in Afghanistan has been severely affected by war, terrorism, ethnic and religious conflicts, tyranny, and dictatorships. After 9/11, Afghanistan received considerable money from The United States of America, the European Union, and several other regional states and international organizations in order to ginger up the state-building process and to re-establish security, rebuild government institutions, and reconstitute legitimacy in the country. Nonetheless, Afghanistan remains one of the poorest countries on earth. It is often cited as a failed state. the Bonn agreement in 2001 provided an opportunity for state-building issues in Afghanistan. The present study has two objectives: first, to assess the state-building process in Afghanistan initiated after post 9/11, and second, to identify and analyse the significant issues and challenges of the state-building process with special reference to 2005-2015. The paper employs a qualitative method as a strategy for data analysis.

Keywords: Afghanistan and state-building process, Security, Corruption, Warlords.

OP 140

Synthesis and characterization of bismuth nanoparticles using *Endocomia macrocoma* leaves and screening for its antibacterial, antioxidant activity**S. Parashuram and C. M. Kamanavalli*****P. G. Department of Studies in Biochemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad, 580003 India**

Abstract: Nanocrystalline bismuth nanoparticles (Bi NPs) have received great attention in recent years due to their eco-friendly nature and potential energy conversion. The green synthesis of bismuth nanoparticles from *endocomia macrocoma* leaves and the evaluation of physicochemical and structural properties through characterization using various analytical and/or spectroscopic methods. The biogenic synthesis of Bi NPs is characterized by UV-visible spectroscopy, X Ray diffraction (XRD), Dynamic light scattering (DLS), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), and Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with EDS (energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy). TGA and DSC of Bi NPs shows the clear weight loss with respect to temperature and endothermic process respectively. Some phytoconstituents present in the leaves are shown. Synthesized Bi NPs are investigated for antibacterial properties using bacterial strains *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* where gram negative bacteria show better inhibition growth when compared to gram positive and Bi NPs show good antioxidant properties due to presence of secondary metabolites and further utilized for therapeutic applications.

OP 141

Visualisation of early developmental stages of the wandering glider, *Pantala flavescens* (Fabricius, 1798) embryos (*Odonata: Libellulidae*): A future biomarker**Gayathri. M* and Y. Shibu Vardhanan******Biochemistry & Toxicology Division, Department of Zoology, University of Calicut – 673 635**

Abstract: *Pantala flavescens* (Fabricius 1798) (Globe skimmer or wandering glider) is the longest migratory species among dragonfly species and among all known insects. Considering the global distribution and the long-distance migratory capabilities of *P. flavescens*, it is essential to conduct studies regarding the impact of climate change and other environmental stress on their migration and range expansion. Water quality and other environmental factors may influence the egg stage duration of dragonflies. The embryonic development of *Pantala flavescens* is documented for the first time. In contrast to previously reported insect embryonic development, we describe the embryological development of *P. flavescens* in living conditions by focusing on its externally recognizable features, i.e., we conducted the study in a purely non-destructive manner. Females of *Pantala flavescens* were collected from the paddy fields in Palakkad district, Kerala. The eggs of *P. flavescens* were collected in the laboratory using artificially induced oviposition by dipping the tip of the abdomen in water. The eggs are ellipsoid and transparent. The entire embryonic development was completed within six to seven days. Based on the egg's external morphological features, the embryonic development of *P. flavescens* was divided into six stages. We pictured the eggs at successive embryonic developmental stages: covering germband formation, segmentation, blastokinesis, appendage formation, and dorsal closure. The eggs of most Odonate species start to develop in water; thus, the speed of egg development and the hatching success were directly influenced by environmental conditions, especially water quality. These studies on different stages of embryonic development can be helpful in future studies regarding the impacts of pollutants and climate change on the early embryonic development of dragonflies. **Keywords:** Dragonfly; embryology; odonates; wandering glider; *Pantala flavescens*.

OP 142

Influence of Socio-Economic and Socio-Demographic Factors along with Stress Level in Menstrual Characteristics of the Bengali Adolescent Girls of Darjeeling District**Mampi Debnath****Ph. D Scholar, Department of Anthropology****University of North Bengal, Raja Rammohanpur, Darjeeling, WB (734013), India****Abstract**

Background: During the adolescence period girls are experiencing the onset of menarche, a transit from a girl to a woman. In India it is challenging because of the cultural beliefs, traditions, social stigma and taboos. From studies different socio-economic and demographic factors are found to be associated with age at menarche.

Aim: The aim of the present study is to determine the age at menarche in adolescent girls and to assess the relation between stress and menstrual flow along with the influence of socio-economic and socio-demographic factors.

Materials and methods: The present study was cross-sectional in nature and conducted among the Bengali adolescent girls (11-17 years) of two government schools from Matigara block, Darjeeling district. The sample size was 249. For measuring stress a new scale with 16-items was developed by standard method. Statistical analysis was done by using SPSS (v.26).

Result: Mean age at menarche was 12.08 ± 1.11 years and mean duration of blood flow was 5.44 ± 1.5 days. The level of stress among adolescent girls (who attained menarche) was found to be 13.1% for mild, 53.4% for moderate, 31.6% for severe and 1.9% for extreme level. The duration of flow was 59.2% (3-5 days), 38.3% (6-8 days) and 2.4% (9-14 days) respectively.

Conclusion: No significant correlation was found between duration of flow and stress level in the studied girls.

Keywords: Menarche, Stress, Adolescent girls, Socio-economic, Menstrual flow

OP 143

The Effect of Azole Derivatives Bearing Hydrazone Moiety on Anticancer Activity**Amul Darwari, R. N. Singh* and Poonam Rawat****Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow – 226006**

Abstract: Cancer is a major global public health problem and is growing as the leading cause of mortality, accounting for vast morbidity worldwide. It is a malignant disease characterized by rapid and uncontrolled cell proliferation. It is the second leading cause of death globally. In 2018 alone, an estimated 9.6 million deaths occurred due to cancer. Approximately 70% of these deaths occurred in low-and middle-income countries. This work deals with structural clarification and anticancer activity evaluation of synthesized compounds. The structures of the azole derivatives were confirmed by modern spectroscopic methods. All compounds evaluated for their antiproliferative activity against two human cancer cell lines, i.e., HCT-116 (colon), and HL-60 (leukemia) cells. The compounds showed significant cytotoxicity against types of human cancer cell lines. In addition, the molecular docking study has been achieved using cancer cell protein 3QX3.

Keywords: Azole, Spectroscopy, Antiproliferative activity, HCT-116 (colon), HL-60 (leukemia) cells.

OP 144

Plant spacing on the growth and yield, Nitrogen level of the Basmati rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)**Ramu Yadav and Naveen kumar mourya****Department of Agriculture Agronomy, Rama University, Kanpur U.P -20917, India**

Abstract: The experiment was done at the India Rice Research Institute Farm, Kanpur during boro season to determine the critical growth stage on yield reduction and to find out optimum level of nitrogen and to select stress tolerance nitrogen responsive rice variety. The study presents the first experimental evidence of the effects of atmospheric particulate. PB-1509 and among growth stages, it was the highest during the reproductive growth stage the most appropriate level of nitrogen to get maximum paddy yield of rice variety, Super Basmati. Effect of nine different nitrogen levels 0, 60, 80, 100, 120 kg/ha the most appropriate level of nitrogen to get maximum paddy yield of rice variety, Super Basmati. Photoperiod sensitivity is one of the most important character which acts as an indicator to distinguish a basmati variety from nonbasmati variety.

Keywords: Basmati rice, growth and yield, nitrogen level.

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OP 145

Comparison of different DNA and RNA extraction methods to obtain high DNA and RNA from *Cullenia exarillata***Revathy S.¹, Anilkumar S.¹, K.K. Sabu¹ and S. William Decruse¹****¹Biotechnology and Bioinformatics Division, KSCSTE- Jawaharlal Nehru Tropical Botanic Garden and Research Institute, Palode, Thiruvananthapuram, 695562, India**

Abstract: DNA and RNA isolation is a standard procedure used in all molecular biology laboratories. The plant or plant material will define whether this approach needs to be modified or go through additional steps. Establishing a standard protocol for isolating DNA and RNA from a specific plant is essential for further experiments. *Cullenia exarillata* is an endemic canopy tree found in the western Ghats' evergreen forests. When in blooming, the tree serves as a hotbed of activity and an essential resource for several species of arboreal mammals, including the endangered lion-tailed macaque. The tree also provides food for a variety of animal species, making it an essential food source from August to November, when there is a food crisis in the region. For the tree's long-term survival, it is imperative that it be protected, and research into the genetic diversity of *Cullenia* populations will help in understanding the gene flow and in the implementation of preventative measures for inbreeding depression as well as promote gene flow in highly endemic and threatened animals. Consequently, the DNA and RNA isolation protocols were optimised to be compatible with plant species from various genera, making them appropriate for further work on diversity study.

The presence of significant polysaccharide and phenolic chemical contamination frequently affects the isolation of high-quality DNA and RNA from tree species. Total RNA and DNA from *Cullenia* leaf samples were obtained using modified CTAB techniques. For generating new molecular and biotechnological methods that emphasize conservation of the tree, isolation of good quality RNA and DNA is important. Here, we compared various DNA and RNA extraction methods to determine which was most effective for *Cullenia* leaves. The results showed that total RNA and DNA are of good quality and are not degraded by CTAB. The NanoDrop and **Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer's** guarantee the high purity of the nucleic acids produced by these methods. Additionally, agarose gel electrophoresis revealed distinct bands. The extracted RNA and DNA were suitable for further analysis. The purity and amplification of the collected DNA and RNA

can be verified through further investigation. This method provides an improved pathway for the isolation of DNA and RNA from *Cullenia* using modern biotechnological approaches, which will be extremely beneficial for future studies on this plant.

Keywords: DNA; RNA; CTAB; *Cullenia*.

OP 146

Inhibition of colorectal cancer cell (HCT-116) proliferation through an apoptosis dependent pathway with methanolic leaf extract of *Olea dioica* and in vitro cytotoxicity**Srinivasa K and Manjula Shantaram*****Department of Studies & Research in Biochemistry, Mangalore University, Jnana Kaveri, P. G. Centre, Chikka Aluvara, Kodagu, 571 232**

Abstract: Apoptosis (programmed cell death) is a type of active physiological suicide that occurs naturally during development and ageing as a homeostatic mechanism to keep the stability of cell population in tissues. Apoptosis is distinguished by distinct morphological and biochemical characteristics such as cell shrinkage, membrane blebbing, chromatin condensation, and formation of apoptotic bodies. The aim of this investigation was to check *in vitro* cytotoxic activity and the mechanism of cell death of crude methanolic extracts prepared from *Olea dioica* leaves and the isolated secondary metabolites. The MTT assay was used to test the cytotoxicity and viability of methanolic extract against HCT116 cell line. The apoptotic assays were performed using the Annexin/PI method, as well as DNA fragmentation (TUNEL) assays using flow cytometry. When compared to a chemotherapeutic anticancer drug, Quercetin, the extract decreased cell viability, inhibited cell growth, and induced cell death in a time- and dose-dependent manner in HCT-116 cells ($IC_{50} = 81.05 \pm 9.4 \mu\text{g/mL}$). According to flow cytometric and molecular marker analyses, the extract caused early and late apoptosis in the tested colon cancer cells, as well as cell death via DNA damage. The study demonstrated that apoptosis was the primary mechanism of cell death. As a result, the methanolic extract of *O. dioica* was discovered to inhibit colorectal cancer cell proliferation, presumably through an apoptosis-dependent pathway.

Keywords: Apoptosis, Annexin/PI staining, TUNNEL assay, DNA damage, colorectal cancer (HCT116)

OP 147

The Applications of Magneto Plasmonic for Advance Technology**Daya Shanker, Rashimi Yadav***

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Abstract: The Magneto-Plasmonic emerged from the interaction between magnetic-optical phenomena found in the magnetic material and plasmonic. This interaction occurs in various structures of the nanoparticle, thin film material which enhances magnetic optical properties and plasmonic properties at a high frequency that are widely useful in fields like sensing, telecommunications, nanomedicine, magnetic, and spintronic devices. The author will discuss the challenges of Magneto-plasmonic for future development of technology and investigate the low efficiency and low-frequency range of plasmonic devices for new materials and fabrication technologies in the magneto-plasmonic field. This is a rapidly growing field with many exciting developments and a wide range of applications. The interaction between plasmons and magnetic can be used in light-matter interaction in optical devices and here use of the magnetic field to control the properties of plasmonic in optoelectronics and telecommunications. This study introduced the basic concepts of plasmonic materials and magneto-optical material at the surface of materials in various ways to influence the surface plasmon resonance to create hybrid systems as well as to achieve the balance between surface plasmon properties and magneto-optical properties of systems and to enhance widely potential in magneto-plasmonic properties led to the development of new systems with various characteristics.

Keywords: Magneto-Plasmonic, Surface Plasmon Resonance, Plasmons, and light-matter interaction.

OP 148

Identification of monogeneans parasite from *Cyprinus carpio* and *Oreochromis niloticus* in the Ghaghra River, Uttar Pradesh**Priyanka Rawat* and Amit Tripathi****Department of Zoology, University of Lucknow 226 007, UP, India**

Abstract: Monogenean parasites are important ectoparasites of fish. Found few monogenean parasite of Cyprinidae family in fishes from exotic fish species, viz. *Cyprinus carpio* and *Oreochromis niloticus* (a new exotic species in India). *Dactylogyrus minutus* from the gills of *Cyprinus carpio* collected in the river Ghaghara (Site: Bahraich, & Barabanki). A parasite study was conducted from March 2022 to Feb 2023 to highlight the distribution of gill monogenean parasites from *Oreochromis niloticus*. The study revealed the presence of species of monogeneans: *Cichlidogyrus sclerosus*. These species showed an aggregate pattern within the host population. Here, we review recent research for fish parasite discovery and taxonomy. Our focus to find: find new parasite species targeted at geographical hotspots of exotic fish biodiversity, Morphological identification of monogenean parasite of Cyprinidae family in the targeted area, Prevalence and intensity of the infection of these parasites were highest in the long rainy season and lowest in the dry season. We also explore the far-reaching implications of recent research on monogenean parasite for taxonomy. We end with recommendations aimed at maximizing the found information per fish sacrificed and devoted time and money into research on fish parasite biodiversity.

Keywords: Exotic fish, Monogenean parasite, biodiversity, Species descriptions, Taxonomy.

OP 149

Preparation of Activated carbon for removal of organic contaminants from wastewater**Vinay Rawat and Pankaj Chamoli*****Department of Physics, Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Dehradun-248001, Uttarakhand, India**

Abstract: Industrial developments have increased water contamination globally which is seriously affecting the aquatic system. Numerous industries including packaging, fertilizer, pesticides, gasoline, and oil transportation are dumping tons of contaminated trash, possessing a serious threat to both the environment and aquatic ecosystem. A quick removal of such contaminants is a need of the day. Apart from other techniques, adsorption methods are being widely used for the removal of contaminants due to its simple use ecofriendly nature. The adsorbents based on activated carbon (ACs) are shown to their potency owing their versatility and nontoxicity. The present work is an attempt to prepare the ACs from raw charcoal at low temperature. Synthesized ACs have been characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Visible spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Surface morphology reveals that ACs have large numbers of pores which trigger the adsorption. Then, prepared ACs are examined for the removal of Methylene blue (MB) organic dye at low concentration 0.1mg/ml. Result shows that the prepared ACs have shown excellent removal efficiency against MB (1mg/L) concentration.

Keywords: Contamination, activated carbon, adsorption, Methylene blue

OP 150

Ploidy Analysis and Estimation of β -Asarone Content in *Acorus calamus* Linn., from Tamil Nadu Regions of the Western Ghats**¹Shibin Felix P*, ²Radha RK and ³S William Decruse****¹Department of Biotechnology, University of Kerala, Karyavattom, Kerala 695581****^{1,2,3}Biotechnology & Bioinformatics Division, Jawaharlal Nehru Tropical Botanic Garden & Research Institute, Palode, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala 695562**

Abstract: *Acorus calamus* Linn., (Acoraceae) commonly known as Sweet flag is a semi-aquatic, perennial, aromatic herb with creeping rhizomes. The plant possesses antimicrobial properties, antiulcer activity, antiviral properties and insecticidal properties. The rhizome is emetic, laxative and diuretic. The rhizome is used in the treatment of dysentery, dyspepsia, intestinal worms, cough and fever. Furthermore, the rhizome infusion is also used as central nervous system relaxant, appetite stimulant, anthelmintic, vermifuge, antibacterial reported to be used as an aromatic stimulant, expectorant, carminative, anti-spasmodic, agent, sedative, analgesic and contraceptive. Asarones (α , β & γ) has been reported to be the major bioactive constituent of the volatile calamus oil of which α and β asarone are mostly responsible for the bioactivity. The concentration of asarone in calamus oil depends on the part of the plant used for the extraction of the oil and the ploidy of the plant. *Acorus* ecotypes with low concentrations of β -asarone can be used for medicinal purposes due to the carcinogenic effect of β -asarone. In the present study fresh rhizomes of 9 different accessions of *A. calamus* were collected from Tamil Nadu regions of Western Ghats. Flow cytometric analysis showed that all analysed accessions are diploid in nature with varying β -asarone concentration from the range of 6.99mg/g to 63.77mg/g. The lowest content was observed in the accession collected from Indhunagar, Ooty region with a concentration of 6.99mg/g followed by accession collected from Thalaikundwa, Ooty region (7.09 mg/g) and highest β -asarone content was observed in the sample collected from Prakashapuram, Kodaikanal region with a concentration of 63.77mg/g.

Keywords: *Acorus calamus*, β -asarone, Flow cytometry, HPLC.

OP 151

**Natural History of tube-dwelling spider genus *Ariadna vansda* (Araneae: Segestriidae)
(Siliwal, Yadav & Kumar, 2017) from Vansda National Park, Gujarat, India**

Dr. Archana Yadav and Prof. Dolly Kumar

**Division of Entomology, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, The Maharaja Sayajirao
University of Vadodara, Gujarat**

Abstract: The tube-dwelling spider family Segestriidae is represented in India by only two species, *Ariadna nebulosa* Simon, 1906 and *Segestria inda* Simon, 1906. Both species are known only from their type localities. For about 96 years, there has been no report of these spiders from the Indian subcontinent. Here, we describe new species *Ariadna vansda* (Siliwal, Yadav & Kumar, 2017) from Vansda National Park, Gujarat, India. In the present study we have reported the habitat preference and burrow characteristics of *Ariadna vansda*. The study on ecology, biology and behavior of this spider is poorly documented. We have observed different habitats of spider and found it makes patchy distribution throughout the area. Spider prefers to make trapdoor mostly in steep slop area. The burrows diameter, depth and lid thickness were independent of habitat type.

OP 152

Effect of drought stress on the physiological, biochemical property, callusing and shooting frequency on medicinal plant *Desmodium gangeticum* (L.) DC**Km Babita¹, Alok Ranjan¹ and Malvika Srivastava²**¹**Mahatma Gandhi Post Graduate, College, Gorakhpur**²**Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur**

Abstract: *Desmodium gangeticum* constitutes bioactive compounds like alkaloids, flavones and isoflavones, glycosides, phenolic acid and other secondary metabolites. *Desmodium gangeticum* commonly known as Salparni. Salparni has been used in traditional medicine for centuries. It represents a broad spectrum of therapeutics for various diseases like anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-leishmanial, anti-ulcer, anti-diabetic, and immunomodulatory. It is also implicated in protecting the heart, liver, and kidney and is involved in wound healing.

Global warming and environmental pollution lead to various biotic and abiotic stresses on the plants. In this stress, drought is essential abiotic stress that alters plant growth, development, and reproduction. Drought or soil water deficit relates to low water availability. It is multidimensional stress and causes changes in morpho-physiological, biochemical and molecular traits in plant. Drought stress causes a decrease in chlorophyll content due to oxidative stress or may results in pigment photo-oxidation and chlorophyll degradation and an increase in alkaloids contents. In the present study, plants are grown in drought-stress conditions, which is found to shortening the stem length and increase in root length. The Chlorophyll, Carotenoids and water content in leaves also decreases upon drought stress. Under moderate drought stress protein and carbohydrates content increases. Severe drought stress decreases protein and carbohydrate content. Antioxidative properties like catalase and peroxidase activity increases at moderate drought stress. Whereas it decreases significantly during severe drought stress.

In vitro Micropropagation is new age technology to increase yield and conserve endangered plant species. Henceforth, we tested the Callusing and shooting frequency in drought stress plant. The primary data suggest a sharp decrease in the callusing frequency using axillary node explant exposed to drought stress.

Keywords: *Desmodium gangeticum*, Drought stress, Chlorophyll, Antioxidative property, Secondary metabolites, In Vitro micropropagation.

OP 153

Revolutionizing Chronic Myeloid Leukemia Treatment with miR-486-5p Biomarker Insights**Jay Prakash Jha****PhD Scholar, Department of Biochemistry
Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar**

Abstract: The world of medical research is constantly evolving, and the latest breakthrough in the field of cancer treatment is nothing short of revolutionary. Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML) is a type of cancer that affects the blood and bone marrow, and it has been notoriously difficult to treat. However, recent studies have shed light on a potential new biomarker, miR-486-5p, which could lead to a more effective and personalized approach to CML treatment.

Aim: Recent studies have identified miR-486-5p as a potential biomarker for CML treatment and miR-486-5p expression in BCR-ABL1+ve CML K562 cell line.

Results: - After Imatinib exposure, the miR-486-5p expression was significantly upregulated in K562 cells as compared to untreated K562 cells which resulted as p-value = 0.031.

Conclusion: -The discovery of miR-486-5p as a potential biomarker for CML treatment is an exciting development that offers hope to the millions of people around the world who are affected by this disease. While there are still challenges to be addressed, the potential benefits of using miR-486-5p as a biomarker are significant. In the future, we may be able to use biomarkers like miR-486-5p to develop more personalized and effective approaches to cancer treatment, which could have a transformative impact on the lives of patients and their families.

This exciting discovery has the potential to revolutionize the way we approach cancer treatment, and it offers hope to the millions of people around the world who are affected by this devastating disease. In this article, we'll explore the latest research on miR-486-5p biomarker insights and what it means for the future of CML treatment.

Keywords: CML, BCR-ABL1, miR-486-5p expression, K562 cell line.

OP 154

**Rigidoporus vinctus, an endophytic fungus with antioxidant and antimicrobial properties,
from the shoot of *Bambusa tulda*****Karthik. M.B* and Jayashankar. M****Department of Studies and Research in Microbiology, Mangalore University, Post Graduate
Centre, Jnana Kaveri campus, Kodagu, Karnataka, India**

Abstract: The recent exploration and investigation of various plants for bioactive potential has led to the growing interest to explore their endophytes. Microorganisms which colonize in the tissue of host plants are known as Endophytes. Endophytic fungi have been investigated as bio factories of novel bioactive substances. Bamboo shoot are highly nutrient and contains medicinal components, there endophytes are less explored effort was made to isolate endophytic fungi from the shoot. *Rigidoporus vinctus* is a endophytic fungi isolated by edible shoots of *Bambusa tulda*, from Billigirirangana hills, Chamrajanagara, Karnataka. Isolated fungi are identified by 18S rRNA partial gene sequencing method. ITS region obtained is compared with closely related species from NCBI data base. The isolated fungal culture was subjected to mass culture by submerged fermentation method for production of extracellular Bioactive compounds. Water, ethyl acetate, methanol, and chloroform are used for Solvent extraction method. Acquired extract were screened for phytochemicals- Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Saponins, Tannins, Phenols, and Glycosides. Positive extract were analysed for antioxidant activity by DPPH and FRAP assay, Antagonistic activity agar well diffusion assay against clinical pathogens- *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella sonnei*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* obtained from KIMS Madikeri. The obtained sequences of *Rigidoporus vinctus* are submitted to NCBI with accession number ON287260. Phylogenetic tree is constructed using MEGA 11 software. Result showed that *Rigidoporus vinctus* is a potential fungi for production of numerous bioactive compounds. Ethyl acetate is a high efficient solvent for extraction of active compounds then water, methanol, and chloroform. Extracts confirm presence of phenols, alkaloids and flavonoids. Ethyl acetate extract have significant antibacterial and antioxidant capacity. which endorsed *Rigidoporus vinctus* to be a promising candidate for drug development.

Keywords: 18S rRNA sequencing, Bamboo shoot, antioxidant, bioactive compound.

OP 155

Safety and Efficacy of Intermittent Fasting in Type II Diabetes Mellitus Patients on Insulin Therapy**S Emil Sankar¹, P Sahu² and M Balamurali³**¹Postgraduate Resident, Department of Pharmacology, VSSIMSAR, Burla, Odisha²Assistant Professor, ³Senior Resident, Department of General Medicine, VSSIMSAR, Burla, Odisha, 768017**Abstract**

Objectives: To determine the safety and feasibility of 3 non-consecutive days intermittent fasting (IF) per week in type II diabetes mellitus patients already on insulin therapy.

Methodology: Sixty type II diabetes mellitus patients on insulin therapy attending the outpatient unit of department of general medicine at tertiary care research institute in western Odisha were selected as per the inclusion criteria and randomized into two groups; an intermittent fasting group and control group of thirty participants each after obtaining informed written consent from participants and approval of the institutional ethics committee. Dietary counselling along with continuous glucose monitoring was provided for all participants. Primary objective was to determine the change in HbA1c from baseline to 3 months and secondary objective were to determine body weight reduction and reduction in daily insulin dose requirement.

Results: The intermittent fasting group showed a significant reduction in HbA1c along with reduction in daily insulin dose requirement and bodyweight compared with the control group over 3 months study period ($P < 0.05$). No episodes of severe hypoglycaemia were encountered during the study.

Conclusions: Intermittent non-consecutive days fasting can be considered as a safe and reliable method to attain adequate glycaemic control along with significant reduction in total daily insulin dose requirement and body weight in type II diabetes mellitus patients on insulin therapy.

Keywords: Type II diabetes mellitus, insulin, intermittent fasting.

OP 156

Performance and Perception of First Year Medical Students about the Team Based Learning in Physiology**Dr. M. Usha Rani¹ MD and Dr. Sai Shanmukh Vemparala²**¹**Professor and Head, Department of Physiology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam**²**Postgraduate, Department of Physiology I, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam**

Background: The purpose of this study was to examine how first-year MBBS students at Andhra Medical College in Visakhapatnam perceived and performed team-based learning (TBL) when teaching physiology. In order to foster interactive small group learning, TBL, an instructional technique that strongly relies on student-centred small group interaction, is being employed more frequently in medical education.

Methodology: In the study, 100 students took part in a TBL session that adhered to a set procedure that included pre-class preparation, readiness checking, and small group discussion. A questionnaire was used to gauge participants' perceptions of TBL, and individual and group tests, as well as course evaluation results, were used to gauge participants' performance.

Results: According to the findings, 72% of students were able to learn and comprehend the subject matter through TBL, with 80% saying that discussion within the group improved their understanding of the material. According to 61% of students, additional TBL sessions should take the place of lectures. These results were reflected in the scores in test conducted based on multiple choice questions in which 68 students scored more than 65%. And 19 students scored more than 80%

Conclusions: The study's findings support the use of TBL as a valuable teaching tool in conjunction with other teaching approaches since it helped first-year MBBS students with group learning.

Keywords: Team based learning, study methodology, self-learning, student centred, interactive.

OP 157

Tenofovir induced Nephrotoxicity**Aparna Matpathi****Pharma D Intern, CMR College of Pharmacy, Medchal-501401, Hyderabad**

Abstract: Tenofovir is a widely used antiretroviral drug that has revolutionized the treatment of HIV infection. Despite its efficacy, tenofovir has been associated with the development of nephrotoxicity in some patients. The renal toxicity of tenofovir is primarily characterized by proximal tubular dysfunction and acute kidney injury. In severe cases, this can lead to chronic kidney disease and end-stage renal disease, which are associated with significant morbidity and mortality.

The pathophysiology of tenofovir-induced nephrotoxicity is multifactorial and is thought to involve multiple mechanisms, including mitochondrial toxicity, oxidative stress, and inflammation. These mechanisms can lead to cellular injury and death, resulting in the loss of renal function.

Early detection and management of tenofovir-induced nephrotoxicity are critical to prevent irreversible kidney damage. Patients receiving tenofovir therapy should undergo regular monitoring of renal function, including serum creatinine and estimated glomerular filtration rate. In some cases, it may be necessary to discontinue tenofovir therapy and switch to an alternative antiretroviral agent.

In conclusion, tenofovir-induced nephrotoxicity is an important complication of tenofovir therapy that can have significant clinical implications. A thorough understanding of the pathophysiology, clinical features, and management of this condition is essential for healthcare providers who care for patients receiving tenofovir therapy.

Keywords: Tenofovir, nephrotoxicity, mitochondria, proximal tubular cells, serum uric acid levels.

OP 158

Utility of Principles of Ayurveda in Myocardial Reperfusion Injury: A Review**¹Dr. Reshmi. A. S, ²Dr. Mini. V. G, ³Dr. Giri.P. V MD (AY), PhD****¹PG Scholar, Department of Kayachikitsa, Govt.Ayurveda College, Thiruvananthapuram, 695001****²PhD Scholar, Department of Kayachikitsa, Vaidyaratnam Ayurveda College, Ollur, Thrissur, 680306****³Professor and HOD, Department of Kayachikitsa, Vaidyaratnam Ayurveda College, Ollur, Thrissur, 680306**

Abstract: The consequences of coronary artery disease are attributable to the detrimental effects of acute myocardial reperfusion injury typically seen in patients with ST elevation myocardial infarction. It is thought to be mediated by critical factors namely free radicals, neutrophilendothelium interactions, apoptosis, altered NO formation and intracellular Ca^{2+} overload resulting in a series of biochemical and metabolic transformations within the myocardium. Cells constantly generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) during aerobic metabolism. Oxidative stress occurs in cells when ROS overwhelms the cell's natural antioxidant defences. The corner-stone of therapy for preventing acute MI and limiting the size of infarct is timely reperfusion with interventions such as thrombolysis or primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PPCI). However, the process of myocardial reperfusion can itself induce further cardiomyocyte degeneration and death. Therefore, reducing oxidative stress level, free radical scavenging and improving regeneration potential will be an effective strategy for cessation of adverse effects. As there is always a preference for natural antioxidants rather than synthetic one, it is an important matter of research for evaluating its activity prior to patient administration. There arises the utility of Ayurveda principles. Many modalities are told in Ayurveda classical texts that have to be explored in an evidence-based way. Therapeutic formulations particularly rasayana would be of great importance as it can combat with tissue degeneration. Also, it acts as antioxidant which can prevent many diseases.

Keywords: Myocardial Reperfusion Injury, Apoptosis, Necroptosis, Inflammation, Hridroga, Rasayana.

OP 159

Nanomaterials: Synthesis and Applications**Vaibhav Mishra****Department of Physics****Dr. Shakuntala Misra National Rehabilitation University, Lucknow 226017**

Abstract: Nanomaterials have emerged as an amazing class of materials that consists of a broad spectrum of examples with at least one dimension in the range of 1 to 100 nm. Exceptionally high surface areas can be achieved through the rational design of nanomaterials. Nanomaterials can be produced with outstanding magnetic, electrical, optical, mechanical, and catalytic properties that are substantially different from their bulk counterparts. The nanomaterial properties can be tuned as desired via precisely controlling the size, shape, synthesis conditions, and appropriate functionalization. This review discusses a brief history of nanomaterials and their use throughout history to trigger advances in nanotechnology development. In particular, we describe and define various terms relating to nanomaterials. Various nanomaterial synthesis methods, including top-down and bottom-up approaches, are discussed. The unique features of nanomaterials are highlighted throughout the review. This review describes advances in nanomaterials, specifically fullerenes, carbon nanotubes, graphene, carbon quantum dots, nanodiamonds, carbon nano horns, nanoporous materials, core–shell nanoparticles, silicene, antimonene, MXenes, 2D MOF nanosheets, boron nitride nanosheets, layered double hydroxides, and metal-based nanomaterials. Nanotechnology is an excellent example of an emerging technology, offering engineered nanomaterials with the great potential for producing products with substantially improved performances. Currently, nanomaterials find commercial roles in scratch-free paints, surface coatings, electronics, cosmetics, environmental remediation, sports equipment, sensors, and energy-storage devices. This review attempts to provide information in a single platform about the basic concepts, advances, and trends relating to nanomaterials via covering the related information and discussing synthesis methods, properties, and possible opportunities relating to the broad and fascinating area of nanomaterials. It is not easy to cover all the literature related to nanomaterials, but important papers from history and the current literature are discussed in this review.

OP 160

Role of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Assessment of Valvular Heart Disease**Utkarsh Saxena****Department of Physics****Dr.Shakuntala Mishra National Rehabilitation University****Lucknow, UP 226017**

Abstract: MRI is already an established diagnostic modality for assessing valvular heart disease although it is not usually used as the initial non-invasive test. The preferred diagnostic modality for valvular disorder is currently echocardiography. However, MRI has been offered as a good alternative test in the event of inconclusive echocardiography results. During the course of valvular disorder in heart, the valve orifice area decreases and the pressure gradient across the diseased valve increases. Valvular orifice area is the major core indicator for valvular stenosis severity grading. Compared with valvular regurgitation, assessment with MRI for valvular stenosis is less complicated. The aim of this article is to detail the MRI techniques in assessing native and prosthetic heart valve stenosis.

The stenosis condition produces volume and pressure overloading to the cardiac chamber upstream of the diseased valve. An increasing degree of valvular obstruction results in increasing velocity and pressure gradient of blood flow across the valve. The pressure gradient across the diseased valve is directly related to the valve orifice area. The core determinant factor for severity grading of valvular stenosis from any cause is valvular area. The stenotic cardiac valve will produce a turbulent jet flow into the receiving chamber downstream which is visualised as a dark signal void in gradient echo CINE MRI images. Peak flow velocity value and the pressure gradient flow across the diseased valve are also the parameters that indicate the degree of valvular stenosis severity. MRI can be used for direct measurement of stenotic valvular area and peak velocity of flow across the stenotic valve. A good correlation between MRI and echocardiography result and the reliability and safety of using MRI in valvular stenosis assessment were reported. Gradient echo CINE and gradient echo quantitative (Q) flow mapping MRI are still the key techniques to demonstrate the stenotic valve structure and to quantify the velocity of flow across the valve respectively.

OP 161

Optimal Release Time for Modular Software in Random Field Environment**Ritu Gupta, Sanghita P Nath*****Department of Mathematics, Amity University, Noida, UP, India**

Abstract: In this paper, we propose a software reliability growth model (SRGM) to estimate the reliability of a large and complicated modular system. In order to make the fault detection and fault correction processes suitable to real-world circumstances, the influence of a random field environment (RFE) in an imperfect debugging environment is taken into account. The unexpected nature of the uncertain components in the software's working settings may have a significant and unanticipated impact on the reliability of the software. As a result, a software system's reliability in a field environment typically differs from the reliability prediction made during the testing phase of the software development process as well as from all of its comparable applications in other domains. We further determine an optimal release time policy based on cost-reliability constraint. The policy aims to minimize the expected total cost, which includes the costs of testing, debugging, releasing and the risk cost due to software failure. The proposed SRGM may provide a valuable tool for software developers to predict the reliability of a complex modular system and make informed decisions about the optimal release time.

Keywords: SRGM, Software reliability, Imperfect debugging, Random field environment, Optimal release time.

OP 162

Effect of COVID-19 on Pregnancy

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Abstract: The World Health Organization declared a global pandemic of coronavirus disease 2019 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) in March 2020. As the number of confirmed cases increases, evidence on the transmission, incidence, and effect of SARS-CoV-2 infection in mothers and their babies remains limited. In prior pandemics such as SARS and H1N1, pregnant women were more susceptible to serious illness and had greater mortality rates than the general population. Successful pregnancy depends on adaptation of the woman's immune system to tolerate a genetically foreign fetus. Although the immune system changes are not well understood, a shift from cell-mediated immunity toward humoral immunity is believed to occur. These immunologic changes may alter susceptibility to and severity of infectious diseases in pregnant women. Clinical experience of pregnancies complicated with infection by other coronaviruses e.g., SARS and Middle Eastern Respiratory Syndrome, has led to pregnant woman being considered potentially vulnerable to severe SARSCoV-2 infection. Physiological changes during pregnancy have a significant impact on the immune system, respiratory system, cardiovascular function, and coagulation. These may have positive or negative effects on COVID-19 disease progression. Asymptomatic infection presents a further challenge regarding service provision, prevention, and management. Besides the direct impacts of the disease, a plethora of indirect consequences of the pandemic adversely affect maternal health, including reduced access to reproductive health services, increased mental health strain, and increased socioeconomic deprivation. Pregnant women present a unique challenge during this COVID-19 pandemic as they have multiple encounters with healthcare workers (HCW) and most are admitted to hospital for birth. Universal screening of this population will reduce the risk

of asymptomatic transmission to HCW and other pregnant women; early patient isolation and use of appropriate personal protective equipment; and improving understanding of perinatal transmission.

Keywords: COVID-19; immunology; neonatal outcomes; pathophysiology; pregnancy.

OP 163

Investigation of bioactive molecules of *R. communis* by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry**Vijay. S^{1*} and Susikaran. S¹****¹Department of Sericulture, Forest College and Research Institute, TNAU, Mettupalayam-641301**

Abstract: Castor plant (*Ricinus communis* L.) is the most important food plant for the eri silkworm which also produces castor oil and contains a variety of secondary metabolites. Castor plant leaves are also widely employed in many different industries owing to their wide range of biological components. This research used gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) to identify the bioactive compounds in a methanol extract of *R. communis* leaves. The chemicals identified by GC-MS in the methanol extract matched those in the National Institute of Standards and Technology database (NIST). GC-MS analysis of chloroform extract of *R. communis* leaves reveal the presence of bioactive compounds as N- Propargyloxycarbonyl-, tridecyl ester, Ethanol, 2-(9-octadecenyloxy)-, (Z)-, (S)-(+)-2-Amino-3-methyl-1-butanol and Methyl d- lyxofuranoside, Formic acid, 1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, 2-propenyl ester, 2,2-di-n-Propylacetyl chloride, Stigmasterol, Octadecanoic acid and Phytol. Many biological processes are primarily carried out through these bioactive substances.

Keywords: Bioactive compounds, Biological activities, GC-MS, *R. communis*,

OP 164

Microbes used as a Tool for Bioremediation of Heavy Metals from Wastewater**Dr. Madhumita Ghosh Dastidar***, **Jayanth D. R. #**, **Eesha Prasad#****Department of Microbiology, Vijaya College, R. V. Road, Bengaluru****Affiliated to Bengaluru City University**

Introduction: The rapidity of urbanization in a developing country like India has become a major source of ground and surface water contamination. Large quantities of toxic effluents like heavy metals are let out into water bodies from industries which must be treated beforehand. One of the most efficient and eco-friendly methods of reducing heavy metal concentrations is Bioremediation. In this project microbes were isolated and used as a tool for the Bioremediation of heavy metals Cadmium, Chromium, and Lead released from Peenya industrial area and Rajarajeshwari nagar of Bangalore city.

Aims and Objectives:

1. To isolate, analyze, and characterize microorganisms from collected industrial effluents and sewage samples.
2. To estimate the concentration of Cadmium, Chromium and Lead present in collected samples before and after inoculation of microbes to check its efficiency of heavy metals reduction.

Methods: In phase 1, the microorganisms were isolated from the collected wastewater samples and identified using Pour Plate Method, colony characterization, Gram staining, and Biochemical tests. *Pseudomonas* and Consortium of bacteria were abundantly obtained from this phase, later used as primary inoculum for Bioremediation.

In phase 2, the primary inoculum was incubated with heavy metals inoculated and the growth of microorganisms was constantly monitored and observed.

The concentrations of heavy metals- cadmium, chromium, and lead before and after inoculation of microorganisms were measured by using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy and percentage reduction of heavy metals was calculated.

Conclusion

- The microbes isolated from industrial effluents could reduce the concentrations of heavy metals significantly.
- The Bioremediation of heavy metals using microbes is a potential way of reducing their concentration in sewage and industrial effluents.
- This is an environmental friendly and effective way of reducing soil and water pollution which can be applied to reduce heavy metal toxicity in large scale industries.

Keywords: Bioremediation, wastewater samples, heavy metals, atomic absorption spectrometer, eco-friendly.

OP 165

Acute exposure of flubendiamide disrupts sonic hedgehog signalling during eye development in domestic chick *Gallus domesticus***Jigisha Bhosale¹, Juhi Vaishnav², Dhanush Danes², Shashikant Sharma², Suresh Balakrishnan^{2*}**¹Department of Environmental Studies, Faculty of Science, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, 390002, Gujarat, India²Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, 390002, Gujarat, India

Abstract: Pesticides are obnoxious chemicals used to kill pests in agriculture. However, their unrestrained use has led to hazardous effects on animals on land as well as aquatic life. In humans, instances of congenital eye defects have been reported as a consequence of direct or indirect exposure to pesticides. One such pesticide, flubendiamide, has been used by our lab to study its ill effects on the development of chick embryos.

A sub-lethal concentration of Flubendiamide, when dosed in eggs of Rhode Island Red chicks, has shown a number of developmental anomalies. Defects in the eye, such as microphthalmia, anophthalmia and incomplete pigmentation, have been majorly found. According to the literature, the process of eye formation requires tight regulation of a signalling molecule *Shh*, which orchestrates early eye development by splitting of eye field and guiding the neural tube patterning. Therefore, we hypothesize that flubendiamide alters the expression pattern of *Shh* in the early developing embryo, which is the root cause of congenital eye defects.

To validate this hypothesis, we carried out mortality and malformation studies as well as gene expression studies in control and Flubendiamide treated groups on Day 2 and Day 4 of incubation. The study revealed misexpression of *Shh* and associated downstream regulators like *Pax6*, *Wnt11*, *Fgf8*, etc., in the treated group, which leads to defective optic cup formation and patterning of the neural tube, hampering the overall process of eye development.

Keywords: Congenital eye defects, Flubendiamide, Microphthalmia, Anophthalmia

OP 166

Statistical Science: Descriptive Statistics**Sarah Fatima****B.sc Mathematics/Statistics Shia P.G. College, Lucknow 226003**

Abstract: Descriptive statistics is an important branch of statistics that collects, analyze, and interprets the data. It involves the use of quantitative methods to summarize and describe the characteristics of a dataset, including its central tendency, variability, and distribution. The primary goal of descriptive statistics is to provide meaningful insights into the data, which can be used to make informed decisions or draw conclusions. In this paper, we provide an overview of the fundamental concepts and methods used in descriptive statistics. The first section of the paper discusses the different measures of central tendency, including the mean, median, and mode. These measures are used to describe the typical value of a dataset and are useful for summarizing large amounts of data. The second section of the paper focuses on measures of variability, which are used to describe the degree of spread or dispersion of data. These measures include the range, variance, and standard deviation, and they provide important information about the distribution of the data. In the third section the paper discusses about the measures of shapes i.e., skewness and kurtosis. The fourth section of the paper discusses the graphical representations of data, which are an essential tool in descriptive statistics. Graphical representations, such as histograms, box plots, and scatter plots, provide a visual representation of data distribution and can help researchers to identify patterns and trends in the data.

OP 167

To Reuse the Fabric Waste: Implementing the Japanese Technique of Kintsugi
Prof. Vasundhara Saluja & Utsav Bharadwaj
Sharda University, Uttar Pradesh

Abstract: Sustainability is the buzz word these days; it is not just a trend but necessity to survive. The garment industry is one of the largest contributors to global waste with fabric scraps being a significant contributor to the same. While organisation sharing towards sustainable practices, there is a need of innovation to reduce fabric waste. Focusing on 3R's of circular economy – Reduce, Recycle & Reuse, this paper will explore methods to contain the fabric waste in an innovative way through forms pieces of fabrics inspired by Japanese Art Kintsugi.

Keywords: Recycle, Reuse, Reduce, Circular fashion, Kintsugi

OP 168

Synthesis and characterization of Cu-doped BiVO₄/g-C₃N₄ nanocomposites for enhanced photocatalytic activity**Akradip Majumder¹, Swastik Paul¹, Ridipt Mishra¹, Subhasis Roy¹, Biswajit Kamila¹, Arindam Mandal^{1*}****¹Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata – 700009**

Abstract: The intriguing method of converting solar energy into hydrogen by splitting water has drawn a lot of interest to photocatalytic performance in semiconductor-based photocatalysis. CuBiVO₄/ g-C₃N₄ nanocomposite materials owing to their visible light absorbing nature, low recombination rate, and stable structure have been studied extensively for their application in photocatalysis. Zircon, monoclinic scheelite, and tetragonal scheelite are the three crystal phases of bismuth vanadate (BiVO₄). Because of its tiny bandgap of 2.4 eV, monoclinic scheelite BiVO₄ stands out among them as having exceptional visible-light photocatalytic capabilities. The greater degradation ratio is caused by g-C₃N₄ nanosheets' ability to facilitate an easier electron transfer during the process and their large specific surface area. Herein, in our work, we have fabricated Cu-BiVO₄/ g-C₃N₄ heterostructure using a modified sol-gel approach. Cu doping introduces many forbidden states in the heterostructure, which traps the electron, preventing it from recombination. Five different samples with dissimilar compositions of Cu-BiVO₄ nanocomposite materials keeping the composition of g-C₃N₄ constant are fabricated. Furthermore, characterizations such as XRD, SEM, TEM, PL, and FTIR are performed. The PL spectra manifest that the sample with 10 percent Cu-BiVO₄ nanocomposite materials has the lowest recombination rate, and henceforth has less charge transfer resistance. Moreover, on studying all synthesized photocatalysts and based on the literature survey the focus will be on 10 percent Cu-BiVO₄ for checking the degradation efficiency. The SEM images reveal that the fabricated photocatalyst has porous structures, which results in enhanced photocatalytic activity. Finally, depending on all characterization the performance of Cu-doped BiVO₄/g-C₃N₄ nanocomposite photocatalysts is expected to significantly increase. Keywords- Sol-gel, heterostructure, nanocomposite, degradation, photocatalyst.

OP 169

Removal of Dye from aqueous solution using Ion exchange resins**Poornima K^a, Jaya sree D^a, Dhanabal R^b, P. Gomathi Priya^b, C. S. Latha^a and R. Kavitha^a**^aDepartment of Chemistry, Quaid E Millath Government college for Women, Chennai-600002.^bDepartment of Chemical Engineering, Alagappa college of Technology, Anna University, Chennai-600025

Abstract: The presence of synthetic dye in industrial wastewater is one of the most important environment issues. Dyes are widely used in a number of industries, such as textile and leather dyeing, food, cosmetics, paper printing, gasoline, with the textile industry as the largest consumer. Dyeing wastewaters are characterized not only by intensive and difficult for colour removal but also by high pH, suspended and dissolved solids, chemical and biochemical oxygen demands. One of the most promising methods for treating these waste water effluents is the ion exchange removal of dye. This project work summarizes the research on the cationic dye (Malachite green) adsorption by the polymeric resin Indion 225H and AmberLite MAC-3H. Many aspects, such as the contact time, resin dose, initial dye concentration, and pH that might affect the efficiency of dye removal were observed. Regeneration, Kinetics and Isothermal studies were carried out and the results obtained were compared for better performance. Keywords: Wastewater, Dye, Adsorption, Ion exchange resins.

OP 170

Case report of inhibiting synergy pattern by Kinesiotaping in stroke patient: A challenging aspect**Khushboo Anjum¹ and Adarsh Kumar Srivastav²****¹PG Student, Department of Physiotherapy, School of Health Sciences, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur****²Assistant Professor, Department of Physiotherapy, School of Health Sciences, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur**

Background: Spontaneous recovery of synergy pattern in chronic stroke patients is so reduced and often negligible. In this regards many techniques as rehabilitation program have been developed. The overall functionality of motor recovery occurs mainly due to a prolonged rehabilitation process. Therefore kinesiotaping is one of the advanced rehabilitation intervention procedures to reduce recovery and inhibition of synergy patterns among chronic stroke patients.

Purpose: In the case of chronic stroke patients synergy pattern development is usually common which affects the motor function of the upper extremity and quality of life. In this case study kinesiotaping effects are discussed for inhibiting synergy, improving motor function of the upper extremity, and quality of life.

Material and Method: A 50 years old male adult with a stroke since 2017, had an attack with a sudden rise in blood pressure, after which his symptoms starts appearing and progressed day by day.

He had difficulty in elevation in the right upper limb, was unable to perform activities of daily living, and had mild pain during activity. The examination finding shows an increase in muscle tone and a decrease in motor functions in the right upper extremity. Modified Ashworth scale, Fugl-Meyer assessment upper extremity (FMA-UE), and Indian Stroke Scale (ISS) outcome measures were used for evaluation. Patients received kinesiotaping along with conventional rehabilitation for 6 days a week with 24 hours intervals for 2 weeks.

Results: A significant improvement was observed in muscle tone, motor functions of the right upper extremity, and quality of life.

Conclusion: This advanced rehabilitation intervention is effective in inhibiting synergy in chronic stroke patients which propels that it could be beneficial in the future for chronic stroke synergy pattern patients.

Keywords: Kinesiotaping, rehabilitation, stroke, upper extremity

OP 171

Upper limb Myofascial Release to improve Motor functions in a patient with Stroke: A Case Report**Saliha Rafat^{1*} and Adarsh Kumar Srivastav²*****¹MPT (Neurology) Student, Department of Physiotherapy, School of Health Sciences, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur-208024, UP****²Assistant Professor, Department of Physiotherapy, School of Health Sciences, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur-208024, UP**

Background: Stroke is a neurological condition characterized by blockage of blood vessels. It is the 2nd leading cause of death globally and affects roughly 13.7 million people and kills around 5.5 million annually and it is 3rd leading cause of physical disability due to spasticity. Spasticity is a common post stroke complication that causes arm and legs in an abnormal position. Myofascial release therapy is a unique and corresponding approach to loosening and realigning muscles and improving motor functions that causes diminishing in spasticity.

Methods: A 40-year-old female patient homemaker by occupation who presented with a chief complaint of pain in left shoulder, inability to perform active movements of left UL and also had difficulty in doing daily activities. On examination she had increased tone in shoulder, decreased motor functions and quality of life. After assessment treatment was planned and she was treated with Direct Myofascial release mainly on shoulder muscles for a period of 3 days in a week for 2 weeks beginning approximately 6 months after right MCA infarct. Pre and post outcome assessed were Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS), Fugl-Meyer Assessment Upper Extremity (FMA-UE) and Indian stroke scale (ISS) after 2 weeks of treatment.

Results: The Myofascial Release showed significant decrease in tone of muscle on MAS from >2 to +1 or 1, improvement in motor function on FMA-UE from 11/66 to 24/66 and also improvement in patient's quality of life on ISS from 40 to 49 ISS.

Conclusion: We concluded that using a Myofascial release in conjunction with traditional neurorehabilitation aids in upper limb motor function.

Keywords: Stroke, Quality of life, Spasticity, Muscle spasticity.

OP 172

Conjunct effect of low level laser therapy and kinesiотaping in patient with cervical radiculopathy: A Case Report**Sadiya Rafat^{1*} and Dr. Digvijay Sharma²*****¹MPT (Orthopedics) Student, Department of Physiotherapy, School of Health Sciences, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur-208024, UP****²Director, School of Health Sciences, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur-208024, UP**

Background: Cervical radiculopathy is a common condition in which nerve root or inflammation to the nerve is caused by mechanical compression. Different physiotherapy intervention has been established for the management of cervical radiculopathy patients. However, there is scarcity of use of advance physiotherapeutic intervention protocols in such patients. The present case shows the efficacy of an advanced physiotherapeutic protocol which can reduce pain and functional disability in patients with cervical radiculopathy.

Case report: A 42 years old female patient came to physiotherapy OPD with pain present in left side of the neck and radiates upto arm and forearm. She has discomfort in left upper thoracic region. Grade II tenderness was present on left occiput, upper trapezius and deltoid muscles. After assessment treatment was planned and she was treated with 4 weeks rehab protocol. Pre and post outcome measured assessed were VAS (Visual analogue scale), NDI (neck disability index) and DASH (disability of arm shoulder and hand).

Objective: Describe the effectiveness of LASER therapy, kinesiотaping and therapeutic exercises to relieve the pain and disability of neck, arm, shoulder and hand.

Method: The treatment protocol were of 4 weeks, in 1st and 2nd weeks the low level laser therapy along with conventional rehabilitation were given then in 3rd and 4th weeks the kinesiотaping and craniobasal release along with conventional rehabilitation.

Results: This concise rehabilitation protocol showed significant improvement in VAS from 6cm to 0.8cm, improvement in neck disability on neck disability index from 48% to 28% and also improvement in disability of arm, shoulder and hand on DASH from 75 to 53.5.

Conclusion: We concluded that this concise rehabilitation protocol was effective in cervical radiculopathy patients.

Keywords: Cervical radiculopathy, inflammation, kinesiотaping

OP 173

Zero waste pattern making: A technique towards Sustainable Garment Production**Sumayya Chaudhary and Prof. Vasundhara Saluja****Sharda University, Uttar Pradesh**

Abstract: The fashion industry is a significant contributor to environmental pollution due to the vast amount of textile waste generated during production. Zero-waste fashion design is a possible solution to the problem, which aims to minimize textile waste by using innovative pattern-making techniques. The paper will explore the effectiveness of pattern-making techniques in reducing fabric waste in zero-waste designs. Through case studies and interviews of fashion designers, this study will analyze the various techniques used in zero-waste design, including modular pattern pieces, creating one continuous piece of fabric, and incorporating irregular shapes and curves. The results of this study may have implications to curb the waste in garment industry and, hence impacting the environment.

Keywords: Garment industry, textile waste, zero-waste design, Pattern Making

OP 174

Sentiment Based Topic Modeling On Reviews**Dayana Vincent****Department of Data Science
NMKRV College for Women**

Abstract: Online reviews are most valuable information for business and also the customers. However, the increase in the reviews is difficult to process and also to make meaningful insights. This work is an attempt to examine the reviews by the customers on a product using topic modelling based negative sentiment. Data collected from E-commerce websites like Flipkart, Amazon are employed for this purpose. Sentiment analysis is done using happy transformer. Sentiment-based topic modelling using LDA is employed to find the hidden topics in the reviews. In this sentiment-based topic modelling analyses customer's negative reviews on phones. The goal of this project is to gain insights into key topics based on their negative sentiment expressed by customers regarding the phones, which can be used to improve product and service offerings. Various plots such as topic distribution, pie charts are used to get insights. This analysis helped us to reveal several key topics that were discussed in the phone reviews, including camera quality, battery life, hanging, and heating issues, service etc. The results demonstrate the utility of sentiment-based topic modelling for analysing customer negative reviews and identifying key topics of interest. The insights gained from this analysis can help companies to improve their products and services by addressing common customer concerns and feedback. This provides a practical example of how sentiment-based topic modelling can be applied to real-world text data in order to gain insights and to make better decision-making.

Keywords: Sentiment based Topic modelling, Topic Modelling, Negative Reviews, LDA.

OP 175

Medicine as a Career! Apprehensions and Aspirations among 1st year undergraduates**Dr. Vemuri Keerthi¹ and Dr Phanindra Dulipala²**¹Department of Community Medicine, Katuri medical college and hospital, Guntur-522 019²Department of Community Medicine, Katuri medical college and hospital, Guntur-522 019**Abstract:**

Background: Choice of career is a milestone in a student's life. Medical field itself is a milestone where in students has to go through tough, competitive exams which will be followed by delayed settlement in career. Despite of it still many students aspire to become a doctor. Various factors play a role in choosing a career with which comes many apprehensions.

Aims & objectives:

1. To identify factors influencing student's decision to take medicine.
2. To know their worries before starting medical education.
3. To know their anxieties after joining med school.
4. To learn understudies' future desires and affecting variables.

Methodology: An observational study was done among 165 first year medical undergraduates during March 2023. A self-designed semi structured questionnaire consisting of socio-demographic details and questions related to aspirations and apprehensions was given to all the participants after the approval of institutional ethical committee. Data was collected and entered into Microsoft Excel sheet and analysed for descriptive statistics.

Results: Among 165 study participants, 76.4% students had opted medicine as a career out of their passion. About 43.6%, 30.9% students were apprehensive about long course duration before and after starting medical education respectively. Most of the students around 77% were aspiring to do post-graduation on ones' own interest towards speciality.

Conclusion: Our research found that, despite students' concerns about the long course duration, they still want to pursue a career in medicine and specialise, owing to their strong desire to become doctors.

Keywords: Medical career, Students, Apprehension, Aspirations.

OP 176

Impact of COVID-19 on Quality of Life, A Scoping ReviewVartika Mishra^{1*} and Dr. Adarsh Kumar Srivastav (PT)²¹MPT (Neurology) Student, Department of Physiotherapy, School of Health Sciences, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur-208024 UP²Assistant Professor, Department of Physiotherapy, School of Health Sciences, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur-208024 UP**Abstract****Introduction:**

Corona viruses are the diverse group of viruses that can infect mild to severe respiratory infections in humans. It caused fatal respiratory illness. The virus emerged as a new public health concern in the twenty-first century. Like many other aspects, it is expected that the quality of life (QoL) of the public is largely affected during and after COVID-19 pandemic. This caused an outbreak of unusual viral pneumonia. Quality of life (QOL) is the multidimensional concept that measures a person's wellbeing. The discussion and use of QOL as the measurable outcome in health has been increased in recent decades as the healthcare has shifted from a disease-focused biomedical model to a more holistic, well-being focused bio psychosocial model. The objective of this study is to determine how much quality of life of the people affect during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods: Various databases including Google scholar, PUBMED, Cochrane, APA, EMBASE search was done using the following keyword; Covid and Quality of Life. Articles included in this study are from inception to March 2023.

Results: 5 articles were included in this scoping review. We identified the description of how Quality of Life is affected among covid population. The included studies focused impacts of COVID-19 and showed significant negative and poor impact on Quality of life among covid patients.

Conclusion:

We concluded that the Covid-19 has higher negative impact on the Quality of Life during and after pandemic and it affects person's quality of life poorly.

Keywords: COVID-19 and QUALITY OF LIFE

OP 177

VARIATION OF REACTION TIME IN PROFESSIONAL AND RECREATIONAL PLAYERS

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ABSTRACT: Elite players are the professionally trained player according to their domain game's criteria. While recreational players (RP) are the players who used to play the game just for the fun. Reaction time (RT) is the time difference between the given stimulus and action performed. Aim and objective of the study is to find the existence of variation occur in professional and recreational players. The present review includes literature search up to April 2023 . Electronic database Pubmed, Scopus, Cochrane and Google Scholar were search. Only article written in English were search, a search strategy developed for selection of the article. In result there have been 6 studies that evaluated the significance difference between the reaction time in professional and recreational players. Which helps professional players to stay concentrated, improves decision taking skills and enhances multi-tasking abilities in comparison to the recreational players. Some of the studies also preferred calling recreational players as non-professional players.

Key words: Elite players, Recreational players, Search Engine, Pubmed, Reaction time

OP 178

Influence of materialism on consumer buying behavior in India**Swapnil Gaur****Ph.D. scholar, Swami Rama Himalayan University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand**

Abstract: The consumer behavior in India has been evolving at a steady rate since the late 90's with the rise in income levels of people who fall under the category of middle class. As the income levels increased, the disposable income of people increased proportionally with it. Thus, people now have more money to spend on various products and services in the market. With so many varieties and classes of products & services to choose from in the market, various factors were found to influence the buying behavior of luxury goods in the Indian consumer. One such factor is materialism. Materialism has been defined as the propensity to consider material possessions and physical comfort as more important than spiritual values (Hudders, et al 2011). An individual showing materialistic behavior is shown to reflect great importance to the material or non-living things as compared to the relationships, ethnic & moral values, etc. Materialism serves as a driver for consumer buying behavior as it often propels a consumer to go for impulse buying. Especially when we take an example of luxury goods, materialism serves as a major driver. When individuals are subjected to social comparison, they are compelled to go for a similar or higher purchase than what someone in their social circle has done and thus, their materialistic values come into play. Such individuals (the ones who show materialism) are often found to take great pride in their purchase. This study will further enrich the existing literature on materialism and consumer behavior by studying the influence that materialism has over the buying behavior of an Indian middle class consumer. The middle class is one of the rising income groups in terms of market share and buying percentage, therefore, the findings of this study will have significant implications for the marketers.

OP 179

Relationship between sleep habits and Smartphone Dependence in Adolescents**Vandana Kumari****Assistant Professor****Sakaldiha P.G. College, Chandauli, UP**

Abstract: Adolescents and college going students frequently experience inadequate sleep in this digital age. It has been discovered that women need more sleep than men do. The primary goal of this research is to look into the relationships between sleep duration and Smartphone dependence. Methods: 300 female college students from the Varanasi district were chosen for this questionnaire-based research. The correlation between sleep habits and Smartphone dependence has been investigated. The Smartphone Addiction Scale and Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index questionnaire have been used for the study. Results: Participants slept for an average of 5.25 ± 1.49 hours each night. Smartphone dependence and sleep duration had a substantial negative association, according to a Pearson coefficient co relational analysis ($P < 0.01$). The findings of this research highlight the significance of preventing Smartphone dependence in order to preserve healthy sleeping patterns in adolescent females.

Keywords: sleep, smartphone dependence, sleep habits, healthy sleeping patterns.

OP 180

The future of chemotherapy lies in drug Nano carriers for advanced cancer therapies**Kirti¹****¹Department of Biotechnology, Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida 201312**

Abstract: Cancer is the second leading cause of death globally, trailing only cardiovascular disease. It is characterised by unregulated cell division and the absence of cell death, which, with the exception of haematological malignancies, leads to the formation of an aberrant cell mass or tumour. This original tumour expands as a result of additional vascularization, gains metastatic potential over time, and spreads to other body regions, resulting in metastasis and mortality. Environmental or inherited factors damage or mutate the genetic material of the cells, causing cancer. Local and nonmetastatic cancers are mostly treated with surgery and radiotherapy, whereas metastatic cancers are treated with anti-cancer medications (chemotherapy, hormone and biological therapies). Chemotherapy relies on the prevention of fast cell division, a feature of cancer cells. However, chemotherapy also affects normal cells with fast proliferation rates, such as those in the hair follicles, bone marrow, and gastrointestinal tract, resulting in the side effects that are characteristic of chemotherapy. The indiscriminate killing of normal cells, the toxicity of current chemotherapeutic medications, and the emergence of multidrug resistance underscore the need for the development of novel effective tailored treatments based on the molecular biology of tumour cells. These novel targeted therapies, of increasing interest as evidenced by FDA-approved targeted cancer drugs in recent years, block biologic transduction pathways and/or specific cancer proteins to induce the death of cancer cells via apoptosis and stimulation of the immune system, or specifically deliver chemotherapeutic agents to cancer cells while minimising unwanted side effects. This review focuses on indirect targeted approaches that deliver chemotherapeutic agents to molecular targets overexpressed on the surface of tumour cells. Although targeted therapies can be achieved directly by altering specific cell signalling with monoclonal antibodies or small molecule inhibitors, the focus of this article is on indirect targeted approaches that deliver chemotherapeutic agents to molecular targets overexpressed on the surface of tumour cells. Particularly, we provide a detailed description of various cytotoxic drug carriers, such as liposomes, carbon nanotubes, dendrimers, polymeric micelles, polymeric conjugates, and polymeric nanoparticles, in passive and active targeted cancer therapy, by

enhancing the permeability and retention or by the functionalization of the surface of the carriers, emphasising those that have received FDA approval or are part of the most significant clinical studies to date. These drug carriers not only deliver chemotherapeutic agents to tumours while avoiding normal tissues and lowering systemic toxicity, but they also shield cytotoxic medications from degradation, increase their half-life, payload, and solubility, and decrease renal clearance. Despite the numerous advantages of all the analysed anticancer drug carriers, only a few of them have received FDA approval; specifically, only two polymer-protein conjugates, five liposomal formulations, and one polymeric nanoparticle are commercially available, compared to sixteen monoclonal antibodies. Several clinical trials using polymer-protein and polymer-drug conjugates, liposomal formulations, including immune liposomes, polymeric micelles, and polymeric nanoparticles are now ongoing. Due to their unresolved toxicity, no FDA approvals or clinical trials are currently underway for carbon nanotubes or dendrimers. Moreover, we analyse in detail the most promising and advanced preclinical studies of polymeric nanoparticles as carriers of different cytotoxic agents to active and passive tumour targeting published in the last 5 years, as they have enormous potential in cancer therapy and are one of the most widely studied nanoplatforms in this field in recent years. In the last six years, 90 percent of the studies based on cancer therapies with polymeric nanoparticles have been published, highlighting the new interest in these formulations.

Keywords: Cancer, Chemotherapy, Nanocarriers.

OP 181

Synthesis and Characterization of CdO/WO₃ nanocomposite by Hydrothermal Method**Nishant, R K Shukla*, Anchal Srivastava and Navina Wadhvani****Department of Physics, University of Lucknow, Lucknow - 226007, India**

Abstract: Nanocomposite CdO/WO₃ have interesting electrochromic, photochromic and physical properties that makes them useful in a variety of applications like gas sensing, photocatalysis, energy storage devices etc. This paper presents the formation of CdO/WO₃ nanocomposite in different molar ratio by hydrothermal reaction. All samples have been characterized by X-ray diffraction; Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy and UV-Vis spectrophotometer. XRD pattern conforms the formation of orthogonal phase of WO₃ and monoclinic phase of cadmium tungstate (CdWO₄). FTIR spectra of CdO/WO₃ have been measured in the wavenumber region of 400-4000cm⁻¹. The bending and stretching vibration of Cd-O (503 cm⁻¹), W-O (658 cm⁻¹), W-O-W (cm⁻¹), Cd-O-W (835 cm⁻¹), and O-H (1650 cm⁻¹) have been identified in FTIR spectra of CdO/WO₃. UV-Vis spectra conforms the variation in optical property of CdO/WO₃ and bandgap is obtained 2.3 to 2.5 eV from Tauc plot.

OP 182

Green synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles using peels of citrus limon**Vishnu Kumar Dwivedi, R K Shukla, Anchal Srivastava and Navina Wadhvani*****Department of Physics, University of Lucknow, Lucknow 226007, India**

Abstract: Green nanotechnology is an interesting research area due to the potential applications in the development of novel technologies. Especially, biologically produced nanomaterials have become an important branch of nanomaterials with optimum performance in the field of agriculture. In this study peel extract of citrus limon were used to synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles. Zinc acetate dihydrate was used as a precursor with citrus limon peel extract. The structural and optical properties of nanoparticles were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer (UV-Vis) and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The size range of zinc oxide nanoparticles prepared is 6-46 nm.

Keywords: Zinc oxide, green synthesis, peel extract, XRD.

OP 183

A Study of Career Planning and Career Development on Employee Satisfaction in Private Institution at Lucknow District**Anukriti Mishra****Research Scholar, Babu Banarasi Das University, Lucknow, UP**

Abstract: This study aims to determine the relationship between career planning and career development opportunities available to the employees and their job satisfaction. This study is focusing on private institution at Lucknow District. Methodology/Sample for this paper, survey was conducted by using structured questionnaire that were administered through e-mail and by distributing to five hundred respondents from private institution situated at Lucknow district. Hypothesis testing has been done by using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) through AMOS (SPSS-20). Sample size for the study is 350 respondents and the sampling procedure used is convenience based. The study determined that there is positive relationship between career planning and career development and employee job satisfaction and there is positive relationship between career management and employee job satisfaction in education sector. Employees are satisfied with career planning and career development activities that are offered at their organizations. Recently in Corporate world has become more competitive hence, employees have become more conscious in career development.

Key word: Career planning, Career development, Employee career management, Employee Job Satisfaction

OP 184

A study of the relationship between green governance and sustainable finance in PSU banks***Dr. Seema Tripathi**
IISE College, Lucknow, UP

Abstract: In order to strengthen its green infrastructure, achieve its sustainable development goals, and address climate concerns like global warming, its enormous population, and enormous green depletion, India must now accept challenges from the international community. Green finance must be used if the nation is to survive. Green finance, often known as climate finance, requires a shift in emphasis and behavior from conventional forms of funding to more environmentally friendly financing. India needs a green finance plan if it is to meet its lofty objectives for sustainable development. It is necessary to persuade Indian, as well as global, financial institutions and corporations, to refocus on the topic of green finance. There have been many opportunities and difficulties on this front. In order to manage India's sustainable development objectives and go forward with green financing, this study aims to comprehend the scenario in which India currently finds itself. This study is descriptive in nature and is based on secondary data referred from government, national, and international institutions.

Keyword: Green Governance, Sustainable Finance, Indian Banking sector, Environment, NABARD, SIDBI.

OP 185

Expatriation, Immigration and career development: Various modes of Engagement**Dr Alka Singh Bhatt****Amity Business School, Amity University, Lucknow Campus, Lucknow, UP****Abstract**

Purpose: The paper has two goals. The first is to develop a conceptual framework for analyzing the strategies of internationally mobile professionals in managing barriers to their career development. This framework is developed using Duberley et al.'s and Richardson's concept of "modes of engagement". The second goal is to better understand the nature of the careers that ethnic minority migrants undertake.

Design/methodology/approach: Qualitative interviews were conducted with 43 skilled Indian migrants. Six additional interviews were conducted with key informants involved in the development and implementation of immigration policies in India. Furthermore a few more countries immigration policymaking is analyzed.

Findings: In order to manage structural barriers to their career development, participants navigated within the organizational and national structures using four modes: maintenance, transformation, entrepreneurship, and opt out.

Research limitations/implications: There was limited access to the developers of immigration policies. The paper focused on only one ethnic minority group.

Practical implications: The management of migrants in India needs to be more supportive of their efforts in using their capital.

Originality/value: The paper contributes to the literature on careers of internationally mobile professionals by offering an understanding of the experiences of an under-researched group of participants, that is to say persons from an ethnic minority who relocated to live and work in India.

Keywords: Careers, Career development, Expatriates, Migrant workers, Immigration, Ethnic minorities, France

OP 186

Strength of Dielectric constant of CuO doped Polyaniline**Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh**

Assistant Professor, Department of Physics

Dr. Shakuntala Misra National Rehabilitation University Lucknow-226017

Abstract: Polyaniline/CuO NCs at different weight percentages are synthesized by chemical oxidative polymerization method. The composites have been synthesized with various compositions (10, 15, and 20 wt %) of cupric oxide in Polyaniline (PANI), the chemical characterization are made using XRD (X-ray diffraction). The surface morphology of these composites have been studied with scanning electron micrograph (SEM). The dielectric properties have been studied at different wt% CuO doped Polyaniline (PANI) with function of frequency range from 100 Hz to 5 MHz and also at temperatures range 303 K to 343 K. The dielectric loss decreases with increasing the frequency and increases with increasing CuO concentration. The maximum dielectric loss is found to be at lower wt %CuO doped Polyaniline (PANI) NCs.

Keywords: Conducting Polyaniline, XRD, SEM, Nanocomposites, Dielectric constant.

OP 187

Digital Voyeurism (Cyber Voyeurism) Against Women in India: Issues and Solutions**Priya Gupta****Research Scholar, Department of Law****Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, UP**

Abstract: In India, a country that worships Aadi Shakti Navadurga, women have got respect and a special place from the very beginning. The history of crimes against women has started since ancient times, but with the development of information and technology, crimes against women have also increased and due to this, there has been a change in the form of crimes that have been going on since ancient times, which we see today as cyber-crimes in the cyber world, one of them the crime we know as digital voyeurism.

Digital voyeurism is the crime of taking non-consensual photos or videos of women's private areas and sharing them online.

Watching or recording through any electronic device the private intimate acts of a woman without her consent from ancient times to the present day Or taking his picture etc. is voyeurism. And when the same crime is seen or recorded or photographed while doing intimate acts of a woman without her consent through online medium, then that crime becomes digital voyeurism. The same thing has been explained by The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013 in Section 354-C of Indian Penal Code, 1860. And for committing an offense under this section, a provision has been made for a minimum of 1 year and a maximum of 7 years of imprisonment and fine. Under the IT Act, 2000 Voyeurism is a crime, irrespective of gender. Section 66E of this Act provides for punishment in cases of violation of privacy. The punishment for such publication, transmission or capturing is also defined in this section as imprisonment which may extend up to three years or with fine of up to two lakhs or both. Section 67A of the IT Act states that if material which is published online is sexually explicit; the person can be imprisoned for 5 years and be liable to pay a fine of upto ten lakhs.

Under the POCSO Act, 2012 voyeurism is a crime against girl child. Section 14 of this act, imprisonment of 5 years and fine has been given for using a child for pornographic purposes.

And section 15 carries a maximum of 5 years of imprisonment or fine for storage of pornographic material involving a child.

And under Article 21 of The Constitution of India 1950, this crime is a violation of a woman's life and personal liberty and a woman's right to live with human dignity and right to privacy are also violated.

Even after having these laws, the Indian laws are not fully capable to stop this crime, fully capable and strict law is needed to stop this crime.

Keywords: Digital Voyeurism, Cyber Voyeurism, Online Voyeurism, Social Media Voyeurism, Creepshots, Upskirting, Cyber Crime, Voyeurism.

OP 188

Stump Appendicitis; it's rare, but still there: A Case Report**Rajesh Chaudhary¹, Ramesh Baharti², Arvind Bhatia³, Ankit Shukla⁴, Munish Kumar⁵
and Maninder Rana⁶**¹MS, Assistant Professor, Department of Surgery, Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru Government Medical College Chamba, HP, India²MS, Professor, Department Of Surgery, Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru Government Medical College Chamba, HP, India³MS, Senior Resident, Department Of Surgery, Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru Government Medical College Chamba, HP, India⁴DNB, Senior Resident, Department Of Surgical Gastroenterology, Jawahar Lal Nehru Institute of Post Graduate Medical Education & Research, Puducherry, India⁵MD, Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru Government Medical College Chamba, HP, India⁶MD, Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru Government Medical College Chamba, HP, India

Abstract: Acute appendicitis is the most common surgical emergency worldwide so, emergency appendectomy is the most performed emergency surgery throughout the world. Intestinal obstruction, intra-abdominal collection, faecal fistula formation and incisional hernias are the complications of appendectomy. Stump appendicitis is one of the rarest complications of appendectomy. World over, only 132 cases have been reported so far. Since the patients have undergone appendectomy, Stump appendicitis is last of any physician's initial diagnoses, leading to mismanagement of such patients. The diagnosis is usually based on the clinical examination which is like those in acute appendicitis but since there is the history of appendectomy, usually another diagnosis is considered first. Ultrasound of the abdomen can pick up Stump appendicitis, but still undiagnosed cases will require the CECT of abdomen for diagnosis. This difficulty and delay in diagnoses may lead to serious complications like perforation of the Caecum and generalised peritonitis. Completion Appendectomy, whether open or laparoscopic, is the treatment of choice. We present the case of a 31-year-old female patient who presented to ED with a RIF pain after 8 months of emergency Appendectomy. She had a history of similar complaints in the past and was previously treated for UTI, 3 months ago. This time she again presented with the signs and symptoms of acute appendicitis and subsequently was diagnosed as stump appendicitis on USG Abdomen. Completion Appendectomy was done. To manage stump appendicitis high index of suspicion, good clinical acumen and surgical expertise is required.

Although the patients can be managed conservatively with antibiotics, Completion Appendectomy is the treatment of choice.

Keywords: Acute Appendicitis, Stump Appendicitis, Acute abdomen, recurrent appendicitis, appendicular remnant.

OP 189**Systematic review on Socket Shield Technique****Lecturer, PhD scholar, Prosthodontics**

Aim: The aim of this review is to evaluate the clinical outcomes of the socket shield technique.

Material and Methods: This review was conducted according to Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta- Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. An electronic search was conducted in four databases: (1) The National Library of Medicine (MEDLINE/PubMed); (2) Web of Science (WOS); (3) SCOPUS; and (4) Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL). The Cochrane Collaboration tool, the Newcastle-Ottawa Quality Assessment Scale and The Joanna Briggs Institute Critical Appraisal tool were used to assess the quality of evidence in the studies reviewed.

Results: Nine articles were included in this review. The studies analysed showed lower rates of horizontal and vertical alveolar bone resorption, better maintenance of the buccal plate, less marginal bone loss and better esthetic results than simple placement of immediate implants. However, a lack of homogeneity was found in evaluation methods of the different outcomes, surgical procedures and prosthetic management.

Conclusions: Based on the results of this review, it is possible to suggest that socket shield technique could be a good alternative in terms of alveolar bone maintenance, marginal bone stability and aesthetic outcomes in immediate implant treatment.

Keywords: Socket shield technique, Aesthetic zone, Clinical outcomes.

OP 190

Lived Experiences of Incarceration: A narrative review

“A prisoner is required to be treated as a human being entitled to all the basic human rights, human dignity and human sympathy”

Kiran Sharma¹ and Dr. Pawan Kumar Sharma²

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Sharda University, Greater Noida, UP

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Sharda University, Greater Noida, UP

Abstract: Crimes are actions that are against the law, are punishable, and may endanger the safety of the community or cause harm to any of its members. The act of imprisoning someone who has committed a crime keeps them confined to a secure area where everyone must abide by the same severe laws. Crime is a manifestation of thoughts in the mind, just like any other physical action. Retribution is no longer seen as the goal of reform as crime is now primarily seen as a societal issue. The scope of detention as a goal of imprisonment is also quite constrained. The ultimate goal of the prison sentence is thought to be the reformation of the criminal. In addition to the criminal side, the hardships of incarceration cause many prisoners to develop mental problems while they are there. The trial period is really stressful for the person. The under trial's mental condition deteriorates if the trial time is prolonged for months or years, which is fairly usual. The predicament is made worse by the difficult life in prison. The above-mentioned prison conditions have a significant negative impact on the quality of life and subjective wellbeing of the defendant. Criminal behavior may be caused by a negative attitude towards the law, which needs to be changed during reforms.

Keywords: Lived Experiences, Incarceration, Prisoners, Incarcerated people, emotional experiences, and Psychological impact of incarceration.

OP 191**Minimally Invasive Implantology: Simo Concept**

Dr. Brajesh Dammani (Professor), Dr. Aparna Barabde (Professor), Dr. Komal Khond (Lecturer) Dr. Ronika Nipane (Lecturer), Dr. Ashwini Shirbhate and Dr. Bhagyashree Thombare (Professor)

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Within the last decades, we are witnessing a noticeable increase in life expectancy worldwide. This trend can be attributed to greater access to health care, as well as innovations in medicine and related fields. As a result, the growth of the elderly population has been shaping health care policies, since this group requires specific care that includes particularities and challenges.

The prevalence of complete tooth loss (edentulism) is still considerable among this age group and it is suggested that this situation will not change in a near future, especially in low-income countries. Conventional complete dentures are commonly used by dentists to treat completely edentulous patients. There have been problems associated with retention and stability while treating completely edentulous mandibular arches compared to maxillary arch. Complete edentulism is a debilitating and irreversible condition. This can lead directly to difficulty in mastication, esthetics and phonetics and indirectly physical, psychological, and social disability. Thus, rehabilitation of edentulism is essential. The treatment modalities of such condition are complete dentures, tooth supported overdentures, implant supported overdentures and implant supported fixed prosthesis. Conventional complete dentures are most commonly used treatment option for treating completely edentulous patients because of ease of fabrication, conservative approach and economical. But in resorbed edentulous condition particularly in mandibular region, the biggest problem with conventional complete dentures is improper retention and stability. Implant supported fixed prosthesis is the best solution for complete edentulism but it requires proper bone support and major surgical procedure. Despite the advances in oral health care of elderly patients and the use and popularization of dental implants as an effective component in oral rehabilitation, this population still faces difficulties on treatment access, which is mainly precluded by financial constraints.

MINIMALLY INVASIVE IMPLANTOLOGY: SIMO CONCEPT is a very good treatment modality to solve this teeth loss (edentulous) predicament.

OP 192

Wheat Quality Evaluation: Physical, Chemical and Functional Properties**Ritika B. Yadav^{1*}, and Jyoti Narwal¹**¹**Department of Food Technology****Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak (Haryana)-India**

Abstract: Wheat is major crop following rice, which is utilized by whole world to fulfil its everyday protein and energy need. The three major types of wheat utilized in modern food preparation are *Triticum aestivum*, *T. compactum*, *T. durum*. Wheat is utilized to prepare many different products all over the world, each product with distinct grain quality requisites. Wheat quality could be evaluated in terms of milling parameter, nutritional value and end – product utilization. The quality parameters require to prepare cookies may not be desirable during preparation of bread. The selection of cultivars for end product utilization depends on the physical, chemical and functional characteristics of the wheat. Physical properties of wheat grain include length, breadth, thickness, equivalent diameter, porosity, bulk density, true density etc. Likewise, chemical characteristics include moisture ash, fat, protein content, fiber carbohydrate present in the wheat grain. The physico-chemical properties (water and oil absorption capacity, solubility, solvent retention capacity (SRC) of wheat flour also play an important role in development of flour based bakery and other processed products. The millers, bakers and cultivators could be considerably utilizing these characteristics to conclude the applicability of wheat. Thus, exact assessment and study of different quality characteristics of wheat cultivar are necessary in the baking and milling industry.

Keywords: Physical, Chemical, Quality, End-use, Milling, Physico-chemical, SRC etc.

OP 193

The Mechanism of Aristotle's Categories in the Study of Knowledge:**An Epistemological Appraisal****Shubham Kumar Mishra****Research Scholar (Ph.D), Department of Philosophy and Religion****Faculty of Arts, Banaras Hindu University,****Varanasi - 221005, UP, India**

Abstract: This paper is a discussion regarding the formulation of knowledge through the lens of Aristotle's epistemology, especially the categories of Aristotle. As we know that Aristotle is one of the most prominent philosophers of all the time. He is a versatile thinker as well as philosopher, who have a wide contribution to every branch of philosophy and beyond it. In his epistemology, the theory of categories plays a vital role to formulate knowledge which maximizes the appropriateness of knowledge, minimizes error and ignorance and it provides a kind of knowledge which is sustainable and multidimensional in nature. The author discusses about the implication of Aristotle's Categories for the formulation of knowledge not confining to the epistemic enterprise of human life rather it functions universally. Suppose, the case is that there are several books in the library has arranged subject-wise. But A wants the book of mathematics, so A should search the book in the section of mathematics only. Because in the library all the books have arranged categorically with refer to the sections. The contention of the paper is to explore Aristotle's categories in epistemic inquiry not in philosophical activities but also in the regular activities of human life. For instance we are living in the era which provides holistic care facilities in medical system, if a patient needs treatment for a particular disease, the patient need not move where and there in the hospital rather the patient suppose to follow the Categorical diagram of the department of medical sciences and consult the doctor with relate to his or her diseases. The author tries to provide a path of understanding of the problem of knowledge and suggested some solution to the specific questions; what are the fundamentals issues in epistemology regarding knowledge formulation? Is Aristotle's categories provides any solution for the general issue on epestimology?

Keywords: Categories, Language, Substance, Reality, knowledge etc.

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Ideas for Humanism; with in perspective of Buddhism**Rinki Mishra****Research Scholar (Ph.D.) Department Of Philosophy and Religion****Faculty of Arts, Banaras Hindu University****Varanasi- 221005, U.P., India**

Abstract: The humanist discover that his religious emotions are represented in a strengthened sense of personal life and in a collaboration effort to enhance social well-being in place of the old attitudes associated with worship prayer. The term humanism firstly introduced in western perspective, because in western approaches humanism denoting holistic existence of human. Humanism is an educational and cultural philosophy that began in the Renaissance when scholars rediscovered Greek and roman classical philosophy and has as its guiding principle the essential dignity of man. Humanism is much used word these days. In fact, the term has gained so much popularity in recent times that every theory and every institution how claims to have a humanistic outlook. Humanism itself is not a recent phenomenon. The intellectual traditions of India, China, the Greeks, and Rome can be found in its roots. The Regveda, which refers to man as the "child of immortality," is the best expression of this desire. According to the Mahabhart, man is the only living creature, and serving him is serving God. In its early years, Buddhism in particular spread a radical humanist ideology.

Keywords: Humanism, Niravana, wisdom, equality, freedom etc.

OP195**Review of Wearable Technology Applications and Advancements**^{1*}Dr. Vandna Bhalla

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Abstract:

Any electronic device which is on the body of the user is termed wearable technology and it incorporates batteries and microprocessors in addition to internet to store data and sync. It can be clothing, medical device, an accessory, a piece of jewelry etc. Advanced examples include the headset used in VR, Microsoft HoloLens, Google Glass, the AI aided hearing aids and likes of such. The modern wearable tech devices include a broader usability spectrum and include Bluetooth headsets, web enabled glasses, fitness trackers and smartwatches. Wearable technologies help monitor behaviors and activities in daily life of users. Body temperature, blood pressure, heart rate, Oxygen saturation are some common parameters that are monitored by wearable sensors. Today wearable technology fulfils many needs in our lives which includes monitoring health, improving general wellbeing, wellness management, rehabilitation, security at workplace, sustain rigorous trainings and many such activities. It is believed that quality and cost of patient care can be substantially reduced by use of such devices. It's envisaged to provide many more innovative solutions in times to come. The wearable technology devices and sensors generate big data which is not only an opportunity for AI researchers but also a challenge. Many concerns like ethics, security, user acceptance still need to be addressed which will eventually enhance popularity, acceptability, functionality, future research, and usability of such devices. In this review we present the current developments and technology advancement in this field especially in healthcare and examine the key challenges.

Keywords- Wearable technology, sensors, healthcare, big data, concerns, ethics, challenges

OP196**Plant Disease Prediction Using Deep Learning**

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Abstract

Agriculture is an important sector of the Indian economy. Farmers' economic growth depends on the quality of products that they produce. But plants are highly susceptible to diseases that affect the growth of the plant, which in turn affects the farmer's income and the quality of the products. In order to detect a plant disease at its very early stages, the use of plant disease prediction techniques is advantageous. Manual prediction of disease in plants is a tedious job that requires great experience. As a result, some computational method that automatically predicts plant disease is required. This prediction tool is much more helpful to the new farmers. This tool uses image processing strategies to assist farmers in all agricultural region. The set of images are given as an input into the Image pre-processing unit. In pre-processing unit, the images are assigned for testing and training in certain ratio. The image is then passed to the evaluation phase. The output features extracted by the model is used to classify the plant disease.

Currently, more and more attention has been paid to plant diseases detection in monitoring the large acres of crops. Monitoring the health of the plants and detecting diseases is crucial for sustainable agriculture. Plant diseases are challenging to monitor manually as it requires a great deal of work, expertise on plant diseases, and excessive processing time. Hence, this can be achieved by utilizing image processing techniques for plant disease detection. These techniques include image acquisition, image filtering, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification.

Convolutional Neural Network's(CNN) are the state of the art in image recognition and have the ability to give prompt and definitive diagnoses. We trained a deep convolutional neural network using 20639 images on 15 folders of diseased and

healthy plant leaves. This project aims to develop an optimal and more accurate method for detecting diseases of plants by analysing leaf images.

Keywords: Plant Disease Detection, Deep Learning, Convolution Neural Network, OpenCV.

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**A RESEARCH ON REPOSITIONING KHADI AS A SUSTAINABLE FASHION
TEXTILE****Vasundhara Saluja¹, Dr Vibha Kapoor²**
¹Sharda University, Uttar Pradesh,
²Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan

Abstract The concept of ‘Sustainability’ is gaining popularity all over the world. The producers as well as consumers are thinking consciously about their lifestyle and the choices they make. Lot of new opportunities are sprouting aligning to this and the world is vowing to the same. Along with the rising consumer consciousness all over the globe the consumers have started giving importance to Sustainability. They have realised their responsibility towards nature and they need to give back what they take from it. Despite of the growing demand towards Sustainable product differing is the situation of one of the ancient textile ‘Khadi’. It is very important for India to not to forget its legacy and rather make efforts to present this high up to the world. This research will identify the position of ‘Khadi’, and its image in the consumer’s mind. The purpose of the research is to strengthen ‘Khadi’ as a Sustainable Fashion textile merchandise so that it fits in the urban life of the modern Indian masses.

Keywords: Khadi; Sustainable Textile; Fashion; Repositioning; Modern Consumer

OP-198**Phytochemical analysis of *Evolvulus alsinoides* Linn in determining its Central nervous system activity****¹Karnam Nithya, ²S.Rajaram, ³P.Sheelaioice.****¹Department Of Pharmacology, MMCRI, Chennai**

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Abstract:

Herbal medicines are used as both conventional and supplementary therapies to specifically treat failing metabolic functioning. Herbal bio-actives are praised for their potency, acceptance, and safety. *Evolvulus alsinoides* is a plant in the Convolvulaceae family and an important medicinal plant. Traditionally, it is used for different ailments in India and other countries and grows in open and grassy places almost throughout India and other subtropical countries.

Various dosage forms and a wide range of original products have been used in the traditional system of medicine and have reported therapeutic activity experimentally and clinically in various scientific journals

It has a variety of pharmacological qualities, including those that aid wound healing, hepatoprotection, cardioprotection, antidiabetic action, memory and learning, and neuroprotection.

The whole plant is utilised in Ayurvedic medicine to treat neurological disorders including amnesia, asthma, and epilepsy as well as hepatoprotective and brain tonic properties.

Keywords: phytochemistry, *evolvulusalsinoides*, Qualitative analysis, Convolvulaceae, brain tonic, GCMS method.

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur was established on 25th August, 1969 by the managing committee constituted under Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur. It is situated in civil lines, the heart of Gorakhpur city in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Days are not far when the college shall be able to realize the vision and the grand mission of the great soul 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj', whose name decorates the identity of the College. His Holiness 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj, former Head Priest of world fame Shree Guru Goraksh nath Temple, Gorakhpur was the founder of the college. He was a pioneer of educational renaissance in Eastern U.P. It was none other than himself who established Maha Rana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur in 1932 to spread the light of knowledge and awareness among the people of Eastern U.P. whom he found to be living in utter poverty, ignorance and backwardness of all kinds. He came to Gorakhnath temple, Gorakhpur at the age of five from the Royal Rana Family of Mewar, Rajasthan in 1900 and grew and learnt the lesson of selfless sacrifice and dedication to the service of humanity under the spiritual care of his accomplished great Guru Yogiraj Gambhir Nathji Maharaj. In 1949-50 Maharana Pratap Degree College was established by "Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad Gorakhpur", which was later sacrificed to contribute to the establishment of Gorakhpur University. Maharana Pratap Degree College along with its entire infrastructure including teaching and non-teaching staff was dedicated to count for the resources to meet up the requirements for establishment of the University of Gorakhpur, in 1958. Post-merger of the Maharana Pratap Degree College into Gorakhpur University, there was a vacuum in the educational facilities of the area. To fill in this vacuum, Digvijai Nath College was established on 25th August 1969. Now the administration of this college is run by the managing committee appointed by Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, under inspiring guidance and patronage of his Holiness Mahant Aditya Nath ji Maharaj. His holiness Gorakshpeethadheeshwar 'Brahmleen Mahant Avedya Nathji Maharaj (the Ex-Head priest of Gorakhnath Temple) and his worthy successor who is the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh His Holiness reverent Yogi Aditya Nath ji maharaj, is the guiding light behind more than four dozen institutions, including D.N.P.G. College Gorakhpur, successfully run by the Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad. The College holds the glory of functioning with four faculty disciplines covering various departments at undergraduate and post graduate levels. College provides education at graduate level in eleven subjects covering Arts, six in Science and Commerce. Post Graduate teaching is offered in Ancient History Archeology & Culture, Geography and Hindi & Modern Indian Language; apart from its renowned Bachelors in Education. In addition to these, part time classes in eight non-practical subjects are also offered and the Institution also serves as an education center of Uttar Pradesh Rajarshi Tandon Open University; and hosts their 26 courses at U.G and P.G. level. In light of letter dated 15 June 2006 from U.P. State Council for Higher Education we revised 'The Self Study Report' on modified format on the basis of guidelines of NAAC-Bangalore. Digvijai Nath P.G. college, Civil lines, Gorakhpur has been placed on the UGC-NAAC approved list in 2021 with B++ grade with C.G.P.A 2.84. Gorakhnath sahyik kendra is established by UP Hindi Sansthan Lucknow in 2019. The institution, guided by the vision of Brahmleen Digvijai Nath Ji Maharaj, is a believer in multi-dimensional development of students.

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Science-Tech Institute (Run by: MKSES Educational Society, Lucknow)

The Science-Tech is one of the premier institutes of Lucknow dedicated to organize various academic activities like conferences, seminars, workshops and training programmes in collaboration with many National & International organizations. The Institute have own Publications house and Journals' to be published Edited books, Course books, research papers and Magazine. The institute is run by by reputed Educational Society named as Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow. The society is working for the development of deprived socio-economic students by providing them quality education. The society is devoted to provide quality education to the poor students in the field of academic and reserch.

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